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Doctoral Dissertation

The ecological role(s) of fungal secondary metabolites and how to unearth them

submitted by

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Affidavit

I hereby declare that I have authored this dissertation independently, and that I have not used any assistance other than that which is permitted. The work contained herein is my own except where explicitly stated otherwise. All ideas taken in wording or in basic content from unpublished sources or from published literature are duly identified and cited, and the precise references included. Any contribution from colleagues is explicitly stated in the authorship statement of the published papers.

I further declare that this dissertation has not been submitted, in whole or in part, in the same or a similar form, to any other educational institution as part of the requirements for an academic degree.

I hereby confirm that I am familiar with the standards of Scientific Integrity and with the guidelines of Good Scientific Practice, and that this work fully complies with these standards and guidelines.

Vienna, January 2023

Andreas SCHÜLLER (manu propria)

This thesis is dedicated to my ever-supportive parents, Monika and Werner

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Abstract

Fungi are important contributors to environmental processes and inhabit every ecosystem on the planet. Their lifestyles range from saprophytic degradation of dead plant or animal material over symbiosis with other organisms to pathogenesis. They produce fitness improving bioactive compounds termed secondary metabolites (SMs). These substances can provide protection against environmental stress conditions or are deployed as weaponry during competition and pathogenesis. There is a high interest in these compounds because some of them find application as pharmaceuticals or in the agricultural and food industry. However, the biosynthesis of these substances by fungi is tightly controlled and limited to situations where they convey a benefit because these substances represent a metabolic and sometimes toxic burden. Hence, most of the SM genes are turned off under laboratory conditions.

During my doctoral thesis, we established an activation tool based on the CRISPR-CAS system using dCas9-VPR which can be used to artificially turn on silent genes in filamentous fungi (publication I). Furthermore, we established a new fungal species, *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer*, for laboratory work and used genetic methods to elucidate the biosynthetic pathway for the SM rasfonin (publication II). In addition to the experimental work, I also present in this thesis a review, where we critically surveyed all available methods for the activation of fungal silent SM gene clusters, including our novel dCas9-VPR activation system (publication III).

The following framework is an extended introduction into the field of fungal SMs focusing on the question on what is known about the different ecological purposes of SMs and on how to unearth their function in future research. In total, I will cover SMs evolution, their regulation and environmental triggers. Lastly, I discuss on how current data and methods can be utilized to study the real ecological purpose of SMs.

Kurzfassung

Pilze leisten einen wichtigen Beitrag in der Umwelt und sind in jedem Ökosystem der Erde zu finden. Ihre Lebensweise reicht vom Abbau von organischem Material über die Symbiose mit anderen Organismen bis hin zur Pathogenese. Sie produzieren bioaktive Verbindungen, die ihre Fitness verbessern und als Sekundärmetaboliten (SM) bezeichnet werden. Diese Stoffe können Schutz vor Umweltstress bieten oder als Waffen gegen andere Organismen eingesetzt werden. Das Interesse an diesen Verbindungen ist groß, da einige von ihnen als Pharmazeutika oder in der Agrar- und Lebensmittelindustrie Verwendung finden könnten. Die Biosynthese dieser Stoffe ist durch den Pilz jedoch streng reguliert, da diese eine metabolische und manchmal toxische Belastung darstellen. Daher sind die meisten SM-Gene unter Laborbedingungen abgeschaltet.

Im Rahmen meiner Doktorarbeit haben wir auf der Grundlage des CRISPR-CAS-Systems, unter Verwendung von dCas9-VPR, eine Methode entwickelt, mit der inaktive Gene in Pilzen künstlich aktiviert werden können (Publikation I). Außerdem haben wir die Pilzart *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* für Laborarbeiten etabliert und den Biosyntheseweg für den SM Rasfonin aufgeklärt (Publikation II). Zusätzlich zu den experimentellen Arbeiten präsentiere ich einen Review, in der wir alle verfügbaren Methoden zur Aktivierung von inaktiven SM-Genclustern in Pilzen, einschließlich dCas9-VPR, kritisch untersucht haben (Publikation III).

Die folgende Rahmenschrift ist eine erweiterte Einführung in das Gebiet der Pilz- SMs, welche sich auf die Frage konzentriert, was über die verschiedenen ökologischen Rollen von SMs bekannt ist und welche Möglichkeiten es gibt, ihre Funktion in der zukünftigen Forschung aufzudecken. Insgesamt werde ich die Entwicklung der SMs, ihre Regulierung und ihre Auslöser in der Umwelt behandeln. Abschließend werde ich erörtern, wie aktuelle Daten und Methoden genutzt werden können, um den tatsächlichen ökologischen Zweck von SMs zu untersuchen.

1 Introduction

1.1 Bioactive Compounds: The Fungal Toolbox

Fungi can be found in any ecosystem on the planet. Some of them can even live in harsh environments like solar salterns [1], permafrost [2] or crude oil [3] and some even surpassed the threshold temperature of other eukaryotes, growing at up to 62°C [4]. They adopt different lifestyles that suit various ecological niches. Saprophytes excel at degrading dead animal and plant biomass. They have the capabilities of producing a wide range of enzymes that can break down materials like keratin [5] or complex polymer structures like cellulose or lignin [6] to utilize them as nutrient source [7]. Fungi can have several relationships to other organisms, ranging from pathogenic over commensalistic to mutual beneficial symbiosis with plants, animals and other microorganisms [7]. Some symbiotic plant associated fungi are even obligatory biotroph which means that they are dependent on the host and cannot survive outside of their host tissue. There are also various inter-fungal interactions and also relationships between fungi and bacteria, like the parasitic invasion of another fungus (mycoparasitism) or the mutualistic beneficial symbiosis between fungus and bacteria (lichens) [7]. These rough divisions into fungal lifestyles is however very blurred as fungi can also sometimes adopt to other forms depending on the environmental conditions (i.e. switches of saprophytic or commensalistic to a pathogenic lifestyle or host specific lifestyles [8]) [7]. Fungal organisms can either grow as single cells like yeasts or form a network (i.e. mycelium) of connected cells named hyphae. Hyphal growth enables polarized growth towards nutrient sources or away from potential threats and is also important for mating, host invasion and alignment and formation of structures like appressoria and sexual fruiting bodies [9]. Figure 1 illustrates the diversity of habitats and hosts of fungi and also their role as saprophyte, pathogen and endophyte and also the sometimes-occurring switches from one lifestyle to another.

Figure 1 Illustration of some ecological habitats of fungi. A: microbial interactions and hosts of (filamentous) fungi. Saprophytic fungi are drawn in dark grey. Pathogenic fungi are drawn in black. Mutualistic beneficial fungi are drawn in blue. Transitions of one lifestyle to another are marked by a colour switch (i.e. saprophytic → pathogenic: grey → black). Competition between fungi is marked by an interaction zone of both colours (i.e. blue vs. black within tree tissue) B: Different ecological niches and climate zones that can be inhabited by fungi in general and sometimes also the same fungal species. A possible pathway of transition between environmental zones is illustrated by bird migration but can occur by various other events as well. Fungi of the same species that live in different ecological niches or environments can show fast diversification of their BGC arsenal.

The most prominent fungi are the bakers' and brewers' yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* [10], plant endophytes, symbioses in form of lichens or algae [11], the fruiting body above the soil of basidiomycetes like the chanterelle, toadstool or porcino [11] or the filamentous fungi that are used for the production of cheese like Camembert, Gorgonzola or Roquefort [12], fermenting fungi like *Aspergillus oryzae* for soy sauce [13] or *Aspergillus niger* for citric acid [14] and fungi that are deployed for various pharmaceuticals [15,16].

But fungi do not always have beneficial effects for humans. They also infest, contaminate and toxify our foods (e.g., the black bread mold *Rhizopus stolonifera* [17]), plants (e.g. *Fusaria*, *Aspergilli*) [18] and livestock (e.g., *Trichophyton sp.*, *Candida sp.*) [19].

The majority of agricultural plant diseases like the bakanae disease in rice plants (*Fusarium fujikuroi*) [20] or the head blight disease of wheat (*Fusarium graminearum*) [21,22] are caused by fungi. Other devastating pathogens within the agricultural food sector are the rice blast fungus *Magnaporthe oryzae* [23], *Botrytis cinera* [24] which has a broad plant host-range, *Colletotrichum* sp. which is a necrotrophic pathogen that infects many crop plants [25] or *Aspergillus flavus* which contaminates stored wheat and produces the mycotoxin aflatoxin which leads to severe damage of the liver upon consumption [26]. There are also plant pathogenic species that are beneficial for humans. *Botrytis cinera* is not only a pathogen with broad host-range but is sometimes considered a noble rot that infects grapes which are used for special wines [24]. The corn smut fungus *Ustilago maydis* forms prominent structures (fungal gall) after infecting corn cobs which are considered a delicacy especially in Mexican and Latin American cuisine [27]. Fungi also establish many mutualistic beneficial interactions with plants, especially their rhizome. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, which are mostly associated with grasses, extend their hyphae past the depletion zone of the roots and promote the uptake of phosphorous and also nitrogen by the plant. They have limited abilities of saprotrophic degradation of organic matter and mostly scavenge nutrients that have been released by other microbes. In some cases it was shown that they also convey resistance against various plant pathogenic organisms [28]. In contrast, ectomycorrhizal fungi which are predominantly associated with trees, excel at saprotrophic degradation of organic matter. They form tight interactions with the tip of the roots from which they extend their hyphal network. As saprophytes, they can access and degrade nutrient sources that are not available to arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi [29,30].

Some fungi cause human diseases. While yeasts, like the common skin fungus *Candida* [31], can lead to normally well-treatable infections like cutaneous or vaginal candidiasis, there are also highly problematic and often lethal infections by fungi like *Aspergillus fumigatus* which can infest the lung of immune-compromised patients (i.e. *Aspergillosis*) [32].

These few examples already showcase the immense diversity of the fungal kingdom on our planet and their beneficial but also detrimental role for humanity. But what are the reasons for some fungi being toxic and others being beneficial for humans. Or can one and the same fungus be beneficial and harmful at the same time?

One of the reasons, fungi are so adaptable to different environments are substances which they can selectively produce and which give them advantages in their environment. These substances are, per definition, not essential for growth or primary metabolism but provide an advantage against other competitors or against environmental conditions. These so-called natural products or SMs are very diverse in their structure as well as their physiological effect and hence also in their ecological role. They comprise mycotoxins, antibiotics, plant hormones, facilitators of metal ion uptake (e.g. siderophores), melanin for UV protection, and so on. For more detailed information about SMs, please read publication III [33] and other reviews [34-36]

Because fungi often have many silent BGCs it cannot be ruled out that, theoretically, also a beneficial fungus bears the risk of producing mycotoxins or antibiotics. In fact, *A. oryzae* which is used for the production of soy sauce, sake and alike, indeed carries a BGC that is homologous to the aflatoxin BGC [37]. Similarly, in varieties of the blue cheese fungus *Penicillium camemberti* the homolog BGC for cyclopiazonic acid could be found [38]. But of course, a fermented consumer good would not exist if it showed acute toxicity. The key to fungi being used for food applications is the process of domestication. Over thousands of years, selective propagation of beneficial traits led to fungi that grow faster on the fermentation substrate (i.e. milk, soy, etc.), contribute to a good texture and taste and also are incapable of producing toxins [39-41].

These are just a few examples to get an overview about the fast adaption to fungi to their environment and the resulting impact on human life. In the next paragraphs, I will shortly explain how SMs are encoded within the genome and how they are regulated. I will present further examples for the ecological role of SMs within the fungal kingdom, explain how (fast) they evolve and deteriorate and discuss on how the research community could elicit the ecological role of the metabolite for the producing fungus.

The blueprints of SMs and their evolution: Biosynthetic gene Clusters:

To understand the evolution and diversification but also the regulation, biosynthesis, and artificial activation of SMs, it is important to know the genomic background. The blueprints for these bioactive compounds are stored in so-called secondary metabolite or biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs). Most of the time, BGCs are comprised by an array of genes that are physically linked within the genome and are co-regulated. These genes have different purposes. At its

core, BGCs have a backbone-, or key-enzyme encoding gene. These genes code for synthases that determine the backbone structure of the SM and hence the compound class. Common classes are polyketides (PKS; synthesised by highly or non-reducing polyketide synthases), non-ribosomal peptides (NRPS), terpenes (synthesised by terpene cyclases), prenylated tryptophane derivatives and ergot alkaloids (dimethylallyltryptophan synthase)[34,42,43]. Most BGCs have one backbone gene but also more than one (see publication II (currently under review; [44]) and even a combination of different classes have been reported [45]. The backbone structure is then modified by so-called decoration or tailoring enzymes which add or remove certain chemical residues, which is one of the reasons for the chemical diversity of SMs. Apart from the genes that synthesise the compound, other genes that code for transporters, transcription factors and resistance genes can be part of a BGC [34,46,47]. BGCs can considerably vary in size and can reach a gene count of up to ~30 genes as published for the aflatoxin/ sterigmatocystin BGC of in the genus *Aspergillus sp.* [48]. There are of course also exceptions. In case of PKS8 from *Fusarium graminearum* [49], it was shown that only the backbone enzyme alone is required for the production of gibberycins. On the other hand, the BGCs that is responsible for the production of kojic acid in *Aspergillus oryzae* [50] does not contain a classic backbone enzyme. There also studies that observed a compound being synthesised by multiple BGCs (i.e., supercluster [51]) or also vice versa, that one BGC is responsible for 2 different compounds (i.e., pathway crosstalk [52]). Of course, the possibility that so far unresearched fungal species harbour yet unknown BGC types, cannot be excluded.

1.2 Regulation of BGCs:

The synthesis of SMs is tightly regulated via transcriptional regulators, and also on the chromatin level via facultative or constitutive heterochromatin as reviewed in publication III [33] and also on the epigenetic level via DNA methylation [53,54].

There are multiple factors that make this tight synthetic regulation necessary. The synthesis of these compounds requires basic building blocks like acyl-CoAs (e.g., acetyl-CoA, malonyl-CoA, propionyl-CoA) or amino acids that, on the one hand, are shared with metabolites from the primary metabolic cycle and, on the other hand, also need energy in form of ATP and NADPH for their production. Furthermore, not only the precursors have to be synthesised, also the whole BGC has to be transcribed, translated and the proteins correctly folded and post translationally processed which again requires energy and resources. Producing SMs is therefore very energy consuming and has the potential to deplete important precursor pools for growth related and developmental processes and other BGCs [55,56]. Additionally, some

bioactive substances also elicit stress in the host, as for instance antibiotic substances. It therefore is logic that the biosynthesis of these bioactive compounds is tightly regulated and only commences under very specific conditions. Otherwise, the immense energy consumption would interfere with fungal growth and therefore overall lower fitness and competitiveness in the environment.

In around 50 % of the predicted BGCs one or more pathway specific transcription factors could be aligned. Transcriptional regulators are responsible for the controlled regulation of genes within a BGC. Examples are AfIR which regulates the sterigmatocystin BGC of *Aspergillus nidulans* [57] and Tri6 which regulates the trichothecene BGC in *Fusarium sporotrichioides* [34,58]. There are also global transcription factors, like VeA or LaeA [59] or MtfA [60], which are conserved between species and genera and regulate BGCs on a broad scale dependent on various environmental signals including, but not limited to light (Velvet [59]) or nutrient starvation (CreA [61], AreA [62], RimO[63]) or pH (PacC [64]) [33].

On a higher hierarchical level, regulation of BGCs is achieved by chromatin modifications. The nuclear DNA in eukaryotes is tightly packed by nucleosomes which consist of 4 homodimers of histone proteins (i.e., H2A, H2B, H3, H4). These histones can be modified on specific residues on their N-terminal tails. The most studied and best understood modifications are methylation, acetylation and phosphorylation. These modifications can then be read, erased and also written by specific enzymes or enzyme complexes which influences the accessibility of the DNA and can also lead to the recruitment of proteins and protein complexes which can bind to specific histone modifications [65,66]. The silencing of genes or whole genomic regions – also in fungi - can be accomplished by methylation of H3K9 and H3K27 which leads to tightly packaging of the nucleosomes by respective reader proteins heterochromatin protein 1 (HP1) and polycomb repressive complex 2 (PRC2), respectively [33,34,54,65-68]. These structures are called heterochromatin and reduce the accessibility of the DNA for proteins like transcription factors or members of the transcriptional machinery. Reversal of this process is achieved by pioneering factors that can enter these structures and alter the modification pattern on the histones to form an open chromatin formation called euchromatin which is related to active transcription. In most fungi and most other eukaryotes, there are two different silencing machineries. PRC2 is responsible for histone 3 lysine 27 trimethylation (H3K27me3) which leads to the formation of facultative heterochromatin, a reversible form of heterochromatin [33,34,54,65-68]. In case of *Neurospora crassa*, it was shown that H3K27 methylation is also involved in subtelomeric silencing and that a short array of telomere repeats (i.e., (TTAGGG)₁₇) is causal for large domain silencing via H3K27 methylation [69]. Genomic regions that are silenced this way can be reactivated once the corresponding signal is received.

The other way of chromatin silencing is H3K9me3 which is performed by an interplay of the lysine methyl-transferase KMT1 (Clr4 in *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*, ClrD in *A. nidulans*) and HP1 (HepA in *A. nidulans*) [67,70]. After the deposition of H3K9me3 by KMT1, HP1 can bind to the modified chromatin and initiate the next round of trimethylation which leads to a spreading of the mark across the silenced region [65,66,68]. This form of chromatin is called constitutive heterochromatin which is normally a permanent silencing mechanism coinciding with repetitive elements at the telomere ends. In *Aspergillus* and *Neurospora crassa* it was shown that H3K9me3 is involved in the silencing at telomere ends. Because many BGCs are near telomeres, regulation by chromatin and positioning within the genome is an important layer of regulation of BGCs [71,72].

During evolution, some fungi lost the ability for H3K27me3 and are devoid of the whole PRC2 machinery like in case of *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* [73], *Ustilago* [74] and some yeasts [75]. It was shown however, that *A. nidulans* can utilize the constitutive heterochromatin pathway via H3K9me3 and ClrD to regulate the transcription of the sterigmatocystin BGC in a facultative way [72]. The same was shown for *Epichloe festucae* which showed different H3K9 and H3K27 methylation patterns and also expression at the lolitrem and ergot alkaloid BGC depending on cultivation type (in planta vs axenic) [76]. This showcases that chromatin regulation is also an important layer of BGC regulation.

For more information about BGC regulation via chromatin please read publication III [33] which is a review about the regulation and artificial activation of fungal BGCs.

1.3 Evolution of BGCs:

There are generally three evolutionary phases of a BGC, as reviewed by Rokas et al. 2018 [77]. Formation, maintenance, and degradation as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Formation, maintenance and degradation of a BGC during evolution. The plot shows “time” vs. “fitness contribution” of a given BGC and indicates if the BGC is under positive or negative selection. During the assembly phase (P1; orange) genome rearrangements, mutations and duplication and/or activity of transposable elements can result in the formation of clustered genes that start to co-evolve together and increase the fitness level of the host. At the end of this phase, the formed BGC is fully functional and contributes an essential part to the fitness of the host. The BGC transitions into the maintenance phase (P2; green) and experiences purifying selection or even positive selection and further BGC modification (P2; cyan) to increase the fitness of the host. If the BGC loses its fitness contributing effect due to environmental changes that make the BGC obsolete, negative selection can set in and lead to the degradation of the BGC (P3, magenta).

Several mechanisms can lead to the formation of a BGC. In most cases, gene duplications and relocations of host genes to the same locus initiate the establishment of a new BGC. In other cases, whole BGCs [78] or even pathogenicity mediating small accessory chromosomes [79] can be transferred by horizontal gene transfer [80,81] from bacteria to fungi [82] or between fungal species [83]. Evidence of such events exist as it was shown in case of an accessory chromosome of *Fusarium oxysporum* that is essential for pathogenicity and also conveys pathogenicity to the non-pathogenic strain [84] or in case of the ~54 kb

sterigmatocystin cluster which was reportedly transferred from *Aspergillus* to *Podospora* by horizontal gene transfer [78].

Mutations of the co-located genes by natural selection then drive the development of a fully functional BGC. In contrast to other genes, the majority of BGCs was shown to be located in polymorphic regions of the genome that develop at a faster pace as the rest of the genome (i.e. syntenic blocks). This is related to the genomic positioning, vicinity of transposable elements (TEs) and selective pressure. BGCs are often located in sub-telomeric regions which are rich in repetitive elements and TEs, are often silenced by heterochromatin and are also known to be hotspots for recombination [68,85-87]. Observations that support the theory of TEs being involved in BGC positioning are for instance the occurrence of homolog BGCs that are at different genomic locations across closely related species as shown for the botrydial BGC which was found to be identical but at 4 different genomic region across 7 investigated *Botrytis* species (flanked by TEs) [88] or another observation where the same genomic locus was occupied by different BGCs (i.e., idiomorph polymorphism) within different *Aspergillus fumigatus* strains [89].

Because BGCs are relevant to the fitness of the fungus they experience a strong positive and negative selective pressure. This ensures that the fungus spends as much energy and resources as needed but at the same time as little as possible to efficiently compete against other microorganisms and sustain adverse environmental conditions. Negative selective pressure also relates to the black queen hypothesis [90] which states that adaptive gene loss and genome reductive evolution can be an important driver for increasing host fitness due to reduced metabolic burden and also to prevent other microorganisms from having a benefit from the produced metabolite. In support of this hypothesis, it could be observed that some plant-associated obligate biotrophic fungi have a reduced number of functional genes and show significant loss of BGCs when compared to necrotrophic pathogens [91]. Further information about organization and evolution of BGCs can be retrieved from publication III [33]

Interestingly the regulation of BGCs follows a different evolutionary pattern. During a comparison between different *Aspergillus* species it became apparent, that the conserved proteins VeA and MtfA which are regarded as master regulators of secondary metabolism and in case of VeA also sexual development and light regulation regulate conserved processes (i.e. secondary metabolism) but that the underlying SM genes and pathways are not conserved and mostly species specific [92]. This means that while BGCs are developing at a fast pace and are mostly unique to their species, many are regulated by conserved transcriptional regulatory networks. This finding highlights the importance of genome positioning and clustering of BGCs for regulation. Supporting evidence came during an experiment in *Aspergillus parasiticus*, where the authors observed that integration of one synthesis gene nor-

1 of the aflatoxin BGC at two distinct loci outside of the BGC drastically reduced or abolished the aflatoxin biosynthesis [93]. Although there are examples where two separated BGCs are responsible for the synthesis of one compound (i.e., cluster crosstalk) [52], the majority of SMs are produced by only single BGC. Cluster crosstalk could be an evolutionary transition event, where a BGC got dispersed to different locations in the genome. Initially, the genes of the BGC are still co-regulated but because of the separation, the co-evolution of the individual parts of the BGC could diverge over time (i.e. diversifying selection [81]) and lead to separate BGCs with different compounds and independent regulation.

Gene regulation by transcriptional activators or activator complexes can also undergo the process of regulatory rewiring [92]. This leads to either a shift in regulation of target genes or the loss or gain of regulatory targets. Rewiring can happen on the DNA but also protein level. On DNA level, acquisition or loss or mutation of a cis-regulatory element can alter DNA specificity or enable or disable binding by the transcriptional regulator. On the protein level, the domains for DNA binding or activation/repression or protein interaction can acquire mutations which alter the respective behavior [94-98]. As stated above, 50% of the BGCs contain a pathway-specific transcription factor but overexpression experiments in *A. nidulans* showed that most of them do not upregulate the BGC they are located in [99]. This phenomenon could indicate that the regulator is experiencing a form of rewiring and currently has no, or other target genes.

During the maintenance phase of BGCs, the functionality and integrity of the BGC is conserved [77,100]. Following the natural selection during formation, BGCs can either be subject to purifying selection or they can evolve even further (e.g. expression rate, compound modifications, ...). In this phase the BGC is actively contributing to the fitness of the host. In case of plant pathogenic fungi this can be seen as arms race between fungal and plant host. This interaction promotes a fast co-evolution of plant defence mechanisms and fungal effectors and SMs which aim to circumvent plant defences and promote plant tissue invasion and propagation. This also contributes significantly to the host-specificity of fungal pathogens [7].

In case the selective pressure is lifted (i.e., the BGC does not convey any fitness improving effect anymore due to change of environment or environmental conditions) or negative selection occurs (see "black queen hypothesis" [90]), the BGC starts to degrade. This can happen via wholesale cluster loss or otherwise deleterious mutations or genomic rearrangements which inactivate the BGC [77,89,101].

All these observations are based on the model of selective pressure. During all three phases, any kind of deleterious mutation or silencing of the BGC can happen but isolates that carry fitness decreasing mutations are unlikely to survive and therefore cannot be observed.

1.4 Does the SM arsenal mirror the fungal lifestyle?

Genome analysis show that, in average, fungi possess the blueprints for up to over 80 substances [102]. Although there are overlaps and similarities between species of the same genera, the majority of these substances are unique to their host and the chemical diversity increases even more between genera [103,104]. Even within species, it was proven that ecotypes of these SMs exist, meaning that fungi from the same species which were isolated from different ecological systems developed their own adaption of their chemical repertoire [105]. The versatility of fungal species and their adaptability to the environment transformed them into specialists that manifest in various pathogenic, commensalistic, symbiotic [106] and saprophytic lifestyles [107,108].

Phyto-hormones:

Plant associated fungi form mutualistic (beneficial for both), commensalistic (beneficial only for fungus) but also parasitic (decrease of host fitness by fungal pathogen) relationships [109]. Independent of the interaction, plant-associated fungi possess the ability to produce an array of phytohormones like auxins (e.g., indole acetic acid), cytokinines, gibberellins, jasmonate, japonic acid, abscisic acid and ethylene or produce effectors that interfere with these pathways within the host. Phytohormones have various, often interconnected roles in plants. They can alter plant growth and resistance and therefore induce beneficial but also detrimental effects in the host plant [110,111]. They mostly influence development like in case of auxins (cell division, differentiation and organ formation, senescence), cytokinines (root and shoot formation, regulation of cell cycle and cell differentiation, interplay with auxin), ethylene (senescence, germination, flowering, fruit maturation, inhibition of root and shoot growth) or gibberellic acid (e.g. germination, flowering, cell division, internode elongation) but they also mediate (a)biotic stress responses like abscisic acid (drought tolerance, seed dormancy, interplay with gibberellic acid pathway.) and the biotic stress response compounds salicylic acid and jasmonic acid [110,112].

Although it was shown that also non-plant- associated fungi produce phytohormones, like *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* [113], pathways for phytohormone production are biased towards plant-associated species because they play a pivotal role during colonization and also after invasion.

For example, Auxins, like indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), are involved in a wide variety of developmental processes in plants such as cell division, organ formation and cell differentiation and play an important role during stress response [110,114-116]. Beneficial and pathogenic

fungi are producing auxins during their interaction with plants. Auxin leads to the production of expansins by the plant which is a key regulator during cell wall extension. It loosens the cell wall integrity and therefore makes the plant more vulnerable for colonization which is a prerequisite for pathogenic fungi but also mycorrhizal fungi [110,117-122]. The importance of auxin in the latter case was shown during the colonization of *Pinus pinaster* by *Hebeloma cylindrosporum* [121,122] where expression of auxins resulted in increased root invasion but did not interfere with growth of the host which suggests that auxin has a role during establishment of the host colonization in this case.

The role of auxin during pathogenicity was experimentally investigated in case of the plant pathogenic fungus *Fusarium oxysporum*. Increased expression of auxin pathway genes led to hypervirulence in Broomrapes (*Orobancha sp.*) [123]. In case of the stem rust fungus *Puccinia graminis f. sp. tritici*, silencing of an auxin gene led to decreased pathogenicity [124]. Similar to pathogenic fungi, many beneficial endophytes also produce auxins to support plant growth and stress response of the host [125]. Auxins however do not only have effects on the host plant but also on the fungi themselves. The impact of auxins varies a lot in a species and sometimes also concentration dependent manner. In case of the chickpea pathogen *Fusarium delphinoides*, low concentrations of auxin lead to increased hyphal growth while high concentration had a growth impeding effect [126]. In the human pathogen *Candida albicans*, it was shown that auxin treatment triggers the transition from yeast like growth to hyphal growth [127]. In the tomato pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum* [128], auxin led to reduced spore germination while in case of *Neurospora crassa* [129,130], the opposite effect was the case.

Similar to auxins, many other phytohormone pathways exist and their variety and role during plant-microbe interaction is vast. Fungi and host plant both produce these substances in an orchestrated way and also in response to each other's presence. Many fungal pathogens but also beneficial endophytes make use of the same pathways to facilitate beneficial but also detrimental effects on the host. It therefore cannot be told with certainty if a fungus is mutually beneficial or a pathogen by only looking at its potential arsenal of phytohormones. Factors like time, concentration, phytohormone composition and developmental stage and tissue of the plant all play important roles which determine if a certain interaction is pathogenic or beneficial to the plant. A good example is the colonization of *Arabidopsis thaliana* roots, by the mutualistic beneficial basidiomycete *Piriformospora indica* [131,132]. *P. indica* produces the SM gibberellin to suppress host defence and promote colonization of the root system which would suggest a pathogenic lifestyle. However, after colonization, the fungus can confer resistance against abiotic stresses and diseases and also mediates the supply and uptake of phosphorous from the soil [133].

Similarly, the phytopathogenic rice blast fungus *Magnaporthe oryzae*, also evades plant defence by secreting the hydroxylated form of jasmonic acid (12OH-JA). In contrast to methylated jasmonic acid, which is responsible for host defence, 12OH-JA regulates flower and tuber development but prevents normal jasmonic acid signaling. Therefore *M. oryzae* uses plant hormones to facilitate invasion. Even after invasion, the enzyme that is responsible for JA conversion, Abm, is secreted to further suppress host immunity and promote further tissue colonization by the fungus [134].

It should be noted in this context that, in addition to SMs, cell wall degrading enzymes (CWDEs) also play an important role during processes that involve SMs like the pathogenic infection or endophytic colonization of plants or the degradation of dead plant material in saprophytes. During infection, CWDEs penetrate the outer defence layer of the plant while fungal effectors and other SMs are deployed for evasion or manipulation of plant defence responses [135]. Plant associated fungi that rely on these mechanisms also show a wider and more diverse array of CWDEs within their genome which is an additional indicator of their lifestyle [136]. This is also true for mycoparasitic fungi, like some *Trichoderma* species as they need to degrade the fungal cell wall of their competitor or prey as part of their antifungal lifestyle [137].

Melanins:

Melanins are a structurally very diverse groups of coloured polyphenols (pigments) which serve various purposes during the lifecycle of a fungus. Their fundamental function is the protection against biotic and abiotic stresses. They can be structural cell wall elements, provide protection against UV and other radiation, mediate thermo-tolerance, protect against desiccation, are deployed as radical ion scavengers and play an important role during plant and animal pathogenesis and also during development of pathogenicity or reproduction related structures like appressoria, sclerotia and conidia [138-142]. Melanins are present across all phyla of the fungal kingdom. The multitude of biosynthetic pathways and precursors for melanins mirror their importance within each ecosystem and throughout evolution and they are seen as important adaptation mechanism against environmental changes [143]. Some fungi constitutively produce melanins, which are termed melanotic fungi (often also called black or brown fungi) and others only conditionally synthesize them, which are called facultative melanotic. Interestingly, species which occupy habitats of extreme conditions, as reviewed by Cordero and Casadevall 2017 [138] and also Gostinčar et al. 2012 [144], often are melanotic and are called brown or black fungi.

Antimicrobials and mycotoxins:

Many fungi can produce antimicrobial substances. The simplest way of interpreting the occurrence of such substances is the generic competition against other microbes or organisms for protection of the fungus and their surrounding resources. The enniatin beauvericin is a known food contaminant and shows a multitude of activities against humans, insects, cancer cell lines, gram positive and negative bacteria and other microbes and even HIV-1 and plasmodium. Its wide range of activity is based on its ionophoric activity which facilitates the membrane permeability for calcium ions and also causes oxidative stress and cell death. It is produced by many fungi including species from the *Fusarium* genus and also by *Beauveria bassiana*, a known insect pathogen that is also used as biocontrol agent [145,146]. The true nature of the compound and its ecological significance for the producing fungi is not yet established but the fact that it is not toxic against the producer but against many other microbes and animals suggests that it is more of a general chemical weapon against competitors.

The more specific these substances act, the more information about the importance and deployment area can be deduced. In case of antibiotics this can often be a very straight forward process. In case of substances that specifically inhibit the cell wall synthesis of gram-positive bacteria (e.g. penicillin [147]) or antibacterial substances that are triggered by a specific bacteria, like in case of bikaverin from *Fusarium spp.* which is produced when the fungus is confronted with the bacterium *Ralstonia solanacearum* [148], the ecological role seems obvious. In case of toxins that target very conserved and essential cellular processes, the presence of endogenous defence mechanisms, like transporters or resistance genes coding for detoxifying enzymes or resistant protein homologs, clearly indicate that the main purpose of these substances is the general suppression of other organisms [47,149]. One such case would be the immunosuppressant mycophenolic acid which targets the inosine-5'-monophosphate dehydrogenase. This essential enzyme is responsible for the synthesis of guanine nucleotides. To protect itself from this self-originated compound *Penicillium brevicompactum*, has a gene that codes for a resistant copy of the target protein. Upon heterologous expression in *Aspergillus nidulans*, the expression host became resistant to mycophenolic acid [150]. For some of these compounds, their role in the lifecycle, apart from mere toxicity, has been investigated as for instance in case of the *Aspergillus fumigatus*. This opportunistic human pathogen causes invasive aspergillosis, an infection of the mammalian lung. The mycotoxin gliotoxin was shown to be a major virulence factor. This toxin causes oxidative stress, inhibits NFκB, and induces apoptosis in various cell types which supports invasion of lung tissue by the hyphae [151]. As self-protection mechanism, the resistance conveying protein GliT is synthesised alongside with gliotoxin. Although the biological relevance during host pathogenesis is verified and also targets and effects could be

determined, the ancestral function is presumably connected to redox homeostasis and antimicrobial defence [47]. This suggests that the role in pathogenicity evolved as side-effect of its protective and defence function.

The capability of microorganisms to produce toxic substances against competitors or their prey is not surprising but sometimes the real ecological effect behind the toxin is not so easy to perceive. Not always is the fungus the direct benefactor of the toxic product. For example, *Neotyphodium coenophialum* which colonizes the grass species *Festuca arundinacea* promotes plant resistance against nematodes and produces the SM ergovaline which is toxic to feeding animals and has the effect of protecting the grass from overgrazing by ruminants. In return, the plant provides support for the fungal reproduction by vertically transmitting the endophyte by infected seeds [152,153]. The production of ergovaline certainly contributes to the fitness of the endophyte, but whether it is the only ecological purpose would need more research and can never be answered with full certainty.

Also, many endophytes (i.e., fungi that live part of or their whole live within plant tissue) can produce antimicrobial substances. It is however interesting to see that some obligate endophytes, which are not capable of surviving outside of the host plant, have a significantly reduced capability of producing SMs compared to other species [91].

Plant pathogens were also shown to produce non-host-selective toxins. These non-host-specific toxins interfere with general pathways like chloroplast formation, or inhibition of the electron transport chain. Therefore, they show an effect on many plants, also outside of the pathogens host range, but most often have just mild impact on plant health. They are seen as an additional disease factor that is not essential for host infection or progress of the disease and therefore, they cannot be seen as an indicator for the expanse of the host range [154]. Apart from phytohormones and non-host-selective toxins, pathogens have developed host specific ways of manipulation. Host-selective toxins (predominantly low molecular weight compounds or cyclic peptides) are mainly described for fungi from the order of *Pleosporales*, especially by species from the genus *Alternaria* and *Cochliobolus*. As the name suggests, these toxins or effector are customized to a specific host and will not work on other plants [154]. Many of these HSTs are located on so-called accessory chromosomes which confer host-specificity upon acquisition. These are probably the BGCs with the most easily perceivable ecological role. Witte et al. describes different host specific BGCs on accessory chromosomes in their review [79]. For instance, the AAL-toxin is encoded on such an accessory chromosome which is only present in tomato pathogenic strains of *A. alternata* (i.e. *A. alternata* f. sp. *Lycopersici*). The same is true for the ACR toxin (i.e. rough lemon and rangpur lime pathotype) [79]. Although most described host-selective-toxins are located on accessory chromosomes, there are also examples for host-selective toxins that are not related

to accessory chromosomes as for instance victorin, which causes Victoria blight in oats and is a cyclic peptide produced by *Cochliobolus victoriae* [154,155].

Special Case: The “Zombie Ant”- Fungus

There are also cases of very specific pathogen-host interactions between fungi and insects. The fungal genus *Ophiocordyceps sp.*, commonly known as “zombie ant fungus”, is known for infecting and manipulating ants [156]. After infection, the fungus perturbs the central nervous system. Thereafter, the infected ants leave the colony and lock themselves to twigs or leaves via a so-called death grip of their mandibular. The mandibular where shown to have different metabolite compositions when compared to ants that have been infected with a non behavior manipulating fungus *Beauveria bassiana* [157]. After that, the ant dies but stays firmly attached to the plant tissue. Subsequently, the fungus builds fruiting bodies which disperses spores. A study which investigated the host- pathogen interaction and host range between *Ophiocordyceps unilateralis sensu lato* and the carpenter ant species *Camponotus castaneus* and *C. americanus* found, that, although the fungus can infect and kill various species, they only trigger the behavioural changes within their specific hosts and also only then, the fruiting body is being built. Secondary metabolomics showed that several compounds are exclusively produced during the interaction with the specific host [156].

Although these examples are just a fragment of the available data, they already illustrate that the secondary metabolome can contain very specific compounds that are also a defining part of the fungal lifestyle like in case of the “zombie ant” fungus. Metabolites like melanin’s or antibiotics are present in nearly every fungal genome and fulfil a more generic role as protectant or chemical weapon. There are general trends that can indicate the preferred eco-system of a fungus like the existence of phytohormone BGCs or presence of accessory chromosomes in plant associated fungi or observations of patterns on the genomic level. For instance, obligate plant endophytes sometimes have a strongly reduced BGC arsenal while necrotrophic host restricted plant pathogens can have a reduced genome size or in case of some biotrophic plant pathogens which have a reduced gene count (i.e. parasitic genome reduction) or saprophytes and mycoparasitic or plant associated fungi which often are enriched in genes for cell wall degrading enzymes [7,154,158]. Although these general trends which showcase the existence of life-style specific sets of BGCs exist, the picture cannot be drawn in black and white. Many exceptions and also lifestyle transitions (e.g., saprophytic to pathogenic in case of *A. fumigatus*) exist and in order to correctly interpret and understand these interactions, full elucidation of the BGC deployment conditions is necessary. Examples of these exceptions are for instance that phytohormones can also be produced by non-plant associated fungi like *S. cerevisiae* or that some opposed interactions rely on similar BGCs

(e.g., both pathogenic and mutualistic beneficial fungi deploy host-defence evading strategies for tissue penetration and colonization). Although generic SMs, like antimicrobial substances have a clear and obvious purpose, a reliable prediction of the ecological role in case of very specific interactions, like the “zombie ant fungus” is hardly possible. In order to elucidate the true ecological purpose, it is important to study the interactions in an environment as natural as possible.

1.5 Species ecotypes showcase the evolutionary speed of BGCs

This fast adaptability and specialisation are possible because many BGCs are often located in polymorphic genome regions. Furthermore, BGCs have an “opportunistic essential” character, depending on the environmental challenges, which leads to conservation of some fitness improving BGCs but at the same time to deterioration of not essential BGCs. This fluctuation of essentiality throughout evolution is also a natural accelerator of this diversification process. Therefore, BGCs have a faster “evolutionary speed” than the rest of the genome as reviewed also in publication III [33]. This partly explains the observation that, within a species, ecotypes can evolve that show variations in the secondary metabolome. This phenomenon has been investigated during several genome comparisons of closely related species and also between different ecotypes of the same species [159].

In case of domesticated fungi, there have been several very interesting studies that showed the domestication effect on the BGC arsenal of fungi. *Aspergillus oryzae* is being domesticated (i.e., cultivation and selection by humans) since 7.000 B.C. in a form of mixed rice fermentation together with *S. cerevisiae*. *A. oryzae* and its close relative and presumably ancestor, the mycotoxin producing plant pathogen *A. flavus* share 99.5% DNA sequence identity. Genome and transcriptome analysis of different *A. oryzae* isolates show that putative selective sweep regions are enriched in SM genes and genes which are connected to flavor relevant and starch degrading traits. Furthermore, BGCs are dramatically downregulated in *A. oryzae* compared to *A. flavus*. Especially in case of the toxic SMs aflatoxin and cyclopiazonic acid, *A. oryzae* isolates show no expression and therefore no biosynthesis of the toxins which is a key phenotypic trait necessary for it being regarded as GRAS (“generally regarded as safe”) organism. Closer investigation showed that the *A. oryzae* isolates showed several mutations, one of which is a mutation in the binding site of the promoter of the transcriptional regulator aflR, which are possibly responsible for the abolished biosynthesis of these compounds. Notably, aflatoxin is not only carcinogenic for humans but also genotoxic to its fermentation partner *S. cerevisiae* [37].

Similarly, comparison of *Penicillium fuscoglaucum* with its closely related cheese and sausage fermenting fungi *P. camemberti* var. "camemberti" and *P. camemberti* var. "caseifulvum" showed that with increasing domestication process, the varieties not only show different visual and growth phenotypes but also experience a strong downregulation (var. "caseifulvum") or even a frameshift mutation within the backbone gene *cpaA* (var. "camemberti") of the cyclopiazonic acid BGC [38].

In case of geographically isolated strains of the lichen forming fungus *Umbilicaria pustulata*. The analysis of 600 isolates from two climate regions that had significantly different average temperatures showed that one BGC was exclusively present in cold-tempered populations while another shows deleterious mutations and was probably dysfunctional in the same group [160].

Furthermore, as showcased by analysis in the genus *Fusarium* [161] and *Aspergillus* [162] and also between isolates of the broad host range plant pathogen *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* [163], these information can be utilized to reveal pathogenicity factors, pathways that lead to the establishment of pathogenicity and by that also facilitate the prediction of putative future pathogens by comparing the phenotypical, genomic and also transcriptomic traits between (opportunistic) pathogenic and non-pathogenic species or strains.

All these data show the immense influence the domestication process can have on the genome and secondary metabolome of fungi which could be interpreted as human made species ecotypes. As more and more information about ecological niche, BGC elucidation and their ecological purpose is generated and interconnected, the more feasible it will get to predict the habitat and ecological niche of new species and the putative function of unknown BGCs. Conclusively, comparative analysis within a genus or between ecotypes of a species are scarce but hold invaluable information about BGC evolution. The wealth of bioactive substances within the fungal kingdom is not only vast in numbers but also constantly changing and adapting, which makes the mining for bioactive substances from fungal sources a promising and rewarding endeavour. There are however limitations. Some fungi are not yet cultivatable within the laboratory or grow very slowly and generally the number of fungi that are established for genetic laboratory work is still very low. Therefore, in publication II (currently under review; [44]), we addressed this topic and established a strain of *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* for laboratory work and also conducted genomic, transcriptomic and also metabolomic analysis which revealed that most of the BGCs are inactive under laboratory conditions. Furthermore, we established and applied genetic methods for the elucidation of the biosynthetic pathway of the compound rasfonin which is a SM known for its anti-cancer properties.

1.6 Fungal Natural Products: Unearthing their ecological role(s)

The most forward process of finding any biological activity is a generic compound extraction followed by purification and screening against microbial pathogens or cancer cell lines or other assays and screens that look for specific traits. In comparison, the elucidation of the real ecological role, meaning the reason(s) for a certain compound to exist in nature is far more complex. It can never be answered with absolute certainty, but high probability assumptions are possible. In some already mentioned cases, the ecological role is more or less obvious, like antimicrobial compounds specifically inhibiting the cell wall synthesis of gram-positive bacteria or the presence of a resistance gene against the SM itself. Indicative but less certain cases for the actual role are compounds like phytohormones. They are most probably involved in plant interactions but how the fungus is deploying them i.e., in a beneficial or pathogenic context, depends on many complex interactions. In case of multipurpose compounds like melanins, which appear in many organisms, the multitude and versatility of ecological roles are also very context and cell type specific (Spores, cell walls, etc.) and are more general traits. If no obvious bioactivity or role can be assigned, several strategies can be used to shed light on the purpose of these substances which I will go through in the next section.

The natural trigger

Dissection of the natural trigger(s) not only determines why a certain SM is produced but also is the most profound indicator about the role of the compound. In general, there are several (simplified) scenarios that can lead to the triggering of a BGC. In the easiest case, the presence of a simple condition can lead to BGC activation. For example, *Aspergillus nidulans* starts biosynthesis of orsellinic acid after exposure to the metabolite polaramycin B from *Streptomyces rapamycinicus* [164], or the production of UV protectants after exposure to UV-radiation [165]. Of course, it could be that this scenario also involves the presence of other triggers or the absence of one or more unknown repressor(s).

Another possibility is the absence of one or more repressor(s), like the absence of nutrients, for instance in case of BGCs that are carbon and/or nitrogen regulated. In *Fusarium fujikuroi*, the bikaverin and gibberellic acid BGCs are activated only under nitrogen starvation conditions [166]. When supplemented again with nitrogen, the BGCs also get inactivated. There are also cases of independent triggers of the same BGC which was shown in the case of *Aspergillus terreus* which produced the pathogenesis associated SM terrain when one of the conditions present in the rizosphere of the host was mimicked (i.e., presence of methionine, nitrogen starvation or iron starvation) [167]. In *Aspergillus nidulans*, the BGC for sterigmatocystin is under carbon catabolite repression which is mediated by the protein RimO [63].

More complicated but potentially the most common type is a combinatorial triggering system that relies on the presence and/ or absence of several conditions at the same time like in case of the behaviour manipulating fungus *Ophiocordyceps unilateralis sensu lato* which could infect and kill all tested ant species but could only manipulate the behaviour of its natural host. Further investigation revealed that the fungus was producing a different array of SMs depending on the ant species [156].

In order to mimic the natural environment of the fungus, information about the place of isolation, community analysis of the area and general flora and fauna of the environmental ecological habitat can give important information and clues that could be utilized during the experimental setup in order to naturally trigger the production of SMs.

Of course, all these scenarios are, on purpose, illustrated in a very simplified way. They only take the observations that have been made by the experimenter into account and do not mirror the complexity of all the intertwined regulatory mechanisms or other triggers/conditions that are theoretically necessary but are not perceived. For instance, in case of the first and second scenario, other factors that might also induce or repress the BGC might be crucial but are not part of the (variable) experimental setup during the study. The experiments always try to use as few variables as possible while maintaining the same standard laboratory conditions as media components or cultivation conditions or developmental stage etc., which all could be additional causalities for the observed phenotype (i.e., the production of the SM).

Nevertheless, determining a distinct trigger for the activation of a BGC reveals at least one of the scenarios where this SM is important for the fungal host. This information specifies the deployment area of the SM and therefore is and indicator for the ecological relevance. Based on these observations, subsequent experiments can give more insight into the exact mechanisms behind the BGC activation and hence, elucidate the ecological role of the SM.

Silent or cryptic BGCs: Transcriptional repression vs. evolutionary inactivation:

As BGCs are shaped by “chance” during evolution, the whole expanse of purposes might never be fully understood. It is important to keep in mind that evolution is a constant process and we will always only look at the current state of a BGC in a species and also within a certain ecotype. We therefore do not know if a certain BGC is being assembled, is being maintained or is in the process of degradation. If we artificially activate a silent BGC that is in the degradation or build up phase, it might result in a synthetic product that never had naturally been produced and never had an ecological purpose.

However, if the natural trigger of a BGC cannot be found, artificial expression by molecular biology methods is often the only way of getting a BGC derived biosynthetic product. While this fact does not impose a problem for finding new bioactive substances, it can be a

misleading hindrance when aiming for the real ecological purpose of a SM. At the same time, characterization of the presumed biosynthetic product of an artificially activated BGC is an inevitable step that gives important insights in the putative ecological purpose and hence maybe also its natural environmental trigger(s). Additionally, it might also yield a substance that is interesting for human application. Therefore, in publication I [168], we established a gene activation tool that is a fusion protein of the RNA guided protein dCas9 and the artificial trans-activator VPR. With this tool it is possible to activate one or multiple genes anywhere within the genome without disturbing the genetic locus.

Genome analysis: BGC composition, integrity, position and phylogenetic comparison

Inter and intragenomic analysis can give information about the evolutionary state, stability and purpose of a BGC. The position of the BGC (e.g., proximity to telomers) and neighbouring DNA motifs (e.g., TEs, quantitative trait loci (QTLs; [169]) show if a BGC is within a polymorphic region (i.e., higher recombination rate) or within syntenic blocks which proceed at a different evolutionary speed. BGCs in conserved regions tend to also be present with high homology in phylogenetic or ecologically (i.e., same lifestyle) related species, as for instance in case of the BGC for the antifungal compound griseofulvin that is present across different fungal species which indicates a conserved role in the lifecycle of the fungi [170]. On the other hand, BGCs were also found near quantitative trait loci (QTL) as for instance shown in the plant pathogen *Pyrenophora spp.* where NRPS were co-localized with virulence associated regions [169,171]. In these instances, it could be hypothesised that these BGCs are also involved in virulence associated aspects and that the close vicinity promotes a co-evolution of both, BGCs and QTLs. BGCs that are in polymorphic genomic regions could indicate that these BGCs or their genomic regions are hotspots for adaptive evolution to their environment. In case of pathogenic invasions, the host will also develop defence mechanisms that have to be evaded by the pathogen by quick adaptation. In support of this assumption, pathogenicity related genes of *A. fumigatus* (causal pathogen for aspergillosis) that are upregulated during infection of murine lung tissue show a positional bias towards the telomers and are lineage-specific compared to other closely related non-pathogenic fungi [86,172].

As shown in case of *A. fumigatus* and *A. fischeri* [173] or *Ophiostoma ulmi* and *O. novo-ulmi* [174], comparison of genomes of closely related pathogenic and non-pathogenic species, can reveal pathogenicity related traits and BGCs which also contributes to the revelation of the ecological purpose of a BGC.

Apart from phylogenetic and genome positioning, close examination of reading frames and gene annotations of BGCs can hold valuable information. The integrity of the reading frame shows if a gene is fully functional or if it already acquired mutations that lead to premature stop codons or frameshifts which would indicate that the cluster is not being maintained anymore

and on its way to the “genetic bin”. Gene annotations can also hold information about the compound. The presence of a resistance conveying gene points towards an antimicrobial substance. Transporters and signal peptides within protein sequences can indicate the localization of the SM, its intermediates and its synthesizing enzymes which also can be important indicators for their ecological role [175]. Compartmentalisation during and after SM biosynthesis can either have the purpose of transferring the compound where it is needed (e.g., antimicrobial or pathogenicity related substances are exported out of the cell) [176,177] or where it is being stored/ processed or disposed of (e.g. vacuoles, peroxisomes) [178] or removal from the cell or a compartment where it could inflict damage [47,175,179].

1.7 Discussion and Conclusion: Nature has all the information, the laboratory all the means of verification

Connecting data: Transcriptomics, metabolomics, phylogenomics, community and environmental analysis.

Research on fungal SMs is strongly focused on strains being cultivated under very defined laboratory conditions. Mostly, only one species or co-cultivation of very few species are performed. These experimental setups eliminate most of the naturally occurring triggers or interactions that are relevant for SM production like the growth matrix, microbial community, long term interactions, weather conditions, and so on. Samples from the real environment contain all the necessary information about which compounds are being transcribed by which organism and under which conditions. The problem is the accessibility of these information. As technology and methodology is progressing into the area of single cell and community omics application, such analysis could reveal many yet unknown interactions that can hardly be studied in a laboratory environment. With omics approaches it could be possible to prepare metagenome sequence analysis [180,181], transcriptomics [182,183] and also metabolomics [184] of a whole community within one sample (e.g. soil) [185]. This would reveal the expression profile (of BGCs), chemical composition and metabolites and matrix composition that are involved in the interactions within the sample. Repetitive analysis at different times of the year and exact documentation of the sample site (temperature, date, parameters of the sample site, weather, etc) are important variables that all can putatively influence not only the community composition but also the SM expression profile. Interconnection of these data and information from different ecological habitats that contain the species of interest can provide the necessary information to perform correlation analysis of all different parameters which can lead to the activation conditions of BGCs. Environmental parameters can be connected to the active or inactive state of a BGC and subsequent analysis in the laboratory can be conducted

to fully verify and reveal the ecological triggers of the BGC. This information then can be used to dissect the mode of action and molecular target of the metabolite.

Proposals that focus on the ecology and the environment of the microbe as the trait-based approach already exist [186] and some prediction platforms already incorporate aspects of environmental metadata (e.g., axiBGC [187] or IMG-ABC [188]). However, these environmentally guided omics strategies and especially their linkage are just in their infancy because most of current research is driven by the ambition of finding new substances that can be potentially used in an applied context and not by the elucidation of the ecological role itself. Therefore, current experimental setups rather work on either high throughput platforms that try to find easily triggered SMs of any microorganism within a laboratory environment or aim for the artificial activation of silent BGCs in a laboratory environment. These substances then get investigated more closely via assays that show different traits of interest (e.g.: antimicrobial, etc.) which contrasts with experiments that look for traits that are relevant in the environmental context.

To get a better understanding on how microbes interact with each other on a BGC-level and how these interactions are mirrored in the genome and secondary metabolome, community analysis that comprise a thorough investigation of every involved aspect are a crucial core piece. Not only will this help with finding the ecological role of a SM, but it also could help with finding causes and cures of plant or human diseases or promote the tackling of challenges in any sector where microbe communities are an important and defining but underestimated and overlooked piece of the puzzle.

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2 Publications

Publication I:

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2.1 Publication I

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A novel fungal gene regulation system based on inducible VPR-dCas9 and nucleosome map-guided sgRNA positioning

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Abstract

Programmable transcriptional regulation is a powerful tool to study gene functions. Current methods to selectively regulate target genes are mainly based on promoter exchange or on overexpressing transcriptional activators. To expand the discovery toolbox, we designed a dCas9-based RNA-guided synthetic transcription activation system for *Aspergillus nidulans* that uses enzymatically disabled “dead” Cas9 fused to three consecutive activation domains (VPR-dCas9). The dCas9-encoding gene is under the control of an estrogen-responsive promoter to allow induction timing and to avoid possible negative effects by strong constitutive expression of the highly active VPR domains. Especially in silent genomic regions, facultative heterochromatin and strictly positioned nucleosomes can constitute a relevant obstacle to the transcriptional machinery. To avoid this negative impact and to facilitate optimal positioning of RNA-guided VPR-dCas9 to targeted promoters, we have created a genome-wide nucleosome map from actively growing cells and stationary cultures to identify the cognate nucleosome-free regions (NFRs). Based on these maps, different single-guide RNAs (sgRNAs) were designed and tested for their targeting and activation potential. Our results demonstrate that the system can be used to regulate several genes in parallel and, depending on the VPR-dCas9 positioning, expression can be pushed to very high levels. We have used the system to turn on individual genes within two different biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs) which are silent under normal growth conditions. This method also opens opportunities to stepwise activate individual genes in a cluster to decipher the correlated biosynthetic pathway.

Keypoints

- An inducible RNA-guided transcriptional regulator based on VPR-dCas9 was established in *Aspergillus nidulans*.
- Genome-wide nucleosome positioning maps were created that facilitate sgRNA positioning.
- The system was successfully applied to activate genes within two silent biosynthetic gene clusters.

Keywords dCas9 gene activation · Programmable transcriptional regulator · *Aspergillus* · Biosynthetic gene clusters · Genome-wide nucleosome positioning map

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Introduction

Filamentous fungi produce a plethora of metabolites and enzymes which are essential components of their response to environmental, nutritional or developmental signals. These metabolites can have beneficial but also detrimental effects on plant and animal health. In agricultural sciences, fungal research is focused on understanding the biology and genetics of phytopathogens to combat diseases and to reduce economic losses caused by product deterioration and the accumulation of toxic secondary metabolites (SMs) (Brefort et al. 2009; Hollingsworth et al. 2008). Usually, multi-gene biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs) are responsible for the production of these SMs. These clusters show similar structures at the genomic level, always containing one or more core genes that code for backbone-generating enzymes which define the substance class of the cluster product. These backbone or signature gene(s) often code for polyketide synthases (PKSs), non-ribosomal peptide synthetases (NRPSs), prenyltransferases or terpene cyclases. Apart from the core genes, several other protein classes can be involved that serve the purpose of adding modifications, regulating gene transcription or transport of the metabolite (Brakhage 2013). Usually, the individual genes within a given BGC are transcriptionally co-regulated, not expressed by default and activated only in response to a “proprietary” expression signal. For most of these clusters, standard laboratory conditions do not generate this critical signal and consequently, their cognate products cannot be identified (Bachleitner et al. 2019; Chujo and Scott 2014; Connolly et al. 2013; Gacek-Matthews et al. 2016; Gacek and Strauss 2012; Reyes-Dominguez et al. 2010; Studt et al. 2016). About 50% of the BGCs contain a gene that encodes a pathway-specific transcriptional activator (Keller 2019). In some cases, the expression of these transcription factors (TFs) is sufficient to orchestrate the production of the BGC product but more often overexpression of the resident TF does not upregulate the cluster (Ahuja et al. 2012; Bromann et al. 2012; Grau et al. 2018). The absence of a pathway-specific TF complicates the targeted activation of a specific cluster (Brakhage 2013; Macheleidt et al. 2016; Then Bergh and Brakhage 1998; Tilburn et al. 1995).

The number of genes that are involved in the production of SMs can vary greatly. Some SMs need only a single gene like the *PKS8* in *Fusarium graminearum* (Westphal et al. 2018). Others need the coordinated involvement of few to many genes for the assembly of the BGC product like the asperthecin cluster of *Aspergillus nidulans* which comprises 3 genes (Szewczyk et al. 2008) or the sterigmatocystin cluster of *A. nidulans* which consists of 25 genes (Brown et al. 1996). Genomes of filamentous fungi contain a large number and diversity of BGCs. It is well established that the repression of SM BGCs can comprise a multitude of global but also specific regulators that act on the maintenance of a repressive chromatin structure, influence signal transduction pathways or impact gene expression by post-translational modifications or processing of regulators (Brakhage 2013;

Brakhage and Schroeckh 2011; García-Estrada et al. 2018; Gerke and Braus 2014; Keller 2019; Lyu et al. 2020; Reyes-Dominguez et al. 2010; Romsdahl and Wang 2019). Therefore, the products of many silent SM BGCs remain elusive. For activation of cryptic clusters in fungi, a plethora of methods was already applied. They comprise promoter replacements in cis (Ahuja et al. 2012; Chiang et al. 2010; Lin et al. 2019; Wiemann et al. 2018; Yeh et al. 2016), the expression of hybrid transactivators (Grau et al. 2018), overexpression or deletion of cluster-specific and global regulators (Bachleitner et al. 2019; Bok et al. 2006, 2009; Chiang et al. 2010; Gacek-Matthews et al. 2016; Grau et al. 2019; Niehaus et al. 2016b; Oakley et al. 2017; Szewczyk et al. 2008), interference with chromatin-based silencing (Bok et al. 2009, 2013; Connolly et al. 2013; Gacek-Matthews et al. 2016; Niehaus et al. 2016b; Reyes-Dominguez et al. 2010; Studt et al. 2013, 2016; Westphal et al. 2019), protein stabilisation (Gerke et al. 2012), trans-expression of whole BGCs in a heterologous host (Clevenger et al. 2017) and approaches based on the variation of cultivation conditions (i.e. “OSMAC”) including the cocultivation with other organisms (Bode et al. 2002; Nützmann et al. 2011; Scherlach et al. 2011; Schroeckh et al. 2009). In case of the model fungus *A. nidulans*, these methods were successful in deciphering the biosynthetic pathways of 32 of its approximately 64 clusters (Ahuja et al. 2012; Andersen et al. 2013; MacCabe et al. 1991; Bergmann et al. 2007; Bok et al. 2006, 2009; Bromann et al. 2012; Brown et al. 1996; Chiang et al. 2008, 2009, 2016; Eisendle et al. 2003; Gerke et al. 2012; Grau et al. 2018; Hai et al. 2019; Ishikawa et al. 2014; Lin et al. 2019; Lo et al. 2012; Macheleidt et al. 2016; Romsdahl and Wang 2019; Sanchez et al. 2010, 2011, 2012; Sung et al. 2017; Szewczyk et al. 2008; Watanabe et al. 1999; Yaegashi et al. 2013; Yeh et al. 2012, 2016). The same is true for other fungi such as *Fusarium* spp. (Hansen et al. 2015; Niehaus et al. 2016a; Wiemann et al. 2013), *Penicillium* sp. (Nielsen et al. 2017) and *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* (Graham-Taylor et al. 2020).

Due to the recent revolution in sequencing techniques, the complete genome sequence of over 700 different fungal species has been determined so far (<https://mycocosm.jgi.doe.gov>). This theoretically represents an enormously rich resource for novel bioactive compounds (Nordberg et al. 2014). Many fungi however have very low homologous recombination rates which makes gene targeting in situ very inefficient and laborious. This complicates the genetic manipulation of these species and slows down the revelation of novel compounds. Furthermore, already established methods cannot be used for the activation of any given BGC type. Promoter exchanges seem only practical with small predicted clusters or clusters that harbour a clear candidate of BGC-specific TF that can be overexpressed and converted to its active state. For BGCs that do not contain a TF or contain a TF that requires specific post-translational modifications for activity, this approach will not be successful. In *A. nidulans*, Yeh et al. (2016) and Lin et al. (2019) conducted serial promoter exchanges and thereby successfully elucidated the synthesis of fellutamide B

(six promoter replacements) and aspermidgulenes (four promoter replacements). BGCs can however contain many more genes, like the sterigmatocystin cluster which consist of around twenty-five genes (Brown et al. 1996). Promoter exchange experiments, although shown to be successful on small clusters, are however often laborious and require selection marker recycling strategies (e.g. *Cre/loxP*) (Aguiar et al. 2014). Another problem that emerges during promoter exchange studies is the integrity of the transformation locus. Fungi like *Aspergillus* spp. and *Fusarium* spp. have a high gene density (~1 gene/3000 bps (Bashyal et al. 2017; Cuomo et al. 2007; Galagan et al. 2005)) when compared with other eukaryotes like human (~1 gene/150,000 bps (Ezkurdia et al. 2014; Piovesan et al. 2019)), *Mus musculus* (~1 gene/83,000 bps (Weitzman 2002)), *Caenorhabditis elegans* (~1 gene/5000 bps (Consortium 1998)), *Drosophila melanogaster* (~1 gene/9000 bps (Adams et al. 2000)), *Arabidopsis thaliana* (~1 gene/5000 bps (Arabidopsis Genome 2000)) or *Oryzae sativa* (~1 gene/9500 bps (Kawahara et al. 2013)). Thus, many control elements (promoters, terminators, binding motifs, etc.) in filamentous fungi like *A. nidulans* are in near vicinity to each other. Interfering with the integrity of the genomic locus could lead to unforeseen consequences on neighbouring genes, cis- or trans-regulatory elements and the chromatin structure at this locus.

Apart from promoter replacement approaches, hybrid transactivators were tested for activation. By fusing the DNA-binding domain of the cluster-specific TF from a gene residing in the (+)-Asperlin BGC with an activation domain of another transcriptional activator (i.e. AfoA), the cluster could be activated and the cognate product was identified (Grau et al. 2018). Again, this approach can only be successful if the BGC in question contains also a specific TF.

Other approaches that interfere with chromatin-based regulators, such as histone deacetylases (Shwab et al. 2007; Studt et al. 2013), heterochromatin protein 1 (Reyes-Dominguez et al. 2010), histone methyl transferases (Chujo and Scott 2014; Connolly et al. 2013; Studt et al. 2016) or histone demethylases (Bachleitner et al. 2019; Gacek-Matthews et al. 2016), also do not work for all BGCs as some are up-regulated by chromatin engineering but others are repressed by the same changes. Furthermore, this approach cannot be used for targeting only a specific cluster. Modification of chromatin may not only have effects on BGCs, but can also influence primary metabolism and developmental processes.

Because of these complications and limitations of established techniques, there are still a great number of fungal species that await the deciphering of their predicted BGCs and the characterisation of their cognate metabolite (Lyu et al. 2020). Here, we present a new method to activate silent genes which is based on the expression and precise targeting of a synthetic activator composed of an enzymatically disabled “dead” Cas9 (dCas9) fused to three consecutively arranged strong activation domains termed V-P-R. The whole dCas9-VPR system was already described to function in human cell lines by Chavez et al. (2015). In the

tripartite activation domain, “V” represents 4 copies of the VP16 domain of the Herpes Simplex Virus (i.e. VP64), “P” stands for a part of the p65 domain of the human transcription factor NF- κ B and “R” represents a segment of the Rta transactivator of the Epstein-Barr virus. Each of these activator domains have been extensively studied and shown to individually enhance or facilitate gene activation by engaging in different protein interactions within the transcriptional machinery (Chang et al. 2005; Hall and Struhl 2002; Hardwick et al. 1992; Lecoq et al. 2017; Lee and Hahn 1995; Schmitz and Baeuerle 1991). We centred our approach on a dCas9-based gene activation system because with this, the activator can be targeted at one or more genomic locations easily and simultaneously simply by expressing the right combination of guide RNAs. Moreover, the functionality of the conventional CRISPR/Cas9 system for genetic manipulation of a single site or multiple loci (multiplex sgRNAs) is firmly established in *A. nidulans* and other filamentous fungi as reviewed by Song et al. (Nødvig et al. 2018; Song et al. 2019). We reasoned that VPR-dCas9 can be expressed in the host and guided by co-expressed sgRNAs to any accessible locus in the genome. By expression of one or more sgRNAs in the VPR-dCas9-containing strain, one or more individual genes in different combinations can be targeted and activated in a predicted BGC. This also provides the opportunity to stepwise activate different genes within a target BGC that may lead to the discovery of a novel metabolite and its intermediates. As this system does not require in loco transformation at the BGC of interest, it can be applied as ectopic construct or as an episomal plasmid by utilising the AMA1 region of *A. nidulans*. This would make it applicable in various other species as well which do not support fast and efficient in loco transformations. The functionality of the *A. nidulans* AMA1 region was already verified in several other fungal species which makes this a very promising option for introducing the VPR-dCas9 activator system into other species (Bok et al. 2015; Brückner et al. 1992; Kubodera et al. 2002; Rebordinos et al. 2000; Shimizu et al. 2012).

Here, we detail the methodology and provide proof-of-concept for functionality of the VPR-dCas9 system by targeting BGCs that are involved in the production of monodictyphenone (*mdp*) and prenylated xanthenes (Chiang et al. 2010; Sanchez et al. 2011), as well as two genes in a predicted cluster for which the cognate product is not known yet.

Materials and methods

Plasmid generation

Plasmids were constructed by means of DNA restriction digests, polymerase chain reactions (PCRs) and subsequent ligation by yeast recombinational cloning (YRC) (Schumacher 2012). All oligos were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (“DNA Oligos in Tubes”; St. Louis, MO, USA). For YRC, overlap

extension PCRs were used for creating fragments with homologous overhangs (≥ 20 nucleotides). The backbone plasmid was *pRS426* (Christianson et al. 1992) and the yeast strain for transformation was the uracil-auxotrophic strain FGSC 9721 (FY 834) (Winston et al. 1995). Five microliters of each PCR fragment were used for YRC. After YRC, the purified plasmids (New England Biolabs; Ipswich, MA, USA; Monarch® Plasmid Miniprep Kit; Art. No.: T1010S) were verified by sequencing (“Ready2Run” by LGC Genomics GmbH; Berlin, Germany). All plasmids that have been generated and used in that study are summarised Table 1. All fragments and the corresponding primers are listed in Supplementary Table S1.

For generation of *pVPR4* (for plasmid map, see Fig. 1a; the number indicates the laboratory internal plasmid version), the backbone vector *pRS426* was digested with *EcoRI* and *XhoI* over night at 37 °C in 2× Tango buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific™; Waltham, MA, USA; Art. No.: ER0271, ER0691) and directly used for YRC. Together with the digest, following DNA fragments were used for transformation of yeast strain FY834 (for primer pairs, see Supplementary Table S1). The gene of the human estrogen receptor alpha (*hER*) was amplified by primer pair *hER-F/R* (template source: *phERpyr4* (Pachlinger et al. 2005)), which is under the control of the constitutive *coxA* promoter (Sarkari et al. 2017) which was amplified by primer pair *P.coxA-1-F/R* and *P.coxA-2-F/R* (template source: genomic DNA from *Aspergillus niger* wild-type isolate (in-house strain collection AIT-#931)) and the terminator region of the *tef1* orthologue of *A. niger* (An18g04840) which was amplified by primer pair *T.tef1-1-F/R* (template source: genomic DNA from *A. niger* wild-type isolate (in-house strain collection AIT-#931)). The *VPR-dCas9* fusion was amplified from two different sources. *VPR* was amplified by primer pair *VPR-F/R* (template source: *pWalium20-*

Table 1 Plasmids. Plasmid names, the most important elements and the backbone plasmid are shown. Consecutive numbers in the plasmid name (i.e. m1–m4 and A1–A2) indicate different sgRNAs. Targeted genes are shown under elements in parenthesis. Elements comprise the human estrogen receptor gene (*hER*), the activator *VPR-dCas9*, the selection markers (i.e. *argB* or *pyroA*) and the different sgRNA cassettes

Plasmid	Elements	Backbone
<i>pVPR4</i>	<i>hER</i> , <i>VPR-dCas9</i> , <i>argB</i>	<i>pRS426</i>
<i>psgRNA</i>	sgRNA scaffold, <i>pyroA</i>	<i>pRS426</i>
<i>psgRNA-m1</i>	sgRNA-m1 (<i>mdpE</i>), <i>pyroA</i>	<i>psgRNA</i>
<i>psgRNA-m2</i>	sgRNA-m2 (<i>mdpE</i>), <i>pyroA</i>	<i>psgRNA</i>
<i>psgRNA-m3</i>	sgRNA-m3 (<i>mdpE</i>), <i>pyroA</i>	<i>psgRNA</i>
<i>psgRNA-m4</i>	sgRNA-m4 (<i>mdpE</i>), <i>pyroA</i>	<i>psgRNA</i>
<i>psgRNA-A1</i>	sgRNA-A1 (AN8506), <i>pyroA</i>	<i>psgRNA</i>
<i>psgRNA-A2</i>	sgRNA-A2 (AN8507), <i>pyroA</i>	<i>psgRNA</i>

10XUAS-3XFLAG-*dCas9-VPR* (Addgene No.: #78897) (Lin et al. 2015)) while *dCas9* was amplified by primer pair *dCas9-1-F/R* and *dCas9-2-F/R* (template source: *pCAG-BirA*-dCas9-eGFP* which was kindly provided by the Leonardt laboratory (Schmidtman et al. 2016)). The estrogen response elements which represent the promoter of the *VPR-dCas9* fusion gene were amplified by primer pair *P.ERE-F/R* (template source: *pJW52_[3xERE-RS-P(nirA)]-[hER-trpC]-[pyro3/4]* (Bödi 2008)). The terminator of *VPR-dCas9* originates from the *glucanase* gene of *Botrytis cinerea* and was amplified by primer pairs *T.gluc-F/R* (template source: *pNAH-PoliC::bclt3-gfp* (Brandhoff et al. 2017)). For selection of transformants, the whole *argB* gene (including promoter and terminator region) from *A. nidulans* was used as auxotrophy marker which was

Fig. 1 Schematic drawing of plasmids encoding the components of the VPR-dCas9 activation system. Selection markers for fungal transformation are depicted in grey, promoters in green and terminators in purple. **a** Plasmid VPR4 carries the gene for the activator VPR-dCas9 (cyan, yellow) which has a synthetic promoter containing estrogen response elements (EREs) as binding motif for the human estrogen receptor (hER). The terminator of *VPR-dCas9* is derived from the glucanase gene of *Botrytis cinerea*. The *hER* gene (blue) is transcribed constitutively by the *coxA* promoter from *Aspergillus niger* and termination is controlled by the terminator region of the *tefl* orthologue of *A. niger*. The produced hER protein remains transcriptionally inactive unless it is converted to an active form (i.e. homodimer formation) by the addition of estrogens (i.e. DES). The selection marker *argB* is originated from *A. nidulans*. **b** Plasmid sgRNA is the parent vector of all sgRNA-carrying plasmids. It carries the sgRNA scaffold (magenta) which consists of the tracrRNA and HDV ribozyme. Directly upstream of the tracrRNA sequence an Eco91I restriction site is introduced for insertion of the specific gRNA sequences together with the hammerhead ribozyme. After insertion, both elements combined form the functional sgRNA cassette which releases the functional sgRNA upon transcription. The sgRNA cassette is constitutively expressed by the *gpdA* promoter of *A. fumigatus* and terminated by the terminator of the *tefl* gene of *A. fumigatus*. The selection marker *pyroA* originates from *A. fumigatus*. Detailed information about the plasmids and their construction can be retrieved from section “Plasmid generation”. Figure was generated by SnapGene® software (from GSL Biotech; available at snapgene.com)

amplified by primer pair *argB*-F/R (template source: gDNA of *A. nidulans* WIM 126 (Mooney and Yager 1990)).

For the generation of *psgRNA* (Fig. 1b) and subsequent plasmids (i.e. *psgRNA* carrying a sgRNA), *pRS426* was digested with *NdeI* (Thermo Fisher Scientific™; Art. No.: ER0581). Together with the digest, following DNA fragments were used for transformation of FY834 (see Supplementary Table S1 for information about primers). The missing part of the *URA3* marker (disrupted by *NdeI*) was amplified by primer pair *URA3*-F/R as well as the 2μ -*ori* which was amplified by primer pair 2μ -*ori*-F/R (template source: *pRS426* (Christianson et al. 1992)). The plasmid furthermore contains the sgRNA cassette which was amplified by primer pair *sgRNAscaff*-F/R (template source: *pFC334* (Nødvig et al. 2015), which was kindly provided by the Mortensen laboratory). The promoter for the sgRNA cassette is from the *gpdA* gene and was amplified by primer pair *P.gpdA*-F/R (template source: gDNA from *Aspergillus fumigatus* wild-type isolate (in-house strain collection AIT-#1232)) while the terminator was from the *tefl* gene and was amplified by primer pair *tefl*-2-F/R (template source: gDNA of *A. fumigatus* wild-type isolate (in-house strain collection AIT-#1232)). *pyroA* (including promoter and terminator) from *A. fumigatus* was used as auxotrophy marker for selection of transformants and was amplified by primer pair *pyroA*-F/R (template source: gDNA of *A. fumigatus* wild-type isolate (in-house strain collection AIT-#1232)).

For the insertion of sgRNAs into *psgRNA* (i.e. generation of plasmids *psgRNA*-m1 to m4 and *psgRNA*-A1 and A2), the plasmid was digested by *Eco91I* (Thermo Fisher Scientific™;

Art. No.: ER0392). The digested plasmid was then used together with 2 μ L of the respective annealed gRNA oligonucleotides for transformation of FY834. For annealing of the forward and reverse gRNA oligonucleotide (Supplementary Table S2), both were dissolved in annealing buffer (final concentrations: 10 mM Tris, pH 7.5, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 100 μ M of each oligonucleotide). The DNA was subsequently denaturised by heating the mix up to 95 °C for 5 min in a Thermocycler (Analytic Jena AG; Jena, Germany; Biometra, Thermocycler, Art. No.: T3000-48) followed by an annealing step by cooling the mix down to 25 °C at 0.03 °C/s (Protocol by Sigma-Aldrich (Sigma-Aldrich 2020)).

Strain generation and molecular methods

Strain generation

Strains used in this study are depicted in Table 2. All strains had the *nkuA* Δ background to reduce non-homologous end joining and facilitate homologous recombination events (Nayak et al. 2006). Strains were transformed by using protoplast transformation (Tilburn et al. 1983). All transformations were conducted with circular plasmids. For generation of strain VPR4, strain A1153 was transformed with *pVPR4*. After single spore isolation, the in situ integration (i.e. *argB*) and presence of all relevant features of *pVPR4* was verified by PCR. Primer pairs that were used for the verification of strain VPR4 and the results can be obtained from Supplementary Table S1 and Supplementary Fig. S1, respectively. A correct transformant was then transformed with plasmid *psgRNA* containing a sgRNA. In case of multiple sgRNA-carrying strains (i.e. VPR4-mA1, VPR4-m1&m2, VPR4-m2&m3), plasmids *psgRNA*-m1 to m4 were transformed simultaneously and the uptake of different combinations was verified by PCR. In case of strain VPR4-A1 and A2, either *psgRNA*-A1 or *psgRNA*-A2 was transformed into VPR4. For sgRNA-carrying strains, the presence of the specific sgRNA was verified by PCR as well. Information about primer pairs and results of the PCRs can be obtained from Supplementary Table S1 and Supplementary Fig. S2, respectively. DNA was extracted according to Cenis (1992) with following deviation. Prior to extraction, the fungus was grown on solid *Aspergillus* minimal media (AMM; Barratt et al. (1965)) and subsequently a thin layer of mycelia was transferred into a Lysing matrix A tube (MP Biomedicals; Irvine, CA; Art. No.: SKU 116910100). The material was then homogenised in a FastPrep-24™ (MP Biomedicals, Art. No.: SKU 116004500) at 6 m*s⁻¹ for 20 s in Cenis lysis buffer. DNA was used for fragment amplification for YRC (Q5® polymerase (New England Biolabs; Art. No.: M0491L) and for diagnostic PCR reactions (GoTaq® Green Master Mix (Promega; Madison, WI, USA; Art. No.:M7845). PCR was performed according to the respective manufacturer’s instruction.

Table 2 *Aspergillus nidulans* strains used during this study. All strains that are used for activation experiments are descendants of strain FGSC A1153. The suffixes T1/T2/T3 in column “Strain” refer to the different independent transformants per construct. In parenthesis are the strain numbers of our in-house collection

Strain	Genotype	Parent strain	Transformed plasmid	Reference
WIM 126 (#3)	<i>yA2, pabaA1, veA+</i>	–	–	Mooney and Yager (1990)
FGSC A1153 (#634)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 pyroA4 argB2 nkuA::bar</i>	–	–	McCluskey et al. (2010)
VPR4 (#833)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 pyroA4 nkuA::bar</i>	A1153	<i>pVPR4</i>	This study
VPR4-m1 (#834)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-m1</i>	This study
VPR4-m2 (#835)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-m2</i>	This study
VPR4-m3 (#836)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-m3</i>	This study
VPR4-m4-T1 (#837)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-m4</i>	This study
VPR4-m4-T2 (#838)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-m4</i>	This study
VPR4-m1&2 (#839)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-m1</i> <i>psgRNA-m2</i>	This study
VPR4-m2&3 (#840)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-m2</i> <i>psgRNA-m3</i>	This study
VPR4-mAll-T1 (#841)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-m1</i> <i>psgRNA-m2</i> <i>psgRNA-m3</i> <i>psgRNA-m4</i>	This study
VPR4-mAll-T2 (#842)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-m1</i> <i>psgRNA-m2</i> <i>psgRNA-m3</i> <i>psgRNA-m4</i>	This study
VPR4-A1-T1 (#843)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-A1</i>	This study
VPR4-A1-T2 (#844)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-A1</i>	This study
VPR4-A1-T3 (#845)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-A1</i>	This study
VPR4-A2-T1 (#846)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-A2</i>	This study
VPR4-A2-T2 (#847)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-A2</i>	This study
VPR4-A2-T3 (#848)	<i>yA1 pabaA1 nkuA::bar</i>	VPR4	<i>psgRNA-A2</i>	This study

Annealing temperature was set to 58 °C for Q5® amplifications and to 60 °C for GoTaq® amplifications. For RNA isolation, freeze-dried mycelium was ground to a fine powder using mortar and pestle under liquid nitrogen and RNA was extracted with TRIzol™ Reagent (Invitrogen; Carlsbad, CA, USA; Art. No.: 15596026) according to the manual. RNA content was measured using a NanoDrop™ spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific™; Art. No.: ND-2000C). For cDNA synthesis, 2 µg total RNA was treated with DNaseI (Thermo Fisher Scientific™; Art. No.: EN0521). Complete removal of any residual DNA was then verified by PCR with the primer pair for the gene *actA* (AN6542), *actA*-control (Supplementary Table S1). Next, 1 µg of DNA-free sample was taken for cDNA synthesis (Bio-Rad; Hercules, CA, USA; iScript™ cDNA Synthesis Kit, Art. No.: 1708891).

Successful cDNA synthesis was again verified using the primer pair *actA*-control (Supplementary Table S1).

Reverse transcriptase quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) analysis

The cDNA was diluted 1/5 with dH₂O and 2.5 µL was used for qPCR analysis (10 µL total volume; Bio-Rad, iTaq Universal SYBR Green Supermix; Art. No.: 172-5124) in a Bio-Rad CFX384 C1000 Touch Thermal cycler. The qPCRs were done in technical duplicates. Only primer pairs with an efficiency between 90 and 110% were considered for qPCR analysis. The genes of interest were compared with the house-keeping genes *actA* (AN6542) and *benA* (AN1182) and the relative fold change in expression was calculated according to

the $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method (Livak and Schmittgen 2001). The qPCR program was run as follows: 95 °C (3 min)—40 repetitions of (95 °C (10 s)—60 °C or 64 °C (10 s)—72 °C (30 s)—95 °C (10 s)—melting curve (65 °C–95 °C at 0.5 °C intervals and 5-s hold at each interval). All qPCR primer pairs were run at an annealing temperature of 60 °C apart from primers for *mdpG* which were run at 64 °C. A complete list of qPCR primers can be found in Supplementary Table S1.

Nucleosome mapping

A. nidulans (strain WIM 126 (Mooney and Yager 1990)) was grown in shaking flasks for 15 or 48 h in AMM supplemented with 1% glucose, 100 mM sodium nitrate and para-aminobenzoic acid (paba; Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim am Albuch, Germany; Fluka; Art. No.: 06930). Before harvest, mycelia were fixed with 1% formaldehyde (Roth; Art. No.: 4979) for 15 min and fixation was stopped with 1M glycine (Carl Roth; Karlsruhe, Germany; Art. No.: 3790). Mycelia were filtered and shock frozen in liquid nitrogen prior to grinding using a mortar and pestle.

To fragment the DNA, mycelia were suspended in 2 mL MNase digestion buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5 (Sigma; Art. No.: 3375), 50 mM NaCl (Carl Roth; Art. No.: 3957), 5 mM MgCl₂ (Carl Roth; Art. No.: KK36.1), 1 mM CaCl₂ (Carl Roth; Art. No.: A119.1), 1× proteinase inhibitor mix (Sigma; Art. No.: P8215) and 1 mM phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF, Sigma; Art. No.: 6367) and 300 µL aliquots of suspension were treated with 0.4 U micrococcal nuclease (MNase, Sigma; Art. No.: N3755) at 37 °C for 6 min. The MNase reaction was stopped by adding 300 µL stop buffer 2 (50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 255 mM NaCl, 40 mM EDTA (Carl Roth; Art. No.: 8040), 2% triton X-100 (Sigma; Art. No.: 8787) and 0.2% sodium deoxycholate (Sigma; Art. No.: D6750). Fixation was reversed by incubation for 15 min at 65 °C, the supernatant was purified using a PCR purification kit (Qiagen; Hilden, Germany; Art. No.: 28181) and samples were electrophoresed on a 1.5% agarose gel to check the MNase digestion. Sequencing library preparation and sequencing was performed at Vienna BioCenter Core Facilities. Illumina libraries were prepared using Nextera XT DNA Library Preparation Kit and paired end 50 bp sequencing was done on an Illumina HiSeq 2000 system. Obtained fastq files were mapped on *A. nidulans* WIM 126 genome assembly using BWA (version 0.7.17) and coverage per base pair was calculated using samtools (version 1.9) and bedtools (version 2.28.0) to receive a representation of the genome-wide nucleosome occupancy. The datasets were uploaded to the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) with the submission numbers SRR12336645 (15 h) and SRR12336644 (48 h).

Guide RNA design

The region of interest was analysed for the occurrence of the protospacer adjacent motifs (PAMs; i.e. NGG) and possible protospacer sequences (i.e. target-specific sequence of sgRNA) were subjected to a full genome blast against the genome of *A. nidulans* to select the protospacers that are closest to the anticipated locus with least possible off-targets. The borders of nucleosome-free regions were designated as the region between a 75 base pair offset from the adjacent dyad axis (i.e. peak maximum) (see Fig. 4 and Fig. 6). In case of the activation of *mdpE*, sgRNA sequences upstream as well as downstream of the nucleosome-free region were chosen additionally. Two sgRNAs were positioned close to the predicted transcriptional start site (TSS) of *mdpE*. Sequences of sgRNAs can be retrieved from Supplementary Table S2. The positioning of the sgRNAs within the genome is shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 6.

Media and growth conditions for activation experiments

During activation experiments, controls and activation strains were all grown and treated under identical conditions. 4×10^6 conidia per mL AMM media were inoculated in 60 mL AMM liquid media and 10 mM nitrate as nitrogen source. The cells were grown for 40 h at 37 °C and 180 rpm on orbital shaker platforms before adding the inducer to all flasks (i.e. samples as well as controls (=VPR4)). The inducer mix contained 75 nM diethylstilbestrol (DES; Sigma-Aldrich, Art. No.: 4628) in ethanol absolute (glass flask: Sigma; EMPARTA® ACS; Art. No.: 1070172511) (final inducer concentration: 33 pM DES). After induction, cultures were incubated for further 8 h. Subsequently 1 mL of supernatant was taken for SM analysis as described in section “SM analysis”. Mycelia were harvested by filtering through Miracloth fabric (Millipore; Burlington, MA, USA; Art. No.: 475855-1R), washed in dH₂O, frozen in liquid nitrogen and freeze-dried for dry mass determination and transcript analysis.

Phenotyping

The growth phenotype was determined on solid complete media (CM by DR. C. F. Robert (Barratt et al. 1965)), AMM and AMM supplemented with different concentrations of DES (Sigma, Art. No.: 4628) between 0.033 and 50 nM. Plates were inoculated with 10 µL of a 100 spores/µL spore suspension and incubated for 4 days at 37 °C in the dark. After 4 days, radial growth was measured and a picture was taken. Each growth test was done in triplicates. Additionally, the dry mass accumulation and production of SMs (i.e. penicillin G, sterigmatocystin, austinol, dehydroaustinol, emericellamide A) were compared under the same conditions as during

activation experiments (section “Media and growth conditions for activation experiments”) with the exception of comparing DES-induced and not induced VPR4 strains.

SM analysis

One millilitre of supernatant of *A. nidulans* liquid culture was analysed. The samples were run on a QTrap 5500 LC-MS/MS System (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA) equipped with a TurboIonSpray electrospray ionisation (ESI) source and a 1290 Series HPLC System (Agilent, Waldbronn, Germany). Chromatographic separation was done at 25 °C using a Gemini C18 150 × 4.6 mm i.d., 5 µm particle size, equipped with a C18 3 × 4 mm i.d. security guard cartridge (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA). The chromatographic method and chromatographic and mass spectrometric parameters are described elsewhere (Sulyok et al. 2020). The concentration of each metabolite was then normalised to the generated dry mass during cultivation.

Results

Systems development and experimental design

An overview of the system and the workflow are shown in Fig. 1 (plasmids) and Fig. 2 (workflow). To develop the system, we consecutively transformed *A. nidulans* FGSC A1153 with two constructs. First, plasmid VPR4 is constitutively expressing *hER* and an inducible (mediated by activated *hER*) *VPR-dCas9*. The expression of *VPR-dCas9* can be induced by the addition of estrogens (i.e. DES) which leads to the activation of *hER*, its subsequent dimerisation, binding to estrogen response elements (EREs; i.e. promoter region of *VPR-dCas9*) and activation of respective genes (Pachlinger et al. 2005). A verified transformant carrying *pVPR4* was then used as the recipient strain for the second plasmid which carries the constitutively expressed sgRNA cassette (descendants of *psgRNA*). The sgRNA is flanked by a hammerhead ribozyme and a HDV ribozyme to facilitate the proper processing and release of functional sgRNAs (Nødvig et al. 2015). During activation experiments, strain VPR4 was used as control strain to rule out artefacts that originate from components of plasmid VPR4 (i.e. *VPR-dCas9*, *hER*) or the inducer. An overview on the whole experimental workflow is shown in Fig. 2.

To improve correct positioning and “landing” of sgRNA-loaded VPR-dCas9 at the selected target region, we considered two points. First, the synthetic activator should be located at a suitable distance from the expected general transcriptional machinery to ensure efficient contacts between the activator, Mediator complex and the RNA-Polymerase II complex. We therefore positioned VPR-dCas9 at different distances from

the predicted transcriptional start site of the target gene. Secondly, we hypothesised that the sgRNA target sequences should not be buried in densely packed nucleosomes but optimally lie in nucleosome-free regions. We therefore performed genome-wide nucleosome accessibility assays using micrococcal nuclease digests followed by whole genome sequencing (MNase-seq). Two nucleosome positioning maps were created in the wild-type strain WIM 126 grown at two different physiological conditions on defined AMM, i.e. conditions of active growth (i.e. primary metabolism; 15 h shake cultures) and in stationary phase (i.e. secondary metabolism; 48 h shake cultures). Transformants with verified correct molecular integration events of *pVPR4* (i.e. strain VPR4) were analysed for SM production under non-induced and DES-induced (i.e. activating) conditions (section: “Media and growth conditions for activation experiments”) to exclude that the addition of estrogens already results in elevated levels of SMs without any sgRNA-directed targeting of VPR-dCas9 (Supplementary Fig. S4). Finally, during activation experiments, sgRNA-carrying strains and control strain (i.e. VPR4) were treated as described in section “Media and growth conditions for activation experiments”. Target gene transcription was measured by reverse transcriptase quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) and the mean fold change in expression was determined by comparing sgRNA-carrying strains to control strain (i.e. VPR4). Plasmids and strains that were used or created during this study are listed in Table 1 and Table 2.

hER-containing strains show slight stress phenotypes in the presence of DES

As the activation system is based the estrogen-inducible *VPR-dCas9*, we first tested if the combination of *hER* and estrogen already led to a background activity of the SM clusters which we planned to activate at a later step. For this, we first controlled the growth phenotypes of *hER*-containing strains and found that the activated estrogen receptor has a significant impact on growth of the strains when elevated amounts of DES are applied. The phenotype of the strain VPR4 and strains additionally carrying a guide RNA was identical. Strains that do not carry *hER* (i.e. FGSC A1153) are not affected by elevated DES levels (Supplementary Fig. S3). To check if *hER* is the cause for this phenotype, two other strains that only carry the *hER* under a constitutive promoter were also grown under same conditions (data not shown). This experiment verified that the activated estrogen receptor causes this phenotype which is in accordance with our previous observations (Pachlinger et al. 2005). The maximal inducer concentration that was tolerated by the actual strains without displaying any morphological phenotype was above 33 pM DES. One hundred pM DES already showed a clear reduction in colony diameter. Consequently, for subsequent activation

Fig. 2 VPR-dCas9 activation and experimental design. Green or grey rectangulars represent expressed or not expressed genes respectively. Green arrows indicate active promoters while orange arrows represent promoters poised for activation. **a** All strains carry plasmid VPR4 (control as well as activation strains). pVPR4 contains the constitutively expressed (P.const; cyan) human estrogen receptor gene (hER) which is inactive in absence of the inducer. Upon induction with DES, hER is activated and able to bind to estrogen response elements (EREs; vertical yellow bars) which are present in the engineered VPR-dCas9 gene promoter. Upon binding, hER facilitates transcription of the gene that codes for VPR-dCas9. **b** In the control strain (only pVPR4), sgRNAs are not expressed and thus VPR-dCas9 is present in the cell but not targeted to the designated region of interest (horizontal violet bars). The activation

strains (pVPR4 and one or more psgRNA with functional sgRNA cassette) constitutively express sgRNA(s) (target sequence in violet) which guide VPR-dCas9 to the region of interest (horizontal violet bars) and facilitate transcription of the targeted gene (i.e. TF). Hence, the activation strain should experience an elevated expression of the targeted gene compared with the control strain, which can only be attributed to the presence of the sgRNA. In one application, the targeted gene could be a transcription factor gene (TF) of a silent BGC and forced expression of this TF gene could subsequently lead to the upregulation of the whole cluster as shown in the figure. In another scenario, several sgRNAs could be targeted to many genes within a predicted cluster and the cognate metabolite(s) could be identified subsequently

experiments, 33 pM DES was chosen as final inducer concentration which has already been documented to trigger strong activation (Pachlinger et al. 2005). Furthermore, this concentration had no effect on dry mass accumulation. The effect on SM background levels was not significant (Supplementary Fig. S4). We concluded that the system is suitable to be applied for the forced activation of the chosen SM cluster genes.

Activation of the silent monodictyphenone gene cluster

For a proof-of-concept, we chose the monodictyphenone (*mdp*) cluster of *A. nidulans* which was shown to be silent under standard laboratory conditions in a wild-type strain because the cluster is subject to negative chromatin-level control by the COMPASS (Bok et al. 2009) and the H3K4 demethylase KdmB (Gacek-Matthews et al. 2016). The *mdp* cluster comprises at least 10 genes. Among them are *mdpE*, which encodes a transcription factor, and *mdpG*, the backbone gene which encodes a non-reducing PKS (NR-PKS). This BGC was analysed in more detail by Chiang and colleagues who showed that overexpression of *mdpE* is necessary and sufficient to activate the backbone gene *mdpG* and all other cluster genes to eventually synthesise the final product monodictyphenone (Chiang et al. 2010). We therefore guided VPR-dCas9 to the *mdpE* gene promoter. An overview on the cluster, its expression profile under primary and secondary

metabolic conditions and corresponding nucleosome positioning maps are shown in Fig. 3.

To test the effect of different VPR-dCas9 positions in relation to the predicted NFRs, we designed 4 different sgRNAs according to the high-resolution map of the *mdpE* upstream region including the 5' untranslated region (UTR) and nucleosome positions as shown in Fig. 4a. The sgRNAs m1 and m2 were positioned close to the predicted TSS of *mdpE*; m3 was positioned directly inside the first obvious upstream NFR which encompasses roughly 50 bps and lies around 300 bps upstream of the TSS. Finally, m4 was selected to bind even further upstream from the TSS, i.e. roughly 600 bps upstream (Fig. 4a). There would be another NFR at ~700–800 bps upstream but RNA-seq data suggest that this could very well belong to the downstream UTR of the gene AN0149 and was therefore not considered for sgRNA design. The expression analyses of *mdpE* in strains having VPR-dCas9 positioned at these different places either alone or in combination with other sgRNAs are shown in Fig. 4b. Interestingly, in this promoter, positioning of VPR-dCas9 by any single sgRNA is obviously not sufficient for activation of *mdpE* because all measured transcript levels were in the range of the control strain. A clear activation potential was mediated only by sgRNA combinations of either two or all four guide RNAs. The combination of m1 + m2 (m1&2) already showed a clear activation of *mdpE* in the range of 7-fold higher transcript levels compared with the background found in the control strain grown under the same conditions. When m2 was

Fig. 3 Overview of the monodictyphenone cluster of *A. nidulans*. The section spans the whole cluster. Apart from gene annotations (arrows), nucleosome positioning as well as the mRNA profile (Gacek-Matthews et al. 2016) at nutrient-rich (15/17 h) and nutrient-depleted (48 h) conditions are depicted in purple and grey histograms respectively. White arrows are genes that are not necessary for the synthesis of the BGC

products. Grey, orange and ruby arrows are genes involved in the monodictyphenone biosynthesis. The orange arrow is the backbone gene of the cluster which encodes for the non-reduced polyketide synthase MdpG. The ruby arrow is the gene that encodes for the pathway-specific transcription factor MdpE which is the target for the activation by VPR-dCas9

Fig. 4 Targeted activation of the transcription factor gene *mdpE* via VPR-dCas9 and MdpE-mediated activation of the backbone gene *mdpG*. **a** Promoter region of the target gene *mdpE* together with RNA-seq data (grey histograms; Gacek-Matthews et al. (2016)) and nucleosome positioning maps (purple histograms) under nutrient-rich (15/17 h) and nutrient-depleted (48 h) conditions. The nucleosome-free region (NFR) is shown in grey white pattern which is delimited by the nucleosomal borders (set to an offset of 75 base pairs proximal to the dyad axis of the neighbouring nucleosomes). The dyad axes are shown in vertical blue dashed lines and were set at the peak of the nucleosome histogram. Positions of sgRNAs are depicted in red (m1–m4). **b** Expression of the gene *mdpE* in the controls (only pVPR4) and strains that additionally carry one or more sgRNAs (m1 | m2 | m3 | m4 | m1&2 | m2&3 | mAll) that target the promoter region of the gene *mdpE*. **c** Expression of the backbone gene *mdpG* in the same samples as shown in **b** which is caused by the activation of *mdpE*. Cultures were done in triplicates, and qPCR was done in technical duplicates. A Student's *t* test was used to verify the significance of the activation over the controls (i.e. VPR4) (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$)

combined with m3 (m2&3) that binds to the NFR, the activation was rising to 10-fold above background levels. The highest potential was found when all four chosen sgRNAs m1 to m4 (mAll) were expressed in one strain together with VPR-dCas9. In this case, *mdpE* expression was activated roughly 30-fold over the background of the control strain. These results indicate that both spatial positioning and the amount of VPR-dCas9 present at the promoter define the functionality of this fusion protein as synthetic activator.

To see if the *mdpE* expression levels are sufficiently high to yield a functional amount of the MdpE

transcription factor, we tested the same samples also for expression of *mdpG*. RT-qPCR analysis shown in Fig. 4c documents that the forced expression of *mdpE* results in upregulation of its target gene *mdpG*. We detected a similar expression pattern of both genes. Consistent with the function of MdpE as cluster-specific TF, activation of *mdpG* was only achieved in samples where *mdpE* was expressed successfully, i.e. when at least two different sgRNAs were expressed simultaneously in the strain. Even if the expression levels of the two genes show a similar trend, it should be noted, however, that the

amplitude of *mdpG* activation was much lower than for the “direct” VPR-dCas9 target *mdpE* (note the scale in y-axes of Fig. 4b and Fig. 4c).

Activation of a silent BGC of unknown function

As second example for proof-of-concept, we chose a predicted gene cluster for which no experimental evidence is available so far and no cognate metabolite is known. Genes at this target location are predicted to be part of the BGC-AN8504 (Inglis et al. 2013) which is a putative *gliP*-like NRPS (Cerqueira et al. 2014). A cluster prediction program delineates the putative BGC (prediction tool antiSMASH (Medema et al. 2011)) comprising presumably 16 genes from AN8495 to AN8508 and containing the putative NRPS-encoding gene AN8504 as well as a putative TF encoded by AN8506 (Fig. 5). The nucleosome maps of this region show that the predicted BGC has a number of pronounced nucleosome-free regions which made it suitable for our tests.

We targeted the promoter of the TF gene AN8506 which seems to share a very small 305 bp-control region with the divergently transcribed gene AN8507 encoding a predicted transmembrane transport protein (Cerqueira et al. 2014). The control region contains a clearly formed NFR that would perfectly serve as entry point for sgRNAs to position our activator. Interestingly, despite sharing a common promoter, the transcriptional levels differed between both genes under

previously tested conditions (Schinko et al., 2010, Gacek-Matthews et al. 2016; see Fig. 5). While AN8506 (TF) was weakly transcribed in both 17 h and 48 h cultures (nutrient-limited conditions; see RNA-seq data in Fig. 5), the transmembrane protein AN8507 was completely silent. This bidirectional promoter region therefore served a suitable site to test how the positioning of VPR-dCas9 in relation to the TSS of the divergently transcribed genes influences their transcription pattern. The expression profiles and nucleosome positioning maps of all genes putatively forming a BGC are shown in Fig. 5.

AN8506 and AN8507 are controlled by a bidirectional promoter of only 305 bps in length that clearly contains a NFR roughly in the middle (Fig. 6a). We designed two different sgRNAs for targeting VPR-dCas9 inside the NFR. The idea was to test how the position of the activator in relation to the gene would influence its activation potential. sgRNA A1 was designed to bind close to AN8506 and A2 should bind close to AN8507. The high-resolution nucleosome positioning map in Fig. 6a shows that the +1 nucleosome of the moderately expressed gene AN8506 is very well positioned at both time points while this is not the case for AN8507. In the activation experiment shown in Fig. 6b, we found that AN8506 is moderately activated by both sgRNAs in a similar range, i.e. roughly 6-fold by A1 and 3.5-fold by A2 suggesting that A1 positions VPR-dCas9 slightly better in relation to the general transcriptional machinery responsible for AN8506

Fig. 5 Overview of the predicted cluster AN8504 of *A. nidulans*. The cluster (as predicted by antiSMASH) begins at gene AN8495 and ends at AN8508. Nucleosome positioning as well as the mRNA profile (Gacek-Matthews et al. 2016) at nutrient-rich (15/17 h) and nutrient-depleted (48 h) conditions is depicted in purple and grey histograms respectively. The backbone gene (AN8504; orange arrow) shows no transcription at either condition. Two sgRNAs were designed that target VPR-dCas9 to

the bidirectional promoter that regulates the genes AN8506 and AN8507 (red frame). AN8506 (ruby arrow) is the putative transcription factor and AN8507 (cyan arrow) is the putative membrane protein. AN8506 shows a low basal transcription level (comparable with 0.32 times of the expression level of the housekeeping gene *benA*) while AN8507 shows no reads at either condition

Fig. 6 Targeting of VPR-dCas9 to a bidirectional promoter and activation of its underlying genes AN8506 and AN8507. **a** The section shown comprises the begin of both genes AN8506 and AN8507 which share a bidirectional promoter of around 305 base pairs. The histograms show the mRNA profile (grey; Gacek-Matthews et al. (2016)) and the nucleosome positioning (purple) under nutrient-rich (15/17 h) and nutrient-depleted (48 h) conditions. The nucleosome-free region (NFR) is shown in grey white pattern which is delimited by the nucleosomal borders (set to an offset of 75 base pairs proximal to the dyad axis of the neighbouring

nucleosomes). The dyad axes are shown in vertical blue dashed lines and were set at the peak of the nucleosome histogram. Positions of sgRNAs are depicted in red (A1 and A2). **b** Expression data of the activation experiment: Controls: VPR4 (no sgRNA), A1: VPR4-A1-T1 to T3 | A2: VPR4-A2-T1 to T3. Three independent transformants per sgRNA (T1, T2, T3). Cultures were executed in triplicates. qPCR was performed in technical duplicates. Reproducibility was verified by two independent conduction of the experiment. The significance of the activation effect was verified by a Student's *t* test (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$)

transcription. Although the promoter architecture suggests a bidirectionally active regulatory unit, the divergently transcribed AN8507 gene is far stronger activated than AN8506 by both A1 and A2. The fact that the activation potential of VPR-dCas9 is weaker on genes that are already moderately expressed supports this finding (Chavez et al. 2016). However, when comparing the effect of sgRNA A1 and A2 for the activation of gene AN8507, it gets apparent that even small changes in positioning of the activator lead to huge differences in the resulting gene activation. sgRNA A1 and A2 are only 50 bps apart from each other. Despite this small genomic distance, VPR-dCas9 can upregulate gene AN8507 only 30-fold when positioned by sgRNA A1 but is able to boost the transcription to 4,000-fold when positioned by sgRNA A2 (compared with control strain VPR4!). While a molecular explanation for the huge difference in activation

potential remains obscure, this case documents again how significant the impact of sgRNA positioning in relation to the (predicted) TSS of the target gene is.

Next, we also wanted to see whether upregulation of the TF AN8506 was sufficient to result in the expression of the NRPS-encoding gene AN8504. We therefore tested the same samples for transcription of the AN8504, but our RT-qPCR results did not detect any signal in these samples (data not shown). This indicates that expression of the TF or the transporter gene residing inside a BGC is not sufficient to turn on the backbone gene of the predicted cluster or that TF AN8506 does not positively regulate the backbone gene AN8504 at all. Using our novel VPR-dCas9 system and targeting different sgRNAs to all genes predicted to form the BGC would be a promising way to upregulate the whole cluster independently of a transcription factor. Therefore, it still could be possible to

assign a product to this cluster and even to decipher the cognate biosynthetic pathway.

Discussion

Programmable transcriptional regulation is a powerful tool for the study of gene functions in general and for the activation of silent fungal BGCs in particular. The system presented here features a couple of advantages over traditional promoter replacements, in trans TF overexpression or heterologous expression strategies previously used to control gene expression.

Keeping the genomic arrangement of the targeted locus intact

One advantage of the system is that the genetic locus of interest (e.g. a predicted BGC for which no product is known so far) is not perturbed by introduced recombinant DNA. In traditional systems, artificially introduced constitutive or inducible promoters are recombined at the locus usually with a selection marker and vector sequences (Weld et al. 2006). These changes in genomic locus arrangements may lead to silencing of the introduced genetic material (e.g. selection marker) or nearby genes if the integration event is located directly in, or adjacent to a heterochromatic region due to position effect. This was shown in *Drosophila* (position effect variegation (Elgin and Reuter 2013; Henikoff 1990)), yeast and also filamentous fungi (telomere position effect (Allshire et al. 1994; Gottschling et al. 1990; Palmer and Keller 2010)). The VPR-dCas9 activator functions in the context of the native locus similar to a classical transcription activator. The sgRNA-dCas9 module functions quasi as DNA-binding domain of this synthetic factor, and by a simple change of the sgRNA sequence, it can easily be targeted at different positions in relation to the core promoter (TATA or CCAAT box) (Chang et al. 2013; Kinghorn and Turner 1992). It is well established that the interplay between the general transcription factor machinery which assembles at the core promoter as pre-initiation complex (PIC) and the transcriptional activators binding to control elements upstream of the PIC is critical for promoter activity (Soutourina 2018). This is because the Mediator complex must be correctly situated to be able to connect the factors bound at the control elements to the PIC at the core promoter. If this arrangement is not optimal, promoter activity will be low (Dobi and Winston 2007). This aspect becomes particularly important when bidirectional promoters are targeted. Insertion of recombinant DNA during promoter replacement strategies disrupts co-regulation of the neighbouring genes risking regulatory off-target effects on the other gene with unknown consequences (loss- or gain-of-function phenotypes).

Providing an optimal landing platform and distance for the activator to the general transcription machinery

Stable interaction of an activator with DNA in promoter control elements is facilitated by binding of the factor within a NFR. Typical RNA-Pol II-transcribed fungal promoters feature such NFRs in a distance of average ~ 200 bp upstream of the start codon respectively from -111 to -5 of the TSSs (Chen et al. 2013; Yuan et al. 2005). As the NFR is flanked by nucleosome -1 at the promoter proximal and nucleosome -2 at the promoter distal side, the location of the NFR in relation to the core promoter is clearly also critical. The possibility to guide VPR-dCas9 to different positions within a promoter is another invaluable advantage of the presented system. Of course, to be able to provide an optimal landing platform for VPR-dCas9 in the NFR of a targeted gene promoter, a nucleosome positioning map of this locus needs to be available. Optimally, recording of these nucleosome maps by MNase-Seq should be done under the same conditions than the planned VPR-dCas9 activation because it is known that some genes have NFRs that are not static and thus nucleosomes may be differently positioned under changing environmental or developmental conditions (Lai and Pugh 2017). For example, the nitrate-responsive nucleosome shifting in the *niaA-niaD* intergenic region in *A. nidulans* is one of the paradigmatic examples for such regulation (Berger et al. 2006, 2008; Muro-Pastor et al. 1999). In any case, the possibility to move activator positioning sites to different positions in respect to the core promoter represents a unique advantage of the dCas9-based activators. Although the construction of a genome-wide nucleosome positioning map is not a widely implemented method in fungal laboratories, it is not a prerequisite to be able work with VPR-dCas9. The map only has to be generated once per strain and condition. This means that the map generated during this study can also be used by other research groups for the gRNA design to target other *A. nidulans* BGCs.

Advantages of the dCas9-based system over traditional TF overexpression strategies

Several silent BGCs have been successfully activated by overexpression of the proprietary TF gene from a distant locus. The rationale of this approach is that a predicted TF-encoding gene lying next to genes probably forming a BGC is presumably the activator of all genes in its vicinity. Most likely, they all together would form a functional BGC, but so far, nobody was able to find conditions under which these genes—including the TF—are expressed and hence the cluster product is not known. Therefore, the cluster-external forced expression of the TF may activate all genes (ideally the corresponding BGC) under its control and a novel product may be

identified. However, there are important limitations to this approach: (i) many BGCs do not contain a predicted TF (Keller 2019). (ii) If the overexpressed TF requires condition-specific post-translational modifications (e.g. phosphorylation, protein processing) for its activity, but the corresponding conditions are not known, the TF will be present but inactive (Karin and Hunter 1995; Mingot et al. 2001). The VPR-dCas9 system presented here can circumvent these two problems as no PTMs are known to be required for its activity. (iii) In some cases, the upregulation of the cluster does not necessarily lead to product formation which is discussed in the next section.

A possibility to activate the cluster stepwise and hence reveal the biosynthetic pathway

Although we have not yet demonstrated its feasibility, the system provides the possibility to activate a BGC stepwise and under controlled timing conditions. The inducible expression of the VPR-dCas9 activator by addition of estrogen provides a simple control tool for this purpose. By designing a sgRNA-multiplex system similar to the procedure published by Nødvig and colleagues (Nødvig et al. 2018), one, two or more genes within a predicted BGC can be activated simultaneously. The activation of the core biosynthetic backbone gene (PKS, NRPS, prenyltransferases, terpene cyclases or hybrids thereof) in combination with different putative modifying or decorating enzymes and transporters will provide the possibility to elucidate different metabolic products originating from the cluster. If each step is accompanied by high-resolution mass spectrometry of the resulting cultures, new products and their biosynthetic intermediates can be defined and assigned to the corresponding gene. The VPR-dCas9 system thus not only provides the possibility to study the effect of different gene combinations on the metabolic profile, but at the same time, the individual biosynthetic steps could be deciphered. As the system also supports the targeting of VPR-dCas9 to all genes of a BGC simultaneously, the forced overexpression of the whole cluster without a single promoter exchange is possible. Some clusters however do not produce a (detectable) compound despite all their genes being overexpressed. Possible reasons for this phenomenon could be that (i) the compound is only produced in small amounts that are below the limit of detection or are camouflaged by the background noise of other metabolites, (ii) an incomplete or mutated BGC that lost important functional elements during evolution or (iii) necessary precursor compounds (e.g. acetyl-coA, amino acids, etc.) are in limiting concentrations or not available at all under the chosen growth condition (e.g. precursor is produced by another (inactive) cluster) (Chiang et al. 2016; Keller 2019). A good example is the interplay between the aspercryptin and the cichorine cluster of *A. nidulans*. The aspercryptin cluster (AN7884) was shown to be upregulated

during cocultivation of *A. nidulans* with *Streptomyces hygroscopicus* (Schroeckh et al. 2009). No BGC product could however be detected. Another publication revealed that the cichorine cluster, which is only active on yeast extract sucrose medium, provides the precursor compound for the aspercryptin cluster (Chiang et al. 2016). Hence, without the active cichorine cluster, the active aspercryptin cluster cannot synthesise aspercryptin. This however was only detectable in an engineered dereplication strain which was missing the 8 most highly expressed secondary metabolite gene clusters and hence had a low level of background noise during metabolite measurement. These examples provide clear evidence that even with strong gene expression, there is not necessarily a detectable product emerging. The prospect that many silent BGCs of scientifically underrepresented fungal species, which are not easily amenable to molecular genetic methods, could be activated with the VPR-dCas9 system makes it a promising tool for future applications for novel drug discovery.

A discovery platform suitable for many genes and fungi

The transfer of this technique to other fungal species is highly likely as long as suitable vectors and reliable transformation protocols exist. Even for genetically less amenable fungi, VPR-dCas9 could be envisaged as an episomal version (i.e. AMA1) or by transformation of a ribonucleoprotein complex. This has been shown already for fungi to work for mutagenesis approaches (Foster et al. 2018; Kuivanen et al. 2019; Nødvig et al. 2018). For mutagenesis, however, only a low copy number of the Cas9 enzyme is required and loss of the nuclease and sgRNA would even be an advantage after mutagenesis has been achieved. In contrast, it is likely that a much higher number of synthetic VPR-dCas9 activator molecules are required when it comes to act as efficient transcriptional regulator at one or more gene promoters. There is no experience to these approaches and future experiments will test its applicability. Application of the system obviously is not restricted to BGCs. It is likely to work as a shuttle system for chromatin and DNA-modifying enzymes altering nucleosomal PTM signatures and the chromatin architecture at the targeted locus. Fusions of dCas9 to such chromatin or DNA modifiers are thus a promising tool to study downstream pathways involved in epigenetic regulation. It should also be mentioned that dCas9 could be fused to a transcriptional repressor or used for transcriptional interference (CRISPRi). This way, also essential genes could be inactivated or knocked down in an inducible manner. This would open new opportunities to elucidate the essentiality of the gene of interest with respect to the developmental state of the fungus (Hilton et al. 2015; Larson et al. 2013).

Guide RNA design as a key factor for activation

The design and positioning of the sgRNAs (i.e. position of VPR-dCas9 in the genome) is a crucial factor for proper function. The majority of Cas9 applications concern the cutting of one or both DNA strands within a gene body (Ran et al. 2013). Once the Cas9 protein can cause a nick or a double-strand break that is erroneously repaired by the DNA repair machinery, presence of Cas9 at the locus is neither necessary nor likely anymore (Brinkman et al. 2018). The story is however different for the activator VPR-dCas9. Not only is the protein bigger, which can lead to steric hindrances at the desired locus, but the outcome of an experiment is not determined by a one-time event (i.e. erroneous DNA repair) but is the result of a persistent presence of the activator at the desired locus. The residence time of dCas9 at the target locus also greatly depends on the guide RNA (Ma et al. 2016). Many transcription-relevant proteins and their binding sites (e.g. RNA-Pol II complex, nucleosomes, transcription factors, CCAAT box binding proteins, TATA box) are in the promoter which on the one hand should not be blocked, but on the other hand, can interfere with the VPR-dCas9 activator (Chen et al. 2013; Mao and Chen 2019; Nikolov and Burley 1997). Furthermore, the activator has to be positioned at a location where it can actually trigger transcriptional activation. However, if the sgRNA is designed in a way which positions VPR-dCas9 too close to the TSS, the transcription could get blocked or reduced due to CRISPRi effects (Larson et al. 2013). Therefore, the chromatin and nucleosome map at the target location can have a major impact on accessibility of VPR-dCas9 to the DNA and therefore its efficiency (Chen et al. 2016; Chung et al. 2020). Many promoters contain loosely attached nucleosomes or even NFRs which could be good entry points for VPR-dCas9 (Yadon et al. 2010).

Limitations of the system (as tested so far)

Despite our promising first results and hypothetical great possibilities, during our work, we observed several important limitations and possible hurdles for an establishment of the system as efficient expression platform. The shortcomings we experienced were, e.g. quite strong variation in expression strengths. For example, the activation pattern of *mdpG* is similar to the induction of *mdpE* but overall expression is much weaker. There is no obvious explanation for that. However, one possibility could be that *mdpA*—an important co-activator for the monodictyphenone BGC (Chiang et al. 2010)—was not targeted and activated together with *mdpE*. It was shown that the cluster activity is significantly reduced if *mdpA* is deleted. It is still not clear if *mdpA* is under the transcriptional control of MdpE. It could also be that they are regulated independently and that complex formation of MdpE and MdpA is needed to exert its full activating function on the other genes

of the cluster. Such a scenario would be consistent with our results. In addition, the strength of activation depends on the position of the gRNA. In case of the very short bidirectional promoter between genes AN8506 and AN8507, even a distance of 50 bps can change the activation potential for about a thousand-fold. It is unlikely that only the short distance accounts for the difference in activation. It seems more likely that other (regulatory) proteins or protein complexes are either hindered during assembly by VPR-dCas9 or, vice versa, that the activator is not able to access the DNA properly. To know the exact proteomic composition at the promoter would help evaluating the outcome of the experiments and give more insight about efficient positioning of gRNAs for optimal gene activation.

Proper sgRNA design and positioning is probably the most crucial aspect of this system. As observed in this study and a study conducted by Li et al. (2017), it is apparent that the distance of the activator to the TSS is the key element to a successful activation which also could lead to a long trial and error phase before finding the proper sgRNA. This would especially mean a huge drawback in case of multiplex sgRNA experiments which would negate some of the benefits of this method. To circumvent this problem and facilitate efficient designing of guide RNAs in the future, we plan to analyse many different promoters by applying several sgRNAs individually (i.e. “guide RNA walking” along the promoter) and assessing the resulting activation. The aim here will be to find common patterns where VPR-dCas9 can effectively be deployed. The outlook is very promising as Li et al. (2017) did a similar experiment in plants. They tested multiple sgRNAs on several promoters in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and found out that the maximal activation occurred between 42 and 210 base pairs upstream of the TSS with a tendency towards regions below 110 base pairs. A proper analysis of this aspect will not only benefit transcriptional activator systems based on dCas9 in fungi but also in other Eukarya.

The fact that activations that range in the thousand folds compared with the basal, non-induced level can be achieved makes it a very promising tool for forced gene activation approaches. To effectively use this tool, the proper design of guide RNAs has to be further studied and optimised. The finding of patterns for in silico prediction of best sgRNA-binding sites would demand in depth research on more promoter/gene types with larger experimental setups (“guide RNA walking” along the promoter) and detailed promoter characterisation like local proteomic composition analyses at the targeted promoters.

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Authors' contributions Study design: AS, LS and JS. Performed research: AS, LS, AG and MS. Analysis of data: AS, HB and MS. Writing of manuscript: AS, LS and JS. All authors read and approved the manuscript.

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Data availability RNA-seq data are available at NCBI GEO under the accession number GSE72126 (Gacek-Matthews et al. 2016).

MNase-seq data are available at NCBI SRA under the accession number SRR12336645 and SRR12336644.

All strains are available upon request from the lab of the corresponding author.

Compliance with ethical standards

This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any of the authors.

Conflict of interest The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethics approval Not applicable.

Consent to participate Not applicable.

Consent for publication Not applicable.

Code availability Not applicable

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2.2 Publication II

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1 **Genome analysis and elucidation of the biosynthetic**
2 **pathway for the cRAS inhibitor rasfonin in**
3 ***Cephalotrichum gorgonifer***

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38 **Abstract:**

39 Background: Fungi are important sources for bioactive compounds that find their applications
40 in many important sectors like in the pharma-, food- or agricultural industries. In an
41 environmental monitoring project for fungi involved in soil nitrogen cycling we also isolated
42 *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* (strain NG_p51). In the course of strain characterization work we
43 found that this strain is able to naturally produce high amounts of rasfonin, a polyketide
44 inducing autophagy, apoptosis, necroptosis in human cell lines and shows anti-tumor activity
45 in RAS-dependent cancer cells.

46 Results: In order to elucidate the biosynthetic pathway of rasfonin, the strain was genome
47 sequenced, annotated, submitted to transcriptome analysis and genetic transformation was
48 established. Biosynthetic gene cluster (BGC) prediction revealed the existence of 22 BGCs of
49 which the majority was not expressed under our experimental conditions. In silico prediction
50 revealed two BGCs with a suite of enzymes possibly involved in rasfonin biosynthesis.
51 Experimental verification by gene-knock out of the key enzyme genes showed that one of the
52 predicted BGCs is indeed responsible for rasfonin biosynthesis.

53 Conclusions: The results of this study lay the ground for molecular biology focused research in
54 *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer*. Furthermore, strain engineering and heterologous expression of
55 the rasfonin BGC is now possible which allow both the construction of rasfonin high producing
56 strains and biosynthesis of rasfonin derivatives for diverse applications.

57

58 **Keywords:** Secondary metabolism, *Cephalotrichum*, *Doratomyces NG_p51*, rasfonin,
59 transcriptome analysis, genome analysis, *in silico* retrosynthesis, biosynthetic gene cluster
60 prediction, natural products discovery

61

62 **Background:**

63 Fungi as producers of bioactive substances

64 Filamentous fungi have the potential to produce a countless number and huge diversity of
65 bioactive substances, also called secondary metabolites (SMs). Those substances fulfil many
66 different functions in the ecology and lifecycles of fungi. They are produced in response to
67 certain developmental stages, metabolic or environmental conditions and stresses, like
68 extreme temperatures (1), osmotic stress (2), UV-radiation (3), nutrient starvation (4, 5), in
69 defence to other organisms such as competitors (6), mating partners (7) and during host-
70 pathogen interactions as signalling molecules or virulence factors (8). SMs are thus molecules
71 that are not essential for viability, but provide a selective advantage in specific situations
72 during the life cycle of a fungal cell or colony. This is also the reason why almost all of these
73 substances are only produced by fungi when a specific developmental, metabolic or
74 environmental signal is present and genetically received. While some SMs can be potentially
75 used as pharmaceuticals (i.e., Lovastatin (e.g., *Pleurotus ostreatus*) (9), Penicillin (*Penicillium*
76 *sp.*) (10)), others can have detrimental effects as toxic food contaminant (i.e., aflatoxins
77 (*Aspergillus flavus*) (11), fumonisins or deoxynivalenol (*Fusarium sp.*) (12, 13), etc.).
78 Therefore, SMs are of major ecological, economical and medicinal importance.

79 Bioinformatic analysis suggests that fungal genomes typically hold the genetic information for
80 dozens of so-called biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs) that serve as blue prints for single SMs
81 (14), and even more than 90 different BGCs in a single species have been reported (15). This
82 genetic diversity gives rise to an enormous variety of SMs, even not considering the numerous
83 intermediate products that are being produced on the way (16). This makes fungi sheer endless

84 reservoirs for novel bioactive substances, given that there are estimated to be more than 5
85 million fungal species worldwide (17).

86 During a project that focused on the role of fungi within the nitrate assimilation process in
87 agricultural soil, a community analysis was performed that elucidated the composition of
88 species and the phylogenetic relationship of the genes responsible for nitrogen assimilation.
89 For a few isolates, among them *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* NG_p51 (previously classified as
90 *Doratomyces* sp.), an unusual placement of the nitrate assimilation genes has been observed
91 (18, 19). This led to the conclusion that there had to be an, until then, unknown way of
92 acquisition of the complete nitrate assimilation cluster including the nitrate transporter, the
93 nitrate reductase and the nitrite reductase by horizontal gene transfer. It was proposed that
94 the cluster was transferred from a donor at the base of the Pezizomycotina to a recipient in the
95 Microascales, to which *C. gorgonifer* belongs (20). Clustering of the three genes was retained,
96 which is otherwise unusual in the Sordariomycetes. These findings prompted us to investigate
97 also possible acquisitions of BGCs coding for SMs from other fungi to *C.gorgonifer*.

98 It is well established that the reason for no expression of BGCs under standard laboratory
99 conditions is chromatin-based silencing (21-25). We and others have thus used genetic or
100 chemical chromatin modification to leverage the production of novel SMs in a number of fungi
101 (e.g., treatment of *Doratomyces* sp. with the HDAC inhibitor valproic acid (26), deletion of a
102 chromatin remodeler-encoding gene, *kdmB* in *Aspergillus nidulans* (27, 28), removal of the
103 heterochromatic marks in *Fusarium fujikuroi* (29), etc.). For recent reviews on genetic and
104 “chemogenetic” methods to active silence BGCs for SMs see (25) and (30). Using a medium
105 throughput effort, we have tested hundreds of isolates from different environmental screening
106 campaigns for their capacity to produce novel SMs upon chromatin activation. In the case of
107 *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51, this led to the observation of bacterial growth inhibition and the
108 discovery of several additionally produced compounds (26).

109 Further investigation in our in-house metabolite screening facility (31) revealed that *C.*
110 *gorgonifer* is able to produce rasfonin, an SM initially isolated from *Talaromyces* strains and
111 found to induce apoptosis in ras-dependent tumor cells (32-35). Although rasfonin has the
112 potential of being a future pharmaceutical, the biosynthetic pathway is still not known. This,
113 however, would greatly assist further research on this SM and facilitate the generation of
114 rasfonin over-production strains for large scale applications. Therefore, we characterized *C.*
115 *gorgonifer* NG_p51 in more detail on a genomics, transcriptomics and metabolomics level and
116 established state-of-the-art molecular biology methods for this fungus. To elicit its putative
117 chemical potential, we also conducted experiments to activate BGCs in *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51
118 via inhibition of chromatin active enzymes.

119 We report here the biosynthetic pathway for rasfonin in *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51. Furthermore,
120 we established state-of-the-art molecular biology methods and performed various “omics”
121 analysis for further strain and species characterization (i.e., genome analysis, BGC prediction,
122 transcriptome analysis, morphological description, genetic transformation, CRISPR/Cas, ...).

123

124 **Results:**

125 **Strain characterization of *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* NG_p51**

126 Ecology and taxonomy

127 We previously isolated the fungal strain NG_p51 and according to the former taxonomic
128 positioning determined the genus of the strain by its ITS region as *Doratomyces* sp. (GenBank:
129 HQ115716.1) (18). In the meantime, the genus *Cephalotrichum* (Microasceae, Hypocreales)
130 has been reorganized and now contains also species formerly affiliated to the genera
131 *Doratomyces* and *Trichurus*. No sexual morphs have been observed. *C. gorgonifer* is
132 frequently found in soil, decaying plant materials, dung and on wet cellulosic materials
133 indoors. Occasionally it has also been isolated from human hair and respiratory samples. Their

134 temperature optimum is around 25°C to 30°C but also growth at 37°C has been observed for
 135 several isolates. There are however no indications for human pathogenicity but data in this
 136 regard is scarce (36, 37).

137 We performed a phylogenetic analysis with ITS sequences (=Internal transcribed spacer
 138 regions of the rDNA and 5.8S region) of strain NG_p51 (GenBank No.: HQ115716.1), together
 139 with the *C. gorgonifer* (including the Ex-epitype of *C. gorgonifer*: *Trichurus spiralis* CBS 635.-
 140 78) and *Cephalotrichum telluricum* (i.e.: closest outgroup) dataset as published by
 141 Woudenberg et al. (37). The resulting phylogenetic tree shows that our strain clearly belongs
 142 to the species *C. gorgonifer* and that the *C. telluricum* species are clustered as an outgroup as
 143 expected (Figure 1). We therefore designated the strain *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51.

144

145

Figure 1 Phylogenetic tree of *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* isolate NG_p51
A: Phylogenetic tree based on the ITS sequences of strain isolate NG_p51 together with several *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* isolates and *C. telluricum* strains as closest. The tree entries follow following pattern: "accession number- genus and species-isolate identifier". The phylogenetic analysis shows that strain isolate NG_p51 belongs to the species *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer*. The tree is drawn to scale, with branch lengths measured in the number of substitutions per site. The strain isolate (i.e. NG_p51) used for all experiments in this publication and the Ex-epitype are written in bold letters.

146

147 Morphology of *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51:

148 Colonies of *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51 reach a diameter between 35 -55 mm on oat meal
149 agar (OA), potato carrot agar (PCA) and potato dextrose agar (PDA) after 14 days at 25°C.
150 They effuse a dark greyish black (Figure 2 a) mycelium, consisting of nearly velutinous
151 layer of synnemata which are 1-2 mm in length (Figure 2 b) and formed by aggregation
152 of conidiophores (the annelophores). Numerous curled sterile setae are present
153 alongside the fertile part of the synnemata (Figure 2 c-d) and conidia are borne from
154 ampuliform annelids which appear smooth-walled and ovoidal to broadly ellipsoidal
155 with truncate base and rounded apex, measuring 4-6 x 3.5-4.0 µm (Figure 2 e).
156 Phenotypic traits of the strain NG_p51 (especially presence of undulate sterile setae,
157 greyish color of conidia *en-masse* as well as their shape and dimensions) are in perfect
158 concordance with the species concept of *C. gorgonifer* (Bainier) Sandoival-Denis, Gené
159 & Guarro (36), in older literature also described under a name *Trichurus spiralis*
160 Hasselbr. by Domsch et al. (38) and Ellis (39).

161

162 *Figure 2 Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* NG_p51. a-b. Colonies on OA after 14 d at 25°C (Petri dish = 9 cm diam). c. Synnemata in
 163 *situ*. d-e. setae and conidia. Scale bars: c = 200 µm, d = 20 µm, e = 10 µm

164

165 Additionally, the growth on malt extract agar plates (MEA) at 28°C, 30°C, 32.5°C, 35°C and
 166 37°C showed that NG_p51 behaves as published for *C. gorgonifer* (36). In the observed range,
 167 optimal growth was at around 28°C. At 35°C, radial growth was strongly impaired while at

168 37°C radial growth was arrested. However, within the inoculation spot, spores at 37°C were
169 germinating and mycelia density was increasing over the 4 days of incubation (Figure 3)

170

Figure 3 Radial growth of *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51 on MEA petri dishes at different 5 temperatures after 4 days.

171

172 SM analysis of *C. gorgonifer*

173 Initial work with NG_p51 revealed that it is capable of suppressing growth of *Staphylococcus*
174 *aureus* and two clinical methicillin resistant isolates of *S. aureus* when grown in the presence
175 of the HDAC inhibitor valproic acid. Valproic acid treatment increased the production of seven

176 antimicrobial compounds (cyclo-(l-proline-l-methionine), p-hydroxybenzaldehyde, cyclo-
177 (phenylalanine-proline), indole-3-carboxylic acid, phenylacetic acid and indole-3-acetic acid)
178 and also lead to the biosynthesis of an otherwise absent compound which was identified as
179 phenyllactic acid (26). Also, rasfonin has been found in these screens, although the production
180 of this bioactive compound was subsequently shown not to be dependent on valproic acid in
181 the growth medium (31). Initial analysis of the production conditions revealed that this
182 metabolite is produced on AMM liquid medium and detectable within 48 hours of incubation
183 (Figure 6). Although rasfonin is a well-known bioactive compound with potential applications
184 in cancer treatment (32-35), its biosynthetic pathway remains unknown. To decipher its
185 production pathway, we sequenced the genome and searched for the presence of BGCs
186 potentially coding for rasfonin production.

187

188 Genome analysis and gene annotation:

189 Whole genome shotgun sequencing of *C. gorgonifer* was performed by 454 pyrosequencing
190 yielding 1.78 Gb of raw sequence data which were assembled into 48 scaffolds of overall 35.9
191 Mb (49.4-fold coverage, N50 of 2.07 Mb). A total of 10,469 gene models were predicted using
192 two different GeneMark gene predictors and manual validation. The annotated ORFs account
193 for 43.8% of the genome. The overall GC content is 55%, while the average GC content of ORFs
194 is 60.3%. Genome sequence data and annotation was deposited in the European Nucleotide
195 Archive (ENA) at EMBL-EBI with the project number PRJEB15373 which can be accessed
196 online at (40).

197 Annotation of biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs):

198 Around 1 (41) to 25 genes (42) can be involved in the biosynthesis of single SMs. In most cases
199 these genes are coregulated and in collinear vicinity to each other forming so-called BGCs (43).
200 Genes within these clusters can code for proteins that are responsible for the biosynthesis of
201 the compound-defining backbone (polyketide synthase (PKS), non-ribosomal peptide

202 synthetase (NRPS), terpene synthase (TPS), ...), the modification of the chemical backbone
203 structure (e.g., cytochrome P 450, transferases, oxidoreductases, O-methyltransferases...), the
204 regulation (global or cluster specific transcription factors (TFs)) of the cluster genes or for
205 transport (delivery to compartments or export to surrounding media) (14, 44).

206 For BGC annotation, antiSMASH 6.0.1 for fungi (fungiSMASH) was used with standard
207 parameters (45). The prediction algorithm for fungal BGCs assigned 308 genes to 24 putative
208 BGCs. Six BGCs, showed homology to BGCs from other species with similarities ranging from
209 20% to 100% which are included in Table 1 with their respective references (Only the best
210 scoring homolog BGC is shown). Similarity in this case is defined as “percentage of genes
211 within the closest known compound that have a significant BLAST hit to genes within the
212 current region” (taken from antiSMASH documentation (45)). In total, ten PKSs and one
213 type3-PKS, three NRPS-PKS hybrids, five NRPSs, six NRPS-like proteins and three putative
214 TSs could be assigned.

215

216 Expression analysis of candidate biosynthetic genes and whole genome transcriptome 217 sequencing under different physiological conditions.

218 To obtain information about the genome wide differential expression pattern of BGC genes we
219 cultivated the fungus under conditions of active growth in liquid shake cultures for 24 hours in
220 Aspergillus minimal medium (AMM) and compared the expression pattern with cells in
221 stationary phase after 48 hours of growth on the same medium. Of all 10469 annotated genes,
222 717 genes that were predicted not to be part of a secondary metabolism pathway by antiSMASH
223 were up-regulated at 48h and 818 were down-regulated. From the 308 genes that are
224 putatively involved in secondary metabolism, 39 were up-regulated at the 48-hour timepoint
225 and 40 were down-regulated. The remaining 231 genes stayed unaffected. 8855 genes were not
226 differentially regulated between the two timepoints which are 85% of the annotated genes.

227 The whole transcript-dataset can be retrieved from the additional materials
 228 (Additional_file_2.xlsx). The whole transcriptome was uploaded at NCBI's Gene Expression
 229 Omnibus (GEO) (46) under the accession number GSE217303

230 To estimate the transcriptional activity of BGCs under the chosen conditions of active growth
 231 versus stationary phase, we categorized the transcriptional status of the key-enzymes within a
 232 given BGC into three states (Table 1 Column Expression; Cat.). The expression of category 1
 233 genes is not detectable or falls below the arbitrarily set threshold of biological relevance (see
 234 caption of Table 1) at both time-points (i.e. 14 of 29 genes). Category 2 genes (3 genes) are
 235 expressed only at one time point (i.e. either 24h or 48 hours) and the expression of category 3
 236 genes (12 genes) is above the threshold at both 24h and 48 hours, although their expression
 237 levels may vary between the two time points (7 genes with at least a 2-fold difference between
 238 the time points). The individual expression levels, differential regulation between 24h and 48h
 239 and their respective transcriptional category of all predicted key-enzyme encoding genes can
 240 be retrieved from Table 1.

241

ID	BB-gene(s)	Type	Expression (BB- gene)				Homologs (Species)	Similarity	Ref.
			24h	48h	Δ	Cat.			
1	DNG_00901	terpene	5.6	6.2	0.6	Cat3	-	-	
2	DNG_01262	T1PKS	5.3	5.6	0.3	Cat3	naphtalene BGC (<i>Daldinia eschscholzii</i>)	33 %	(47)
3	DNG_01539	T1PKS	1.7	3.7	2.0	Cat3	-	-	
4	DNG_02059	T3PKS	4.9	6.1	1.2*, +	Cat3	-	-	
5	DNG_02555	terpene	6.8	4.3	-2.5*, +	Cat3	-	-	
6	DNG_02774	T1PKS	0.0	6.4	7.7*, +	Cat2	-	-	
	DNG_02782	T1PKS	0.0	6.2	9.5*, +	Cat2	-	-	
7	DNG_03072	T1PKS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	
8	DNG_04293	NRPS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	
	DNG_04303	T1PKS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	
9	DNG_04582	NRPS- T1PKS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	betaenone A – C (<i>Phoma betae</i>)	25 %	(48)
10	DNG_04746	terpene	7.7	7.5	-0.1	Cat3	Squalestatin (<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.)	40 %	(49)
11	DNG_06431	T1PKS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	
12	DNG_07105	T1PKS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	
	DNG_07107	T1PKS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	
13	DNG_07411	NRPS	2.1	2.7	0.6	Cat3	-	-	
14	DNG_08044	NRPS	0.0	1.9	0.9	Cat2	phyllostictine A/B (<i>Phyllosticta cirsi</i>)	20 %	(50)

	DNG_08052	NRPS-T ₁ PKS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1			
15	DNG_08262	NRPS-like	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	-
16	DNG_08309	NRPS	5.4	1.4	-4.1 ^{*,+}	Cat3	Dimethylcoprogen (<i>Alternaria alternata</i>)	100 %	(51)
17	DNG_09028	NRPS-like	5.2	5.2	0.0	Cat3	-	-	-
18	DNG_09136	NRPS-like	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	-
19	DNG_09754	NRPS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	-
20	DNG_09868	NRPS-like	5.0	1.6	-3.4 ^{*,+}	Cat3	-	-	-
21	DNG_09951	NRPS-like	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	-
22	DNG_10196	NRPS-like	7.3	5.6	-1.7 ^{*,+}	Cat3	-	-	-
23	DNG_10230	NRPS-T ₁ PKS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	cytochalasin E / K (<i>Aspergillus clavatus</i>)	23 %	(52)
24	DNG_10425	T ₁ PKS	0.0	0.0	-	Cat1	-	-	-

242 *Table 1 Summary of BGCs of Cephalotrichum gorgonifer NG_p51 as predicted by antiSMASH. Columns: ID:*
243 *Cluster ID as assigned by antiSMASH; BB-gene(s): gene number of the key-enzyme encoding genes; type: type*
244 *of key- enzyme; Range (genes): The predicted borders of the BGC with the total gene count in parenthesis;*
245 *Expression: Expression of backbone genes at 24h and 48h are depicted as a 2-zone heatmap (weak expression |*
246 *red --> blue |strong expression), based on their RPKM value. An arbitrary log-value of 1 was considered as a*
247 *biologically relevant expression threshold under which, the expression was set to zero. The column “Δ” depicts*
248 *the differential expression between 24-hour and 48-hour samples and is visually supported by a 3-zone*
249 *heatmap (down-regulated @ 48h | blue --> white --> red | up-regulated @ 48h) with zero being the turning*
250 *point. A significance value of p<0.05 was applied as threshold which is indicated by an Asterix near the*
251 *differential expression value. If the differential expression is higher than 2-fold, it is indicated with an additional*
252 *“+”. The Cat.: Expression Category (Cat1: Silent at 24h and 48h; Cat2: Expressed at either 24h or 48h (i.e.*
253 *differentially expressed); Cat3 (Expressed at both 24h and 48h). Best scoring homolog BGCs in other species*
254 *that were found by antiSMASH are also displayed together with their similarity in % and references.*

255

256 **Prediction of the BGC responsible for rasfonin biosynthesis based on PKS** 257 **domain structure.**

258 Rasfonin (Figure 4) is an α-pyrone-containing natural product composed of two distinct
259 acetate-based polyketide (PK) chains. The PK chains are derived from the condensation of four
260 and six acetyl-CoA subunits resulting in the formation of a partially reduced and di- and
261 trimethylated tetra- and hexaketide, respectively, that are further modified (hydroxylation)
262 and finally linked via an ester bound. These chemical features suggest the involvement of two
263 highly-reducing PKS (HR-PKSs) containing, in addition to the essential acyltransferase (AT),
264 ketoacyl-synthase (KS), and acyl carrier protein (ACP) domains, domains involved in the
265 reduction of the growing PK chain, i.e., a ketoreductase (KR), a dehydratase (DH) and an

266 enoylreductase (ER). Next to this, the methyl groups at C6, C8, C10, and C4', C6', suggest the
267 presence of an intrinsic C-methyltransferase (MT) domain that functions in the transfer of a
268 methyl group from S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) to a β -ketoacyl-ACP substrate for both
269 involved PKSs.

270

271

Figure 4 Structure of rasfonin

272 We thus screened the genome sequence of *C. gorgonifer* for the presence of predicted PKS-
273 encoding genes that harbour a domain composition putatively fitting the enzymatic functions
274 necessary for rasfonin biosynthesis. Bioinformatic analysis of the 14 PKSs present in the *C.*
275 *gorgonifer* genome revealed that seven HR-PKSs harbour the necessary domain architecture
276 (Figure 5 A). Only two BGCs contain two HR-PKSs in close proximity to each other namely
277 BGC 6 (Table 1 ID 1) with the combination of [CgPKS4 +CgPKS5] (Figure 5 A) and BGC 12
278 (Table 1 ID 12) with the combination [CgPKS10 + CgPKS11] (Figure 5 A). Both also encode a
279 putative transferase, i.e., DNG_02776 and DNG_07106, respectively. To further define which
280 of the two BGCs is involved in rasfonin biosynthesis, we questioned our transcriptome data set
281 and found that only the BGC with the HR-PKS pair *CgPKS4* and *CgPKS5* (Figure 5 A; Table 1
282 ID 6) showed expression at 48 hours. The other candidate pair *CgPKS10* and *CgPKS11* (Figure
283 5 A; Table 1 - ID 12) were not expressed at any tested condition.

284 Next, we set out to analyse the extension of the *CgPKS4*/*CgPKS5* BGC. Our transcriptome data
285 showed a clear coregulation in expression of the genes that are positioned between *CgPKS4*
286 and *CgPKS5*. No transcription was observed 24 hours post inoculation (hpi) while expression
287 of all genes was significantly upregulated 48 hpi. The genes upstream of *CgPKS4* and

288 downstream of CgPKS5 were not coregulated (Figure 5 B). The GO annotations of adjacent
 289 genes do not suggest that they are involved in the synthesis of rasfonin. Thus, the BGC likely
 290 spans nine genes, i.e., DNG_02774-DNG_02782. To evaluate the contribution of the putative
 291 CgPKS4/ CgPKS5 BGC to rasfonin biosynthesis, one of the PKS-encoding genes, *CgPKS4*, was
 292 arbitrarily chosen for targeted gene disruption.

293

A

PKS	Gene ID	Gene length	Transcript 24h 48h		Type	Domain organisation
<i>CgPKS1</i>	DNG_01262		+	+	NR-PKS	SAT KS MAT PT ACP ACP TE
<i>CgPKS2</i>	DNG_01539		+	+	HR-PKS	KS AT DH MT ER KR ACP
<i>CgPKS3</i>	DNG_02059		+	+	Type III PKS	Chalcone/stilbene_synt_N Chalcone/stilbene_synt_C
<i>CgPKS4</i>	DNG_02774		-	+	HR-PKS	KS AT DH MT ER KR ACP
<i>CgPKS5</i>	DNG_02782		-	+	HR-PKS	KS AT DH MT ER KR ACP
<i>CgPKS6</i>	DNG_03072		-	-	HR-PKS	KS AT DH ER KR ACP
<i>CgPKS7</i>	DNG_04303		-	-	HR-PKS	KS AT DH MT ER KR ACP
<i>CgPKS8</i>	DNG_04582		-	-	PKS-NRPS	KS AT DH MT KR ACP C A T R
<i>CgPKS9</i>	DNG_06431		-	-	HR-PKS	KS AT DH ER KR ACP
<i>CgPKS10</i>	DNG_07105		-	-	HR-PKS	KS AT DH MT ER KR ACP cAT
<i>CgPKS11</i>	DNG_07107		-	-	HR-PKS	KS AT DH MT ER KR ACP
<i>CgPKS12</i>	DNG_08052		-	-	PKS-NRPS	KS AT DH MT KR ACP C A T R
<i>CgPKS13</i>	DNG_10230		-	-	PKS-NRPS	KS AT DH MT KR ACP C A T R
<i>CgPKS14</i>	DNG_10425		-	-	HR-PKS	KS AT DH MT ER KR ACP cAT

0 3 6 9 12 14 kbp

B

Figure 5 **A** Domain organization was analysed using the NCBI Conserved Domain (36), InterPro (37), SBSPKsv2 (38); and the PKS/NRPS Analysis Web-site (39). KS (red), keto synthase; AT (yellow), acyltransferase; DH (pink), dehydratase; MT (blue) C-methyltransferase; ER (grey) enoylreductase; KR (violet), ketoreductase; ACP (green), acyl carrier protein; cAT (orange), carnitine acyltransferase; Chalcone/stilbene_synt_N (lime-green): Chalcone/stilbene synthase N-terminal; Chalcone/stilbene_synt_C (dark-cyan): Chalcone/stilbene synthase C-terminal. The proposed PKS names are listed together with their gene number and length. The transcriptional activity at 24h or 48 hours ins indicated as “-” (No transcription at given timepoint) or “+” (transcription at given timepoint). The two PKS encoding genes that are proposed to be involved in the rasfonin synthesis (i.e. *CgPKS4* and *CgPKS5*) are highlighted by a red box **B** The proposed BGC for rasfonin biosynthesis is depicted with transcript at 24h and 48h timepoint (shake flask culture, AMM). The BGC borders are depicted in red and were assigned based on the coregulation of genes. Proposed BGC gene names (*rsf1* to *rsf9*) are depicted above gene illustrations.

294

295 **Experimental verification of the BGC involved in rasfonin biosynthesis**

296 The standard method to prove the involvement of a respective candidate gene in SM
297 biosynthesis is deletion of the coding region in the genome, accompanied by the loss of product
298 formation. However, so far *Cephalotrichum* sp. have not yet been genetically modified and
299 used for reverse genetics approaches. Therefore, a transformation method had to be
300 established with the aim to disrupt or mutate *CgPKS4* and show by chemical analysis that
301 rasfonin is not produced any longer in the transformed strain. To maximize the chance
302 obtaining *CgPKS4* mutations by transformation, three different approaches were selected, i.e.,
303 a Cas9 approach (Strain Cg-Cas9-02774-1), an agrobacterium-mediated transformation
304 approach (Strain Cg-At-02774-1) and also a homology directed repair (HDR) approach via
305 protoplast-mediated transformation of a linear fragment (Strain Cg-HDR-02774-1) (53, 54).
306 All three transformation methods were successfully implemented in our *C. gorgonifer* strain
307 NG_p51. Cas9 and the HDR transformations were performed on kryo-stocks of *C. gorgonifer*
308 protoplasts (see material and methods section).

309 Disruption of *CgPKS4* by Cas9 resulted in the strain Cg-Cas9-02774-1. Sequencing of the locus
310 revealed a 640 bp deletion ranging from base pair 269 (i.e.: sgRNA annealing site) to base pair
311 908 of the coding sequence (CDS), a mutation that additionally leads to a frameshift within the
312 remaining CDS of the gene (Sequence at Cas9- restriction site: 5'- ACCAATGCACCCGGT | 640
313 bp deletion | GTTCGACCACCGCGC -3') (see Additional_file_3.gbk).

314 The *A. tumefaciens* mediated mutation resulted in the transformant Cg-At-02774-1 that has
315 the first 2300 base pairs of *CgPKS4* (DNG_02774) replaced with the hygromycin resistance
316 cassette (hph), again resulting in a frameshift within the CDS. The 5'-end homology region
317 spans 1200 base-pairs upstream of the start codon (i.e. promoter region) and the 3'- homology
318 region spans 1500 base-pairs downstream of the exchanged fragment (i.e. first 2300 base pairs
319 of the gene body) (see Additional_file_3.gbk).

320 The transformant Cg-HDR-02774-1 resulted from the HDR-directed approach. Here, the same
321 replacement cassette was used as for the agrobacterium transformation (i.e., PCR product from

322 the “HDR-Fragment” primer pair with template pAt-DNGo2774; Additional_file_1.pdf Table
323 S 1). Both strains (i.e., Cg-At-02774-1 and Cg-HDR-02774-1) were PCR tested for the successful
324 gene replacement event (see Additional_file_1.pdf Figure S1; Additional_file_3.gbk))

325 To test if the mutated target gene is responsible for the biosynthesis of rasfonin, the
326 transformants and the recipient strain NG_p51 were cultivated in parallel. The fungal colonies
327 (mycelia + agar media) were extracted, and extracts were analysed by high performance liquid
328 chromatography (HPLC) for the presence of rasfonin. None of the three tested mutants showed
329 any detectable amounts of rasfonin (Figure 6 C, left) when compared to the wildtype NG_p51
330 (Figure 6 B, left). A 25 µg/mL rasfonin solution produced in our laboratory and verified by
331 NMR (see materials and methods) served as analytical standard (Figure 6 A). Next to this, we
332 spiked the wildtype sample with our standard thereby unequivocally proofing that the peak in
333 the wildtype chromatogram indeed is rasfonin (Figure 6 B and C, right), and that rasfonin is
334 missing in our *CgPKS4* mutants. To verify that not even trace amounts of rasfonin are
335 produced that are not detected by our HPLC method, we subjected an extract from the Cg-
336 Cas9-02774-1 strain to liquid chromatography-high resolution mass spectrometry (LC-

337 HRMS). The results of this analysis showed no detectable amounts of rasfonin in the mutant
338 strains (Additional_file_1.pdf Figure S2). This verifies that CgPKS4 (from now on referred to
339 as Rsf1) is indeed directly involved in the biosynthesis of rasfonin in *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51.

340 Next to *CgPKS4* (*rsf1*), eight genes are coregulated under rasfonin-inducing conditions
341 including a second PKS-encoding gene *CgPKS5* located at the end of the putative BGC. Thus,
342 we propose that the BGC involved in rasfonin biosynthesis stretches between *CgPKS4* and
343 *CgPKS5*, and comprises overall nine genes, *rsf1* to *rsf9* (Figure 5 B). Next to the PKSs, the BGC
344 encodes three putative cytochrome p450s (DNG_02775: *rsf2*; DNG_02779: *rsf6*;
345 DNG_02781: *rsf8*), a putative O-acyltransferase (DNG_02776: *rsf3*), a Major facilitator
346 family1 (MFS1) transporter (DNG_02777: *rsf4*), one FSH domain-containing protein
347 (DNG_02778: *rsf5*) as well as one uncharacterized protein (DNG_02780: *rsf7*).

348

349 **Discussion**

350 Rasfonin carries the potential of an anti-cancer pharmaceutical as it is active against several
351 tumour types. Several studies found that rasfonin suppresses proliferation of pancreatic cancer
352 cells with mutated K-ras which is an important oncogene affected in many cancer types. In K-
353 ras mutated cells rasfonin showed stronger activity compared to cells with wild-type K-ras. The
354 substance also reduced clone formation, invasion and migration of cells with mutated K-ras.
355 Although the exact mechanism is unknown, it was observed that rasfonin strongly
356 downregulates Ras activity and (directly or indirectly) reduces the expression of Son of
357 sevenless (Sos1), a nucleotide exchange factor which is involved in RAS activation (34). In renal
358 cancer cells, rasfonin promotes cell apoptosis and autophagy in connection with the protein
359 Akt (protein Kinase B) which is a frequently activated (i.e., phosphorylated) oncoprotein in
360 tumour cells (33). In another study, a similar effect against clonal formation and migration of
361 osteosarcoma 143B cells was also observed and autophagy was promoted (35). Another recent
362 study with rasfonin found a connection between rasfonin induced caspase-dependent
363 apoptosis and autophagy in ACHN cells (renal adenocarcinoma cell line) and the RPTOR and
364 RICTOR proteins. While RPTOR seems to play a role in the rasfonin-induced apoptosis
365 pathway, RICTOR is important for autophagy triggered by rasfonin (32). In a new study, Hou
366 and colleagues found a functional link between rasfonin activity and necroptosis. Rasfonin
367 enhanced Grb2 binding to a receptor-interacting kinase (RIP1), which plays a critical role in
368 regulating programmed necrosis. These data suggest that Grb2 actively participates in
369 rasfonin-induced necroptosis by interacting with components of the necrosome and mediating
370 their expression. In summary, at the actual stage of knowledge, rasfonin seems mainly to
371 trigger apoptosis and necroptosis through the activation of cellular pathways.

372 In fungi, the true physiological or ecological function of rasfonin remains obscure. No strong
373 antimicrobial activity has been detected so far. Available data from experiments with cancer
374 cell lines suggest a modulation of Ras-signalling pathways by rasfonin, which can suppress
375 proliferation of certain cell lines (34). As a colonizer of cellulosic plant litter, *C. gorgonifer*

376 would encounter numerous other eukaryotes, where alterations of their developmental
377 program through modulation of Ras signalling could be potentially advantageous for the
378 producing organism. However, other eukaryotic cells tested by us, such as *Saccharomyces*
379 *cerevisiae*, seem highly resistant to this compound (our unpublished preliminary
380 observations). The availability of KO strains without detectable rasfonin production will allow
381 to test hypotheses on rasfonin function in the natural environment. An interesting preliminary
382 observation of our study was that the metabolite does not seem to be actively exported into the
383 surrounding of the cell but stays within or attached to the mycelium in a fungal culture
384 (unpublished preliminary observation). Although there is an expressed gene within the BGC
385 that codes for a transporter, computational analysis of the predicted protein sequence by
386 MULOcDeep suggests that the transporter is targeted to a lysosome like membrane (55). This
387 indicates that an intermediate or the final compound is stored within extra compartments like
388 it is the case with fungal toxosomes (56, 57). Of course, some exporter, encoded by a gene
389 residing externally of the rasfonin BGC, might be responsible for export, but this topic needs
390 further investigation.

391 The biosynthesis of rasfonin is coordinated by two highly-reducing iterative type I PKSs. In
392 general, two scenarios are possible that may yield rasfonin. In a first scenario one PKS
393 generates a PK chain that serves as a starter unit and may be passed on to the second PKS for
394 further extension. This mechanism has been proposed for zearalenone in *F. graminearum*
395 (58), T-toxin in *Cochliobolus heterostrophus* (59), asperfuranone in *A. nidulans* (60) or
396 botcinic acid in *Botrytis cinerea* (61). In a second scenario two PKSs are involved in the
397 assembly of two distinct PK chains that are subsequently linked via an ester bond catalyzed by
398 an acyltransferase encoded within the same BGC as it has been shown for lovastatin in
399 *Aspergillus terreus* (62), and the related compactin in *Penicillium citrinum* (63). Noteworthy,
400 in rare cases one PKS is involved in the assembly of two distinct PK chains as it has been
401 recently shown for gregatin A in *Penicillium* sp. Sh 18 (64), or fusamarin in *Fusarium*
402 *mangiferae* (65), and which is likely also true for fujikurin in *Fusarium fujikuroi* (66, 67).

403 However, given the cluster architecture and co-regulation as well as the presence of two HR-
404 PKS- and one putative transferase-encoding genes in the rasfonin BGC, DNG_02776 (*rsf3*),
405 we propose the following route for rasfonin biosynthesis (Figure 7): One HR-PKS, Rsf1
406 (CgPKS4) or Rsf9 (CgPKS5), is involved in the programmed assembly of the partially reduced
407 6,8,10-trimethylated hexaketide (**1**) by successive condensations of acetyl-CoA with 5 malonyl
408 units, while the other assembles the 4',6'-dimethylated tetraketide (**4**). Noteworthy, none of
409 the HR-PKSs harbors a release domain, but the presence of Rsf5, a predicted thioesterase (TE)
410 with similarity to LovG from the lovastatin cluster (68), suggests that Rsf5 may function in the
411 release of the hexaketide. Similar *trans*-TEs have been shown to facilitate off-loading in the
412 case of fusarielin biosynthesis in *F. graminearum* (69), and fusamarin biosynthesis in
413 *Fusarium mangiferae* (65). The PK chain may be released either by TE-mediated hydrolysis
414 followed by the spontaneous intramolecular cyclization accompanied by dehydration yielding
415 **2**, or the cyclization happens directly through TE-catalysed pyrone formation as it has been
416 shown for the TE-domain of CTB1 involved in cercosporin biosynthesis in *Cercospora* sp. (70).
417 **2** is then further modified to yield **3** by hydrogenation and subsequent hydroxylation of C4.
418 The latter step is likely catalysed by one of the cytochrome p450s encoded within the BGC,
419 Rsf2, Rsf6 or Rsf8. Next, Rsf3, encoding a putative O-acyltransferase with similarity to LovD
420 (71) captures **4**, followed by the transacylation of **3** resulting in the formation of **5**, that is
421 further hydroxylated at C8' and C10' likely catalyzed by one or both of the remaining
422 cytochrome p450s encoded in the BGC, yielding the final product rasfonin (**6**).

424 Figure 7 Proposed biosynthetic pathway of rasfonin. **A** The rasfonin BGC. **B** The proposed pathway of rasfonin synthesis

425 Noteworthy, elucidation of the pathway was facilitated in this work by the availability of the
 426 whole genome and a genome-wide transcriptome along with a knowledge-based prediction of
 427 enzymatic domains which are known to synthesize similar molecules. But all this prediction
 428 work in the end needs experimental verification by targeted inactivation of the proposed
 429 biosynthetic gene. For non-model fungi, the transformation-mediated inactivation of a target
 430 genes is often not trivial. Our strategy was to follow three well-known strategies to reach that
 431 goal with a high probability of success. But still, some modifications of standard protocols
 432 were necessary. Here, we developed a modified version of common protoplastation protocols
 433 to ensure a cost- and time efficient method. The possibility to use kryo-stocks significantly
 434 increases the speed and flexibility of transformation experiments. As different fungi will need
 435 different conditions during protoplastation and post-transformation regeneration, we want
 436 to highlight a publication by Wu and co-workers (72) which compares the impact of different

437 buffer compositions and conditions on protoplastation and regeneration efficiency. The
438 publication assisted in the development of the protoplastation protocol for *C. gorgonifer* and
439 will surely also be of use in case of establishment of other fungal species for the laboratory
440 environment.

441 **Conclusions**

442 This work provided the tools and methods for working efficiently with the rasfonin producing
443 strain *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* NG_p51 in a laboratory environment. Thorough
444 characterization and analysis in form of genome analysis, transcriptomics, phylogenetic
445 analysis and morphology have been conducted which provide substantial information for
446 further research. The elucidation of the BGC that is responsible for the biosynthesis of
447 rasfonin enables strain and pathway engineering which could facilitate the development and
448 high yield production of this putative pharmaceutically relevant compound. The
449 establishment of three different transformation methods and the development of an adapted
450 protocol for protoplast and protoplast-kryo stock preparation of *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51
451 significantly speeds up molecular genetics work with this fungus and will also help with
452 establishing such methods in other fungal species. This will hopefully increase the pool of
453 species that can be deployed in a laboratory environment and therefore promote the research
454 on so far unknown novel BGCs.

455

456 **Materials and Methods:**

457 Phylogenetic tree: Evolutionary analysis by Maximum Likelihood method:

458 ITS sequences (For accession numbers see Figure 1) were aligned with the program MEGAX:
459 Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis across computing platforms (Version 10.2.6) (73)
460 with the ClustalW algorithm (standard parameters) (74). After alignment, sequences were
461 trimmed to equal length for the construction of the phylogenetic tree.

462 The tree with the highest log likelihood (-808.77) is shown. The percentage of trees in which
463 the associated taxa clustered together is shown next to the branches. Initial tree(s) for the
464 heuristic search were obtained automatically by applying Neighbor-Join and BioNJ algorithms
465 to a matrix of pairwise distances estimated using the Tamura-Nei model (75), and then
466 selecting the topology with superior log likelihood value. This analysis involved 21 nucleotide
467 sequences. There was a total of 557 positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses were
468 also conducted in MEGA X. Bootstrapping was performed 500 times.

469 Morphological analysis of strain NG_p51

470 For phenotypic characterization, the strain *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* NG_p51 was
471 transferred on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA, Fluka), Malt Extract Agar (MEA, Merck)
472 and Oatmeal Agar (OA) as described by (76) and incubated for 14 days in the dark at
473 25°C. For comparative description of the macroscopic and microscopic characteristics,
474 OA was used according to (36), and additionally compared to (39) and (38) where the
475 fungus is described and illustrated under the name *Trichurus spiralis* (current name:
476 *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* (36)). The photomicrographs were taken using a Motic BA
477 310 microscope with Motic Image Plus 3.0 software. Lactophenol blue was used as a
478 mounting medium for microphotography. Photographs of the colonies were taken with
479 a Sony DSC-RX100.

480 Growth phenotype at different temperatures

481 For determining the growth morphology under different temperatures, spores of strain
482 NG_p51 were grown by plating them from kyro-stocks (50% Tween-20 0.1% spore suspension
483 and 50% glycerol 50% (w/v)) on MEA plates at 30°C for 4 days. Spores were harvested by
484 scraping off the agar with a spatula and 0.1% Tween solution. The spore suspension was then
485 filtered through glass wool filled tips and a 1/1000 dilution was prepared (3 subsequent 1/100
486 dilutions; 100µL spore solution and 900 µL Tween 0.1%) were then counted in a counting

487 chamber (Neubauer improved; PC72.1 - Carlroth) and a dilution with a spore density of 100
488 spores/ μ L (Tween-20 0.1%) was prepared. 10 μ L of the spore solution was then applied in the
489 middle of a MEA plate and 3 plates each were incubated at 28°C / 30°C / 32,5°C / 35°C / 37°C
490 for 4 days. The growth was measured in mm diameter.

491 Genome sequencing and gene prediction

492 The genome sequencing and assembly of *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* was performed using a
493 whole-genome shotgun approach that explored paired-end 454 (LGC Genomics GmbH, Berlin,
494 Germany). Using Newbler v2.6. (Roche (2010) 454 Sequencing System Software Manual, v
495 2.5.3: Part C – GS De Novo Assembler, GS Reference Mapper, SFF Tools, 454. Life Sciences
496 Corp, A Roche Company, Branford) shotgun and 8kb-PE library reads were assembled into
497 702 contigs. Pre-assembled contigs were combined into 48 scaffolds using the SSPACE
498 algorithm (77). To predict genes on the scaffolds two ab initio gene predictor algorithms were
499 applied, GeneMark-S and GenMark-ES version 2.3 (78). Gene models differently predicted by
500 the algorithms were manually curated. The genome was analysed using the PEDANT system
501 (79) to allow comparative feature analysis.

502 Transcriptome: RNA sequencing and analysis

503 Total RNA extraction samples (24h/ 48h; 6 μ g each) were transferred to Vienna Biocenter Core
504 Facilities (80) for library preparation and Illumina high throughput sequencing using poly-A
505 enrichment kit (NEB) and Nextera Library prep kit. 50 bp single end sequencing was
506 performed using a HiSeq v4 Illumina sequencer. Obtained sequences were de-multiplexed,
507 quality controlled, filtered using trimmomatic 0.36 (81) and mapped on the *Cephalotrichum*
508 *gorgonifer* NG_p51 genome assembly (ENA project number PRJEB15373). Mapping was
509 performed using BWA (82). Mapping data were processed using samtools (83) and duplicate
510 reads were removed using Picard MarkDuplicates accessible at (84). Reverse transcripts were
511 counted using python script HTSeq (85). Normalization and statistics were done using
512 R/Bioconductor and the limma and edgeR packages, using mean-variance weighting (voom)

513 and TMM normalisation (86) and robust linear model fitting. A significance cut-off of $p < 0.05$
514 and an absolute difference of 1 (i.e. 2-fold regulation) was applied for analysis. Transcription
515 levels are log₂ read counts per kilobase of exon per million library reads (RPKM). For trace
516 graphs transcript coverage was calculated using bedtools genomecov (87, 88) for each bp
517 normalized to sequencing library sizes as log₂ scaled counts per million reads (CPM). All data
518 are available at NCBI GEO under the accession number GSE217303.

519

520 Molecular biology methods:

521 For gDNA extraction, *Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* colonies were inoculated in 1 mL liquid
522 Czapek DOX media with 10 mM NO₃ in Lysing Matrix A tubes (MP Biomedicals; Irvine, CA;
523 Art.No.: SKU 116910100) for 24-48 hours at 30 degrees and 180 rpm. After incubation, the
524 cultures were centrifuged at 20238 rcf in an Eppendorf 5424 centrifuge. The supernatant was
525 removed and 1 mL CENIS lysis buffer (200 mM TRIS-HCl pH 8.5, 250 mM NaCl, 25 mM
526 EDTA, 0.5% SDS) was added. A FastPrep-24™ ribolyzer (MP Biomedicals; Irvine, CA; Art.No.:
527 SKU116004500) was then used to homogenize the samples (20 seconds, 6.0 m/s) and the
528 gDNA extraction according to CENIS was conducted (89). The dried gDNA was dissolved in
529 100 µL of dH₂O and heated up to 65°C for 10 minutes. 1 µL was taken for PCR.

530 Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) was either performed with the Q5®-polymerase from New
531 England Biolabs (New England Biolabs; Art. No.: M0491L) for plasmid cloning, or with the
532 GoTaq® Green Master Mix (Promega; Madison, WI, USA; Art. No.:M7845) if used for
533 diagnostic PCRs (i.e. strain and plasmid verification). PCR was performed according to the
534 respective manual. Plasmid preparations were performed with Genejet® Plasmid Miniprep
535 Kit (Thermo Scientific™, Art. No.: K0503). All information (primer pair names and sequences,
536 amplicon names and templates) can be retrieved from Additional_file_1.pdf Table S1.

537 Plasmid construction was performed with either NEBBuilder® HiFi DNA Assembly Master
538 Mix (New England Biolabs (NEB); Art. No.: E2621S) or by yeast recombinational cloning

539 (YRC) (90). All PCR fragments were purified with the Monarch PCR & DNA Cleanup Kit (NEB;
 540 Art. No.: T1030L), measured at a NanoDrop™ spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific™;
 541 Art. No.: ND-2000C). All reactions were conducted according to the manufacturer’s manual.
 542 All resulting plasmids were verified by sequencing (“Ready2Run” by LGC Genomics GmbH;
 543 Berlin, Germany). The plasmids can be retrieved in GenBank format from the additional files
 544 (Additional_file_4.gbk to Additional_file_7.gbk). A summary of all plasmids that have been
 545 constructed during this study and their main elements is contained in Table 2.

Plasmid	Main Elements	Backbone
pAt-DNG02774	replacement cassette DNG02774 - <i>A. tumefaciens</i> transformation backbone	pCBRS
pCas9-DNG02774-sgRNA5	pCas9-hph plus sgRNA for DNG02774	pCas9-hph
pCas9-hph	pCas9-scaff plus hygromycin marker	pCas9-scaff
pCas9-scaff	Cas9 - 1/2 AMA1 - sgRNA scaffold	-

546 *Table 2 Plasmids constructed and used during this study. All plasmids can be retrieved from the additional files*
 547 *in genbank format.*

548

549 For construction of the *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* transformation plasmid pAt-DNG02774,
 550 plasmid pCBRS (91) and gDNA from *C. gorgonifer* strain NG_p51 were taken as templates for
 551 PCR with Q5 polymerase. Q5 products Q5_At_02774_1 to Q5_At_02774_5
 552 (Additional_file_1.pdf Table S1) were used for YRC. The correct assembly was verified by
 553 restriction digest of the resulting plasmid with MlsI from Thermo Scientific. The plasmid
 554 contains the features needed for agrobacterium mediated transformation and an exchange
 555 cassette which replaces the first 2300 base-pairs of gene DNG_02774 (i.e.: CgPKS4) with the
 556 hph marker.

557 For plasmid pCas9-DNG02774-sgRNA5 which was used for the Cas9 mediated mutation of
 558 DNG_02774, the two precursor plasmids, pCas9-scaff and pCas9-hph were constructed.

559 pCas9-scaff was assembled by using HiFi and PCR fragments Q5-Cas9-Scaff-1 to Q5-Cas9-
 560 Scaff-7 (Additional_file_1.pdf Table S1). Templates for the PCRs were the plasmid pFC331

561 (54), gDNA from an *Aspergillus fumigatus* wild-type isolate (in-house strain collection AIT-
 562 #1232), gDNA from *Aspergillus nidulans* WIM 126 (92), plasmid psgRNA (93), plasmid
 563 pCSN44 (94) and the plasmid pRS426 (95).

564 For the construction of pCas9-hph, plasmid pCas9-scaff was cut with Eco72I (Thermo
 565 Scientific™; Art. No.: ER0361) and used for HiFi assembly with PCR fragment Q5-Cas9-hph
 566 that contains the hph marker (Additional_file_1.pdf Table S1).

567 For construction of plasmid pCas9-DNG02774-sgRNA5, plasmid pCas9-hph was cut with
 568 Bsp1407I (Thermo Scientific™; Art. No.: ER0932), and assembled together with an sgRNA
 569 oligonucleotide with the sequence 5'-
 570 gtaccagacgaatctacacaCAAGGACTGATGAGTCCGTGAGGACGAAACGAGTAAGCTCGTCTCCT
 571 TGACGAAGTAGCCACCgttttagagctagaaatagc-3'. The sgRNA has the sequence: 5'-
 572 TCCTTGACGAAGTAGCCACC | GGG(PAM)-3' and anneals around base pair 275 downstream
 573 of the start codon of CgPKS4 (DNG_02774).

574

575 Strain construction:

576 All fungal strains used during this study are listed in Table 3.

Strain	Genotype	Parent strain	Transformed vector
<i>C. gorgonifer</i> NG_p51	wildtype strain	-	-
Cg-Cas9-02774-1	ΔDNG_02774	<i>C. gorgonifer</i> NG_p51	pCas9-DNG02774-sgRNA5
Cg-At-02774-1	DNG_02774::hph	<i>C. gorgonifer</i> NG_p51	pAt-DNG02774
Cg-HDR-02774-1	DNG_02774::hph	<i>C. gorgonifer</i> NG_p51	PCR (HDR-Fragment)

577 *Table 3 Fungal strains used during this study. All strains apart from the wildtype NG_p51 have been generated*
 578 *during this study*

579 Agrobacterium transformation:

580 Strain Cg-At-02774-1 was generated by disruption of CgPKS4 by agrobacterium mediated
 581 transformation with plasmid pAt-DNG02774. The transformation was conducted according to

582 Hanif et al. 2002 (96) and Gorfer et al. 2007 (97) with the deviation that fungal cultures were
583 pre-grown on CM-agar plates and that for co-cultivation of bacteria and fungi, not cellophane
584 or agar-blocks were used, but 200µL of a 1:1 mixture of a fungal spore solution (1×10^6
585 spores/mL in Tween-20 0.1%) and an induced *Agrobacterium* culture broth (*Agrobacterium*
586 *tumefaciens* carrying pAt-DNG02774) were plated on 10 MoserIND petri dishes each. After 4
587 days of incubation at 20°C, the plates were overlain with 15 mL of ~40°C warm selection media
588 (YES+ hygromycinB + cefotaxim) and incubated for further 3 days at 30°C before picking
589 transformants. After purification *via* single spore isolation, the proper insertion of the
590 replacement cassette was verified by Q5®-PCR with primer pair At-HDR_Diag
591 (Additional_file_1.pdf Table S1) which amplifies the region that spans from outside of the
592 homology regions and across the whole insert. The proper integration was assessed via size
593 comparison of amplicons of the recipient strain (i.e. NG_p51) and the mutant on an agarose
594 gel.

595

596 Disruption of *CgPKS4* by protoplast transformation (Cas9 and HDR)

597 For the disruption of gene DNG_02774 by Cas9 (i.e. Cg-Cas9-02774-1) or by a linear fragment
598 (HDR; i.e. Cg-HDR-02774-1), 10 µg plasmid pCas9-DNG02774-sgRNA5 respectively 72 µL of
599 an un-purified Q5®-PCR product (i.e. “HDR-fragment” which is the exact same replacement
600 cassette as within pAt-DNG02774; (Additional_file_1.pdf Table S1) was transformed via a
601 modified protoplast transformation protocol into strain NG_p51 as described below. In case of
602 the Cas9 approach, successful disruption was verified by amplification of the promoter and 5'
603 end of the gene DNG_02774 (~2 kb) with primer pair Cas9-Diag (Additional_file_1.pdf Table
604 S1) which showed a 600 base-pair deletion, starting at the sgRNA annealing site. The deletion
605 was further confirmed by sequencing with primer 5'- ATCACTCCCATAGCCGTCATCG3 -3' at
606 the LGC genomics sequencing facility (Berlin, Germany). In case of the HDR approach, the
607 whole replacement cassette was amplified from outside of the homology regions, exactly as
608 described above for the verification of the agrobacterium transformation (i.e. Cg-At-02774-1).

609

610 Modified protoplastation and transformation protocol for *C. gorgonifer*.

611 For protoplast preparation, spores were harvested with Tween® 20 0.1% from a yeast extract
612 sucrose (YES) agar plate and filtered through a glass wool tip. 6 mL of YES-broth in an
613 eprouvette were inoculated with a spore density of 4×10^6 spores per mL media and incubated
614 for 18 hours at 30°C at 180 rpm. The culture was transferred into a falcon tube and centrifuged
615 for 5 minutes at 4°C and 2218 rcf in a 5810 R Eppendorf centrifuge with swingout rotor. The
616 supernatant was discarded and 1 mL of Lysing solution was prepared: 12.5 mg Driselase from
617 Basidiomycetes (Sigma- Aldrich; Art. No.: D9515), 1 mg Chitinase, from *Streptomyces griseus*
618 (Sigma- Aldrich; Art. No.: C6137), 25 mg Lysing enzymes from *Trichoderma harzianum*
619 (Sigma- Aldrich; Art. No.: L1412) in 1 mL of “OsmoStock” solution (40 mM/L Citric acid, 1.1
620 mM/L MgSO₄; set pH to 5.9 with 3 mol/L NaOH). The Lysing solution was added to the
621 mycelium. The mixture was resuspended and transferred into 2 mL tubes and put into an “IKA
622 KS4000 I control” shaker at 30°C at 110 rpm for 5 hours. After visual check of protoplasts, the
623 mixture was centrifuged at 4°C for 10 minutes at 6000 rcf in an Eppendorf 5424R centrifuge
624 and as much intermediate layer (clean protoplasts on top, protoplasts and cell debris at
625 bottom) as possible was removed. Protoplasts count was determined in a counting chamber
626 (Neubauer improved; PC72.1 – Carl Roth, Karlsruhe).

627 For preparation of protoplast kryo-stocks, the solution was set to 4×10^8 protoplasts per mL
628 with OsmoStock solution and the same amount of 50% glycerol was added and mixed. Aliquots
629 of 90 µL were then slowly frozen in 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes within two styro-foam boxes at -
630 80°C. Each tube holds protoplasts for 3 transformations (i.e.: 6×10^6 protoplasts per
631 transformation).

632 For protoplast transformation, one protoplast kryo-stock was thawed on ice. 6×10^6
633 protoplasts (i.e. 30 µL) were taken and adjusted to 200 µL with ice-cold TN1 solution (i.e.
634 modified STC buffer solution: Sorbitol 0.8 mol/L, CaCl₂ 50 mM/L, Tris-HCl pH 8 10 mM/L)

635 (98). 10 µg plasmid DNA (i.e.: pCas9-DNG02774-sgRNA5) or 72 µL of non-purified Q5-PCR
636 product HDR-fragment (Additional_file_1.pdf Table S1) and 50 µL of ice-cold TN2 (= TN1
637 with PEG 4000 40% (w/v)) solution were added and mixed gently per pipetting. The whole
638 mixture was left on ice. After 30 minutes, 1 mL of TN2 solution was added, gently mixed and
639 left at room temperature for 5 minutes. The mixture was then added to 45 mL of ~40°C Bottom
640 Agarose (AMM (99) + 0.8 mol/L Sucrose + 10mM/L NaNO₃+ 0.8 % w/v low melt agarose (Carl
641 Roth; Art. No.: 6351.2) and equally distributed into 3 petri dishes. After 2 hours at room
642 temperature, 15 mL of 45°C Top agarose (same recipe as Bottom Agarose but 1.5% (w/v) low
643 melt agarose and 0.05 mg/mL hygromycin B (Merck Millipore; Art. No.: US1400052; potency:
644 1140 µg/mg) was added to each plate. After solidification, plates were incubated at 30°C until
645 colonies appeared on the surface (~ 7 days). Colonies were picked and two rounds of single
646 spore isolation (strike out – pick – grow until sporulation) were conducted on Aspergillus
647 complete media agar plates (CM by DR. C. F. Robert (99)) with hygromycinB before preparing
648 spore kryo-stocks.

649 Spore-kryo stock preparation:

650 The fungus was grown on a CM plate and incubated for 6 days at 30°C. A spore suspension
651 with Tween-20 0.1% (v/v) was prepared, mixed with a 50% (w/v) glycerol solution at a ratio of
652 1:1 and 5*750 µL aliquots were frozen at -80°C.

653 Fermentation and extraction for rasfonin standard preparation

654 Fermentation conditions, isolation and structural elucidation was carried out according to
655 Labuda et al. (100). The fungal spore suspension (5.0 x 10⁶ spores/mL) was obtained after 7
656 days cultivation of the fungus (*Cephalotrichum gorgonifer* NG_p51) on a potato dextrose agar
657 (PDA, VWR Chemicals, Austria). Five colony plugs were cut (each ca 1 x 1 cm) and thoroughly
658 mixed (on vortex for 2 minutes) with 30 mL of physiological solution (0.9 % NaCl) in a sterile,
659 50 mL Falcon tube. In total, 2 kg of parboiled rice was used as a production substrate. Briefly,
660 a total of 100 g of rice mixed with 100 mL deionized water was let soaked for ca one hour in

661 1000 mL capacity Erlenmeyer flasks, and then sterilized under standard autoclaving
662 conditions (20 min, 121°C, under pressure). Each flask (n=20) was inoculated with 100 µL of
663 spore suspension at the central part of the surface. The flasks were cultivated in perforated
664 plastic bags for 28 days at 30°C in the dark. At the end of the cultivation, the rice cultures were
665 checked for purity, cut into small pieces and the whole content of the plates (fungal colonies
666 with rice-substrate) was harvested into a 5 L glass flask. No heating deactivation nor drying
667 was performed. The material was then mixed with 2 L of acetonitrile (ACN, Honeywell, Seelze,
668 Germany). After vigorous stirring for 2 min in three subsequent steps (with ca 20 min in
669 between), the mixture was filtered through a steel sieve in order to separate the solid particles
670 (fungus and medium). The remaining residual water (generated by condensation of the water
671 on plates during fungal growth) was removed by the addition of 10 g of anhydrous sodium
672 sulphate. The organic phase was then filtered through a filter paper (270 mm i.d., Macherey-
673 Nagel, Düren, Germany) and concentrated under reduced pressure at 45°C (Büchi Rotavapor
674 R-114, Flawil, Switzerland). The whole extraction procedure was repeated twice and yielded
675 3.5 g of crude culture extract.

676

677 Isolation of secondary metabolites for rasfonin standard preparation

678 The crude extract was purified by reversed-phase silica gel vacuum flash chromatography
679 (Interchim, puriFlash®450, Montlucon Cedex, France), using three consecutive Interchim
680 puriFlash® 32 g silica IR-50C18-F0025 flash columns (particle size: 50µm). The columns were
681 eluted with a binary solvent gradient (solvent A: H₂O, solvent B: ACN). The starting linear
682 gradient from 10% B to 27% B during 25 min at a flow rate 15 mL/min was followed by an
683 isocratic gradient at 52% B for 10 min. Then a linear gradient from 52% to 66% B over 7min
684 was applied at the same flow rate and finally the column was washed starting with 100% B for
685 10 min followed by 100% A for 10 min at a flow rate 15-30 mL/min. UV 254 nm and UV scan
686 200-400 nm mode were used for detection and final separation of 7 main fractions (F1-F7),

687 which were consequently concentrated under reduced pressure at 45°C. The target compound
688 was found in fraction F5 (23 - 27 R_t, yield: 370 mg). It was resolved in a solvent mix (1:1:1;
689 ACN/CH₃OH/H₂O) and further purified by an Agilent 1260 Infinity preparative HPLC (USA)
690 on a reversed phase column Gemini NX C-18 (21.20 x 150 mm, 5 μm, 110 Å). Gradient starting
691 with 30 % ACN and 70 % H₂O up to 90 % ACN in 10min (total time 34 min) and a flow rate of
692 25 ml/min. Four fractions (pF1 -pF4, time slice each 0.5 min) were collected, of which pF4
693 contained the target- rasfonin. Yield of rasfonin in pF4 (t_R 17.85-18.70 min) after one stage of
694 prep HPLC was 250 mg. For purity check an Agilent 1200 system was used with the same
695 stationary phase and gradient program (Gemini 5 μm NX-C18 110 Å, 150 x 2 mm) and gradient
696 program at a flow rate 0.3 mL/min. Analytical chromatogram of purified rasfonin and its UV
697 spectrum is presented on Figure S 3 in Additional_file_1.pdf. The identity of rasfonin was
698 furthermore verified by NMR analysis (see below).

699 LC-HRMS

700 LC-HRMS measurements were carried out with a Vanquish UHPLC system coupled to a
701 QExactive HF Orbitrap mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). For chromatographic
702 separation a C18 reversed phase column (X-Bridge, 150x2.1mm id, 3.5μm particle size, Waters)
703 was used with gradient elution applying H₂O +0.1% FA (eluent A) and methanol +0.1% FA
704 (eluent B) as eluents with a constant flow rate of 0.25 ml/min. After an initial minute with
705 constant 10% eluent B, a linear increase towards 100% B was applied in 9 minutes followed by
706 3 constant minutes of 100% B. 7 minutes of re-equilibration with 10% B completed the method
707 with a total length of 20 minutes. Ionisation was carried out in fast polarity switching mode
708 and full scan mass spectra were recorded with a mass range of m/z 100-1000 and a resolution
709 of 120 000 at m/z 200 (FWHM). MS/MS measurements for [M+H]⁺ of Rasfonin were carried
710 out in a data dependant method using an inclusion list. The selected ions were fragmented with
711 stepped normalized collision energy (25, 35, 45 eV) and recorded with a resolution of 15 000
712 at m/z 200 (FWHM) at mass ranges m/z 50 to 460. For compound identification the in-house
713 purified reference standard of Rasfonin (see above) was dissolved and diluted to a

714 concentration of 1 mg/L and measured with the described method within the same sequence
715 as all biological samples.

716

717 NMR

718 All NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance II 400 (resonance frequencies 400.13 MHz
719 for ^1H and 100.63 MHz for ^{13}C) equipped with a 5 mm N_2 -cooled cryoprobe (Prodigy) with z-
720 gradients at room temperature with standard Bruker pulse programs. The sample was
721 dissolved in 0.6 mL of CDCl_3 (99.8% D). Chemical shifts are given in ppm, referenced to
722 residual solvent signals (7.26 ppm for ^1H , 77.0 ppm for ^{13}C). ^1H NMR data were collected with
723 32k complex data points and apodised with a Gaussian window function (lb = -0.3 Hz and gb
724 = 0.3 Hz) prior to Fourier transformation. ^{13}C spectrum with WALTZ16 ^1H decoupling was
725 acquired using 64k data points. Signal-to-noise enhancement was achieved by multiplication
726 of the FID with an exponential window function (lb = 1Hz). All two-dimensional experiments
727 were performed with $1\text{k} \times 256$ data points, while the number of transients (2–16 scans) and
728 the sweep widths were optimized individually. HSQC experiment was acquired using adiabatic
729 pulse for inversion of ^{13}C and GARP-sequence for broadband ^{13}C -decoupling, optimized for
730 $^1\text{J}(\text{CH}) = 145$ Hz. For the NOESY spectrum a mixing time of 0.5 s was used.

731

732 Structure determination of rasfonin (Figure 4) standard by NMR

	^1H	^{13}C
1	-	163.29
2	6.21, d, 1H, $J = 9.6$	124.93
3	7.04, dd, 1H, $J = 9.6; 6.0$	140.58
4	5.34, dd, 1H, $J = 6.0; 2.5$	61.70
5	4.13, dd, 1H, $J = 8.9; 2.5$	83.28
6	2.18, m, 1H	31.37
7	1.21, ddd, 1H, $J = 13.4; 9.0; 3.9$	39.94
	1.03, ddd, 1H, $J = 13.4; 10.0; 4.8$	

8	1.68, m, 1H	27.85
9	2.06, br.d, 1H, $J = 13.2$	46.28
	1.44, dd, 1H, $J = 13.2; 9.8$	
10	-	134.18
11	5.12, br.q, 1H, $J = 7.1$	120.04
12	1.54, br.d, 3H, $J = 7.1$	13.33
13	1.15, d, 3H, $J = 6.6$	18.85
14	0.78, d, 3H, $J = 6.5$	20.59
15	1.52, br.s, 3H	15.53
1'	-	168.08
2'	5.81, d, 1H, $J = 15.6$	115.01
3'	7.34, dd, 1H, $J = 15.6; 0.5$	150.96
4'	-	134.63
5'	5.77, br.d, 1H, $J = 9.9$	143.28
6'	2.88, m, 1H	39.22
7'	1.79 + 1.61, each m, 1H	34.74
8'	3.73, dt, 1H, $J = 10.6; 5.5$	60.60
	3.60, m, 1H	
9'	1.83, d, 3H, $J = 1.2$	12.59
10'	3.60, m, 2H	65.81

Table 4: ^1H and ^{13}C nmr data of rasfonin in CDCl_3

733

734

735 The isolated compound showed a $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ peak at $m/z = 435.2697\ 1229$ (calcd 435.2741 for
736 $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{39}\text{O}_6$) in the ESI spectrum which is in accordance with the expected molecular formula of
737 $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_6$. The ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra revealed the presence of three doubletic methyl groups
738 at $\delta_{\text{H}}/\delta_{\text{C}}$ 1.54/13.33, 1.15/18.85, 0.78/20.59 ppm and two singlet methyl groups at
739 1.52/15.53, and 1.83/12.59 ppm, respectively. In addition, 6 olefinic protons could be detected.
740 Two pairs of them are part from delocalized double bond systems due to conjugation to
741 carboxylic carbons C-1 and C-1': H-2/C-2 and H-3/C-3 showed signals at $\delta_{\text{H}}/\delta_{\text{C}}$ 6.21/124.93
742 and 7.04/140.58 ppm, whereas the system 2' and 3' resonated at $\delta_{\text{H}}/\delta_{\text{C}}$ 5.81/115.01 and
743 7.34/150.96 ppm, respectively. Furthermore, two oxygenated methines and two oxygenated
744 methylene groups were identified in the nmr spectra. Detailed analysis of all two-dimensional
745 nmr spectra proved the presence of rasfonin for the isolated compound. All assigned chemical

746 shifts (Table 4) are in agreement with those already reported for rasfonin by Fujimoto et al.
747 (101).

748

749 Rasfonin analysis of *CgPKS4* knock-out strains:

750 For rasfonin analysis of *CgPKS4*- mutants, triplicates of each knockout strain and the wildtype
751 NG_p51 were cultivated. Fungal spores were plated on YES- agar plates supplemented with
752 100 mM NO₃ and cultivated at 30°C for 7 days. The culture + agar was then cut into ~1 cm²
753 pieces, frozen in liquid nitrogen and lyophilised in a Christ Alpha 2-4 LSCbasic lyophilizer. The
754 freeze-dried material was ground in a Retsch MIXER MILL MM 400 ball mill in a liquid
755 nitrogen cooled 50 mL grinding jar with one 20 mm stainless steel grinding ball per jar at 25hz
756 for 60 seconds. 0.1g of the ground material were extracted with 1.5 mL ACN with 0.1% FA acid
757 on an IKA Vibrax VXR basic shaker at 1500rpm for 1 hour at room temperature. The slurry
758 was then centrifuged for 20 minutes at 20238 rcf and at room temperature in an Eppendorf
759 5424 centrifuge. The supernatant was then filtrated through a 0.22 µM PTFE syringe filter,
760 and the extract was reduced in a prewarmed (45°C) Eppendorf concentrator plus for 30
761 minutes at V-HV settings. The reduced extracts were refilled to 300 µL with ACN and filtered
762 again to remove precipitate that formed during concentration. The extracts were directly
763 measured in via HPLC and LC-HRMS.

764 Measurement of knockout-mutants via HPLC:

765 Samples were analyzed with an Agilent 1200 system with a reversed phase column
766 Phenomenex Gemini NX C-18 (2 x 150 mm, 5 µm, 110 Å). Injection volume of samples was 20
767 µL. The flow rate was 0.3 mL/min with a binary gradient of A from 15% (ACN+0.1% FA) to
768 95% in the time interval 2 minutes to 31 minutes (Solvent B: MQ-H₂O + 0.1% FA). Rasfonin
769 was detected with an Agilent G1315C DAD detector at 280nm. Elution time of rasfonin was at
770 around 21.1 minutes. For reference measurement and sample spiking, a 25 µg/mL rasfonin
771 standard produced by our laboratory (see above) was used.

772

773 **Declarations**

774 Ethics approval and consent to participate: Not applicable

775 Consent for publication: Not applicable

776 Availability of data and materials:

777 The datasets that were generated during this study are accessible at following
778 repositories:

779 **Genome and Gene annotation** of *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51: European Nucleotide
780 Archive (ENA) at EMBL-EBI. Project number PRJEB15373 which can be accessed at
781 <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/data/view/ONZQ01000001-ONZQ01000048> (40)

782 **Transcriptome data** of *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51 at 24h and 48h: The data discussed in
783 this publication have been deposited in NCBI's Gene Expression Omnibus (46) and are
784 accessible through GEO Series accession number GSE217303
785 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE217303>).

786

787 The datasets supporting the conclusions of this article are included within the article
788 and its additional files.

789 Additional_file_1.pdf: Information about oligonucleotides, strain verification, LC-
790 HRMS analysis of KO strains and UV spectrum of rasfonin

791 Additional_file_2.xlsx: Transcriptome dataset and analysis of *C. gorgonifer* NG_p51
792 at 24h and 48h in AMM liquid media

793 Additional_file_3.gbk: Genbank file with the rasfonin BGC and surrounding genetic
794 locus, information on *CgPKS3* disruptions of KO strains.

795 Additional_file_4_pAt_DNGO2774.gbk: Plasmid map pAt_DNGO2774 in genbank
796 format

797 Additional_file_5_pCas9-DNGO2774-sgRNA5.gbk: Plasmid map pCas9-DNGO2774-
798 sgRNA5 in genbank format

799 Additional_file_6_pCas9-hph.gbk: Plasmid map pCas9-hph in genbank format

800 Additional_file_7_pCas9-scaff.gbk: Plasmid map pCas9-scaff in genbank format

801

802

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808 Authors' contributions

809 AS (study design, protocol establishment, micro- and molecular biology, figures, writing), LSR
810 (Biosynthesis pathway of rasfonin, linking of rasfonin to BGC, study design, writing, figures),
811 HB (Transcriptome analysis, BGC prediction), LS (chemical analysis, preliminary data
812 acquisition), RL (Species description, morphology, rasfonin standard preparation and
813 verification, figures), UG (Genome assembly, Gene annotation), MG (Agrobacterium Trafo,
814 Isolation, strain information and identification), MB (NMR analysis), MD (LC-HRMS
815 chemical analysis), EG (HPLC rasfonin method establishment and detection), AG (HPLC-
816 chemical analysis), MS (screening, chemical analysis), JS (Funding acquisition, study design,
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823

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2.3 Publication III

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Review

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Andreas Schüller, Lena Studt-Reinhold and Joseph Strauss

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Review

How to Completely Squeeze a Fungus—Advanced Genome Mining Tools for Novel Bioactive Substances

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Abstract: Fungal species have the capability of producing an overwhelming diversity of bioactive substances that can have beneficial but also detrimental effects on human health. These so-called secondary metabolites naturally serve as antimicrobial “weapon systems”, signaling molecules or developmental effectors for fungi and hence are produced only under very specific environmental conditions or stages in their life cycle. However, as these complex conditions are difficult or even impossible to mimic in laboratory settings, only a small fraction of the true chemical diversity of fungi is known so far. This also implies that a large space for potentially new pharmaceuticals remains unexplored. We here present an overview on current developments in advanced methods that can be used to explore this chemical space. We focus on genetic and genomic methods, how to detect genes that harbor the blueprints for the production of these compounds (i.e., biosynthetic gene clusters, BGCs), and ways to activate these silent chromosomal regions. We provide an in-depth view of the chromatin-level regulation of BGCs and of the potential to use the CRISPR/Cas technology as an activation tool.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Fungal Secondary Metabolites as Biopharmaceuticals of Tomorrow

Bacteria, plants, and filamentous fungi are capable of producing many chemically diverse bioactive substances, referred to as natural products or secondary metabolites (SMs) [1]. Probably the most prominent of these fungal bioactive compounds is penicillin from *Penicillium rubens*, discovered by Alexander Fleming in 1929 [2,3] which initiated the “antibiotic revolution” that led to a major paradigm shift in the treatment of patients [4]. Many fungi and their SMs made it into pharmaceutical application, such as cyclosporin from *Tolypocladium inflatum* which is used as an immunosuppressant [5,6], or lovastatin as a treatment for coronary heart diseases produced by *Aspergillus terreus* [7]. Other fields of application for microbial-derived natural products are the food industry (e.g., soy sauce, sake, and miso by *Aspergillus oryzae* or citric acid by *Aspergillus niger* [8]), the agricultural sector (biocontrol agents [9–11], growth hormones [12]) and many others [13–16]. The ever-rising demand due to the emergence of multi-resistant pathogens and resistant cancer types underscores the importance of mining new bioactive substances from fungal sources [17].

SMs are per definition not essential for growth but may provide selective advantages for the producing organism upon specific environmental challenges: e.g., pH stress (acids and alkaline substances [18]), temperature stress (regulators of membrane fluidity [19]), oxidative stress (antioxidants [20]), UV protection (pigments [21]), microbial warfare (antimicrobials [22]), communication (e.g., quorum sensing via homoserine lactones [23]), pathogenicity and host-infection (effectors or virulence factors [24,25]), support of ion uptake (sideophore production for iron acquisition [26]). As versatile as these functions

are, as diverse are the chemical properties of such natural products. Not surprisingly, most of them are only produced under defined environmental or developmental conditions implying a complex regulation at the molecular level [27].

The blueprints for such bioactive substances are stored in biosynthetic genes that are, in most cases, physically linked in fungal genomes and together with genes for regulators and transporters sometimes constitute very large BGCs [28,29]. These BGCs are silenced by default through heterochromatic structures at the chromosomal level, but once activated by the specific signal, they work similar to an orchestrated factory to produce the cluster-specific compound. Bioinformatic tools have been developed that predict fungal BGCs based on whole-genome sequence data and these predictions show that so far sequenced fungi harbor between ~15 and 50 BGCs, but up to more than 80 BGCs have also been predicted in some genomes [28,30]. However, as outlined above, most of them are transcriptionally silent under standard laboratory conditions and hence the majority of associated natural products are not known [27].

1.2. Genomic Organization and Evolution of BGCs

Depending on the so-called backbone or key enzyme(s) involved in the biosynthesis, SMs are categorized according to the chemical families. They belong to e.g., polyketides, non-ribosomal peptides, terpenes and alkaloids or prenylated tryptophan derivatives. Accordingly, they are synthesized by polyketide synthases (PKSs; further divided into highly reducing (HR-PKS) and non-reducing (NR-PKS)), non-ribosomal peptide synthetases (NRPSs), terpene cyclases (TCs) and dimethylallyltryptophan synthases (DMATSs) or hybrids of them [28,29].

Next to the backbone enzyme-encoding gene(s) BGCs often harbor genes involved in self-resistance against a potentially toxic SM produced by the BGC, transport of precursors, intermediates, or the resulting compound [31,32], transcriptional activation of the biosynthetic genes, and often so-called tailoring or decorating enzymes that modify the structure of the chemical scaffold compound released by the backbone enzyme (e.g., P450 monooxygenases, methyltransferases, hydroxylases, epimerases, etc. [29]).

A few exceptions exist that deviate from this standard configuration. For example, in *Fusarium graminearum*, polyketide synthase PKS8 was shown to be a stand-alone gene that is responsible for the synthesis of gibepyrone A [33], while the kojic acid BGC from *Aspergillus oryzae* does not have a backbone enzyme-encoding gene at all [34]. In other cases, the formation of superclusters was observed which encode for several independently synthesized biosynthetic products [35]. The opposite was also observed, where several BGCs or genes from distinct genomic locations communicate with each other to synthesize one product [36].

Fungi exhibit a very diversified and specialized chemical repertoire. The diversification of BGCs increases with the phylogenetic distance [37,38] but in some cases, it can even be observed within the same or closely related species, which was shown for *Aspergillus fumigatus* [39,40], *Aspergillus niger* [41] as well as between *A. oryzae* and its close relative *Aspergillus flavus* [42]. Constant interactions with other microorganisms and environmental conditions promote the intra and interspecies diversification process by exerting positive or negative selective pressure on BGCs in that specific ecosystem. If a BGC is non-essential or not beneficial in a certain microenvironment it is likely to acquire deleterious mutations or even gene loss over time [43]. A comparison of isolates from the same species but separated microenvironments revealed the emergence of different ecotypes as observed during population genetics studies on *Streptomyces* [44] and *Umbilicaria pustulata* [45].

BGCs are differently affected by evolution compared to the rest of the genome. They are located outside of so-called syntenic blocks, i.e., their position within the genome, and the BGC itself is less conserved than the rest of the genome [46,47]. In support of this, many BGCs were found to be enriched in sub-telomeric regions which are known to be hotspots for recombination [48]. This was shown in *Sclerotinia sclerotium* [49], *Magnaporthe oryzae* [50,51], *A. fumigatus* [52], and *Zyoseptoria tritici* [53].

From an evolutionary perspective, the ability to quickly adapt to new environmental challenges is fundamental for the survival of an organism. In the case of fungi and other microbes, this means that they can adapt and change their metabolomic arsenal fast enough to properly compete against other microbes or environmental changes. This implies that the relevant genomic regions and hence the genes situated in these regions (i.e., BGCs) experience regular mutations (single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) such as missense, nonsense, frameshift, or gain/loss of function) and genomic rearrangements as for instance gene duplications, gene or BGC loss, BGC rearrangements, pseudogenization events and also the acquisition of genetic material via horizontal gene transfer [43]. Organisms that acquire beneficial mutations will surpass others that experience disadvantageous ones whereby the environmental context decides if a certain mutation is beneficial or not. Microbial competition is not only about having the “best weaponry” but also about defense, resource efficiency, and denying beneficial effects to competitors. This not only implies gain of function or the *de novo* assembly of a BGC but also reductive genomic evolution which led to the “Black Queen Hypothesis” (BQH) [54]. The BQH considers that selective pressure can lead to the loss of a gene or function if that gene is dispensable (which makes it more energy efficient not to have it), or if the gene product would give a competitor more benefits than the producing organism itself.

For the artificial activation of silent BGCs in a laboratory context, this means that some of the BGCs will carry deleterious mutations or even miss whole genes that would be necessary for the biosynthesis of the BGC product. In these cases, solely transcriptional activation will not suffice. Close examination of the BGC of interest can already unveil if genes carry a premature stop codon or if homologous BGCs indicate missing genes or frameshift mutations. A possible workaround in these scenarios is the exchange of single genes by their homologs or the genetic repair of a nonsense mutation as performed by Burkhardt et al. with the STC5 gene in *Fusarium fujikuroi* [55].

Multiple genomic, inter-species, and environmental factors contribute to this elevated diversification and evolution of BGCs. The occurrence of mutations and genomic rearrangements depend on many exogenous (e.g., radiation, heat, chemicals, environmental conditions, . . .) and endogenous factors (e.g., errors in DNA damage repair, or active transposable elements). As stated above, BGCs and pathogenicity-related genes are often in polymorphic regions that are prone to such events (e.g., sub-telomeric regions). Transposable elements (TEs) play an important role during evolution and also in the *de novo* assembly of BGCs. In *Verticillium dahliae* it was found that BGC and pathogenicity-related genes are often located close to transposable elements [56]. In a comparative study within *Aspergillus fumigatus* isolates, horizontally transferred BGCs, BGC idiomorphs (i.e., different BGCs in the same genomic location), and BGCs that are present in different genomic locations within the same or closely related species) are often flanked by TEs [39]. Similar findings were also found between *A. oryzae* and *A. flavus* where two strain isolates had different BGCs in the same genomic locus [42] or in the case of several *Botrytis* species where the BOT BGC, involved in botrydial biosynthesis, was present at four different genomic locations across seven examined species [57,58]. When analyzing BGC genes and TE co-occurrence in *Sclerotinia*, they found that the overall co-occurrence of BGC genes and TEs is not significantly enhanced. Upon closer examination, however, it became evident that a subset of BGC genes, which is enriched in key-enzyme encoding genes, is co-occurrent with TEs and that genes in this subset often derive from recent gene duplication events [49]. BGC genes near TEs, therefore, were found less conserved than BGC genes more distal to the TE. All these findings point towards a TE-dependent heterogeneous evolution of BGCs (i.e., genes near TEs have an increased “evolutionary speed”). In the case of BGC prediction, TEs are, to our knowledge, not yet a considered factor, although it seems that these motives could very likely be good indicators for the presence of a BGC. Furthermore, TEs are probably also important factors for the *de novo* assembly of BGCs.

De novo assembly is hypothesized to be a two-step process. The first step starts with the framework establishment of the new metabolic pathway [59]. Often, this is ac-

accomplished by horizontal gene transfer, as shown for the sterigmatocystin cluster from *A. nidulans* to *Podospora* [60], or the transfer of the bikaverin BGC from *Fusarium* to *Botrytis* [61] and many others [59,62–66]). Other mechanisms involve the recruitment of host genes or gene duplication events (e.g., fatty acid synthase as ancestor of PKS enzymes [67]). In a second step, the BGC is clustered by genomic rearrangements. Sometimes, however, it also happens that two separate BGCs, which are not physically linked, are responsible for the biosynthesis of one compound (i.e., cluster crosstalk) [36] or that superclusters (e.g., fumagillin/pseurotin cluster from *Aspergillus fumigatus* [35]) are formed. Cluster crosstalk could be observed with the trichothecene supercluster of *F. graminearum* which consists of a 12 gene BGC and a separated 2 gene BGC plus one single gene at three different genomic loci [68].

All in all, the genomic comparative studies from *A. fumigatus* [39], *A. flavus* and *A. oryzae* [42], *S. sclerotiorum* [49], *V. dahlia* [56], and also the reviews from Lind et al. [39] and Rokas et al. [43] give very good insights into the evolution of BGCs and especially the role of TEs as one of their driving forces.

The fact that this evolutionarily driven arms-race is not only apparent between closely related species but also between different ecotypes of the same species illustrates that BGCs are evolving at a fast pace. This highlights that the research pool of fungal genera and species must be expanded to increase the chance of finding novel natural products in the future. However, most of the current research is focused on mining BGCs in only a few but very well-described genera, the so-called model organisms.

In this review, we highlight the concepts and technical possibilities on how to decrypt the secondary metabolome of a given (filamentous) fungus by efficiently deploying targeted and untargeted BGC-activation methods in synergy with genome mining. Special attention will be paid to more recent strategies involving the chromatin regulation of BGCs and the new possibilities currently emerging by the combination of CRISPR/Cas technology and transcriptional activators, global regulators, or chromatin-modifying enzymes.

2. Deciphering the Genomic Potential of Fungal Genomes for Secondary Metabolites

In silico-prediction of BGCs within the genome of the target fungus gives important information about the (theoretical) chemical potential of a fungus. This is not only important for deciding if a species is a promising candidate for novel bioactive compounds but is also a prerequisite for linking those compounds to a specific cluster and also for targeted BGC activation. Bioinformatic analyses of high-quality genome sequences and transcriptome datasets are becoming cornerstones to explore the theoretical chemical diversity of SMs in a given species. Those resources are routinely used today for gene annotation [69], BGC prediction [70], cluster phylogeny [28,71,72], prediction of the metabolite structure and bioactivity [73], drug target predictions [74,75] and also dereplication [76]. As outlined in Section 1.2, there are many different data types and sources that can be utilized for the prediction of BGCs. In the following paragraph, we will describe the basic principle and the developmental cycle of BGC prediction tools.

Figure 1 illustrates the workflow of genome mining-assisted BGC prediction and revelation. It comprises the crucial steps that are necessary for the prediction and verification of a BGC and its corresponding metabolite. It also shows the pitfalls which can easily remain unnoticed but significantly impact the reliability of the prediction.

Figure 1. Workflow for genome mining assisted BGC prediction and verification. The order and interplay of prediction tools, databases, and scientist is depicted. In orange letters, we point out pitfalls that could lead to incorrect predictions and can easily be overlooked. The correct order is depicted by the arrows and follows the numbered bold headlines. The light-yellow arrow represents a re-prediction of an outdated BGC annotation. Explanations regarding point 5. “Experimental verification”: The top part is the genomic locus with the putative BGC surrounded by a dotted outline; genes are numbered from 1–6, BB stands for “backbone- gene” (gene No. 3; orange) and TF stands for “pathway-specific transcription factor” (gene No. 4, green). Yellow lightning bolt symbols represent genetic manipulation (i.e., gene deletion in case of BB or overexpression in case of TF). The colors represent the three different samples/transformants: The control (“C”) represents the wildtype (wt) or recipient strain and is illustrated by a grey flask, expression bars, and HPLC spectra

(i.e., wt-like synthesis of the investigated secondary metabolite. In this case it is produced but in case of a silent BGC, the peak on the far right would be absent). Transformant 1 (“T1”) has the backbone gene deleted and is represented by an orange flask, gene expression bars and HPLC peaks (orange flat line; i.e., no synthesis of the secondary metabolite); Transformant 2 (“T2”) has the TF of the BGC overexpressed. It is depicted by a green flask, green gene expression bars and a green HPLC peak (i.e., overproduction of the secondary metabolite). Diagrams have either the expression level (“Expr.”) or the absorption value (“Abs.”) as the y-axis and time (“min”) as the x-axis. The setup of 5. Experimental verification represents one possibility of linking a putative BGC to its metabolite. After deposition into a database (6.), the gathered information about the BGC can be utilized for the prediction of BGCs in other genomes (2.).

BGC Prediction Methods

The majority of BGC prediction tools can be classified into either high-confidence/low-novelty (rule-based) or low-confidence/high-novelty (rule-independent) [70,77].

High-confidence/low novelty methods reliably detect BGCs that are closely related to already verified cluster types (i.e., PKS; NRPS, etc.) by scanning the genome for their specific signatures (genes, gene types, genomic arrangement, etc.). These signatures are retrieved from experimentally verified data that links the compound to the respective BGC, which are then implemented into the algorithm. The prediction tool antiSMASH [78] is a very well-established and regularly updated platform that also integrates many other published algorithms. It can be used for fungal, plant, and bacterial genomes and contains methods for finding canonical and also novel BGCs. During the prediction of known BGC types, the procedure often starts with an initial screen for backbone enzyme-encoding genes which serve as anchor-point for further analysis of the region. In a second step, the cluster borders are determined by scanning the area around this anchor point for the presence of other BGC-related genes [78,79]. This means, however, that high-confidence/low-novelty (rule-based) methods can only detect BGCs that share similarities with already discovered and described cluster types

In contrast to this, low-confidence/high-novelty (rule-independent methods) pursue the aim of detecting BGCs of a novel yet unknown type that does not follow currently known patterns (gene types, arrangement, etc.). There are multiple strategies for finding new BGC types that use various experimental and -omics data for this purpose.

MIPS-CG, for example, utilizes an algorithm that does not rely on the use of backbone genes as BGC-anchor points as some BGCs were shown to lack these (e.g., kojic acid BGC). Instead, to identify these non-canonical BGCs, MIPS-CG performs pairwise genome comparisons between different fungal species and removes syntenic blocks, because BGCs are often not located in such regions. Following the assumption that BGCs follow a basic common structure (similar gene functions) MIPS-CG scans for clustered genes that follow this pattern [47].

The EvoMining algorithm uses a phylogenomic approach to detect BGCs. It is based on three evolutionary concepts. First, those new enzymatic functions evolve by retaining the reaction mechanism of the enzyme but changing substrate specificity. Second, the evolution of metabolic pathways can lead to the deployment of existing enzyme families that perform new functions (e.g., fatty acid synthases as the ancestor of PKSs) and third, that BGCs have their origin in central metabolism [71,80].

AntiSMASH version 4 introduced the Clusterfinder algorithm which converts a genome into a string of Pfam domains (i.e., protein family domains). Subsequently, BGCs are annotated where stretches with a significant amount of BGC-related Pfam domains occur [81,82].

The ARTS algorithm (Antibiotic Resistant Target Seeker), although currently supporting only bacterial genomes, is a tool for specifically finding BGCs that encode for an antibiotic. When bacteria produce an antibiotic substance, they can either detoxify and shuttle the compound out of the cell or express a resistant homolog of the gene that is targeted by the antibiotic. The resistance pathway is exploited by ARTS. The algorithm

compares the genome to a reference genome and looks for duplicate housekeeping genes in the genome. These resistant homologs often are inside the same BGC. Furthermore, the cluster is often acquired by horizontal gene transfer (HGT). With the combination of BGC prediction via antiSMASH, gene duplicate screening and the comparison of the phylogeny of core gene trees of the organism and the cluster genes, ARTS can predict clusters that are highly likely to be responsible for the biosynthesis of an antibiotic [83,84]. The FRIGG pipeline pursues a similar approach but can be used for fungal genomes [85].

Middas-M follows the hypothesis that BGCs can be found where an array of genes is coregulated. They combine transcriptomic data of several culture conditions with genomic data to predict BGCs [86]. This method will, however, only catch BGCs that actually can be activated under laboratory conditions.

Algorithms use various curated but also non-curated data sources for their calculation of BGC genes. These data repositories can basically hold any kind of information about BGCs (e.g., gene information, genomic arrangement, related species, protein information, educts and products, transcriptional information, phylogenetics, environmental information, etc.). Curated data sources contain fewer data entries, but the reliability and quality of these entries are often pristine, non-redundant, and experimentally backed which leads to more reliable predictions. Non-curated data sources basically hold all the information that is available (e.g., Genbank). This means that the algorithm has to process and filter a lot of data of various quality and actuality (e.g., low-quality sequencing data and annotation, experimentally not verified predictions, etc.). Depending on the popularity of the examined genus this also can lead to many redundancies that might contain flawed information. All in all, non-curated sources contain more, but less reliable data which can reduce the quality and reliability of the prediction.

It should be mentioned that, as the experimental information about a novel BGC type increases, it will subsequently pass over from the rule-independent (high novelty/low confidence) to the rule-based (low novelty/ high confidence) prediction methods. This developmental process of prediction tools will undoubtedly lead to the discovery of yet unknown BGCs in already known and well-described species; however, it is strongly dependent on high-quality and accurate experimental data, provided by laboratories. The elucidation of novel BGC types and their genomic signatures, plus their proper deposit in data repositories (e.g., MiBiG, NP-atlas 2.0, GNPS, etc.) will significantly improve BGC predictions in the future. For more detailed information about genome mining and predictive tools, please consult the review of Blin and coworkers from 2019 [70].

Table 1 lists many of the actual databases and BGC prediction tools. They are ordered according to their last update (Status: March 2022), and also summarizes their characteristics.

Table 1. List of platforms and databases used for BGC prediction. Ordered by the most recent update. Status March 2022.

Tools and Database Used for BGC Predictions					
Tool/ Database	Type	Purposes	Last Update	Link (Accessed on 15 March 2022)	Ref.
EMBL-EBI/ENA	DB	uncurated Database (large repository: DNA, RNA, genome annotations)	regular updates	ebi.ac.uk	[87,88]
GenBank	DB	uncurated Database (large repository: DNA, RNA, genome annotations)	every 2 month	ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank	[89]
GNPS	DB	“Global Natural Products Social Molecular Networking” community-curated mass spectrometry database	2022	gnps.ucsd.edu	[90]
fungiSMASH	PT	Gold standard for BGC prediction. Allrounder with an extensive variety of integrated tools and algorithms, web-application or stand-alone; Rule-based and rule-independent algorithms. Versions for fungi, bacteria and plants available. Fungal version has additional BGC border detection based on TF-binding sites	2021	https://fungismash.secondarymetabolites.org/#!/start	[78]
NP-atlas 2.0	DB	curated community database of microbially-derived SMS compounds from marine macro algae and diatoms are excluded	2021	npatlas.org/	[91]
TIGRFAMs	DB	curated database of protein families (mainly prokaryotic)	2021	ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/annotation_prok/tigrfams/	[92]
PFAM v35	DB	partly curated database protein domains and families	2021	pfam.xfam.org/	[93]
FunOrder	PT	detection of essential genes within a BGC by a co-evolutionary approach	2021	github.com/gvignolle/FunOrder	[72]
ARTS 2.0	PT	Antibiotics cluster prediction by detection of resistance genes; web application	2020	arts.ziemertlab.com	[83]
HMMER	PT	DNA based Homology search via pHMM; as source code or as web application	2020	hmmer.org/	[94]
CO-OCCUR	PT	genome-wide co-occurrence of BGC-related gene pairs; source code available	2020	github.com/egluckthaler/co-occur	[37]
TOUCAN	PT	BGC prediction via phylogeny, function, composition at amino acid level (k-mers, Pfam protein domains, and GO terms); source code (python/perl) available	2020	github.com/bioinfoUQAM/TOUCAN	[95]
antiSMASH Database v3	DB	high-quality genomes and BGCs of bacteria, archaea, and fungi	2020	antismash-db.secondarymetabolites.org/	[96]
NORINE	DB	manually curated DB for NRPS	2020	bioinfo.lifl.fr/norine/	[97]

Table 1. Cont.

Tools and Database Used for BGC Predictions					
Tool/ Database	Type	Purposes	Last Update	Link (Accessed on 15 March 2022)	Ref.
FRIGG	PT	Antibiotics BGC prediction based on presence of resistance gene; Pipeline that combines different tools; Python and R-based script available	2019	zenodo.org/record/2560245#files/YjIMHepBw5s	[85]
BIG-SCAPE + CORASON	Output refinement	takes output of antismash and generates phylogenic BGC family networks; software application	2019	git.wageningenur.nl/medema-group/BiG-SCAPE	[98]
MiBIg 2	DB	curated database (community effort and institute curation) of known BGCs and their products	2019	mibig.secondarymetabolites.org/	[99]
IMG-ABC v5.0	DB	predicted BGCs with environmental metadata (prediction via antiSMASH v5)	2019	img.jgi.doe.gov/abc-public	[100]
Deep-BGC	PT	Deep learning strategy to determine BGC product classes and chemical activity	2019	github.com/Merck/deepbgc	[101]
RiPPMiner	PT	RiPPs; web-application	2017	nii.ac.in/rippminer.html	[102]
SBSPKSv2	PT	PKS/NRPS (structure/ substrate/ product)	2017	nii.ac.in/sbspks2.html	[103,104]
SEMPI 2	PT	genome-based PKS I modular product prediction; web-application	2017	pharmaceutical-bioinformatics.de/SeMPI/	[105]
CASSIS and SMIPS	PT	Promoter base- BGC prediction focused around SM-key enzymes, online or as application	2016	sbi.hki-jena.de/cassis	[106]
FunGene-ClusterS	PT	Transcriptome and genome-assisted BGC prediction; standalone and web application	2016	fungiminions.shinyapps.io/FunGeneClusterS	[107,108]
2metDB/SecmetDB	PT	PKS/NRPS-prediction tool; software application	2015	sourceforge.net/projects/secmetdb/	[109]
GNP	PT	Structure prediction and LC-MS data peak identification; web-application	2015	magarveylab.ca/gnp/	[110]
Smiles2Mono-mers (s2m)	PT	predict monomers from polymeric structure; webserver and standalone	2015	bioinfo.lifl.fr/norine/smiles2monomers.jsp	[111]
ClusterFinder	PT	BGC detection via Pfam domain occurrence in genome and metagenomic data; software application and integrated into antiSMASH and IMG-ABC	2014	github.com/petercim/ClusterFinder	[82]
MIPS-CG	PT	Clusters of BGC-related Pfam-domains outside of syntenic blocks; web-application	2014	fung-metb.net/ (currently offline)	[47]

Table 1. Cont.

Tools and Database Used for BGC Predictions					
Tool/ Database	Type	Purposes	Last Update	Link (Accessed on 15 March 2022)	Ref.
MIDDAS-M	PT	Motif-Independent transcriptome and genome-assisted BGC prediction	2013	133.242.13.217/MIDDAS-M (currently offline)	[86]
ClusterMine-360	DB	crowd-source, semi and auto-curated database of microbial NRPS and PKS	2013	clustermine360.ca/ (currently offline)	[112]
NRPS-predictor2	PT	predict bacterial and fungal NRPS adenylation domain substrate specificity; web-application	2011	nrps.informatik.uni-tuebingen.de/ (currently offline)	[113]
SMURF	PT	Rule-based-backbone gene search via HMMs in genome data; web-application	2010	jcvi.org/smurf/	[79]
CLUSEAN	PT	PKS/NRPS-prediction tool; software application	2009	bitbucket.org/tilmweber/clusean	[114]

Abbreviations: Database (DB), Prediction Tool (PT).

3. Activation of Microbial BGCs via Environmental Triggers

In the past decades, many strategies have been developed to shed light on this “dark matter” in fungal genomes and thereby unlock the chemical wealth residing within the fungal kingdom. In the pre-genomics era approaches predominantly sought to induce SM biosynthesis by mimicking environmental triggers. Genome sequencing and bioinformatic analyses for BGC predictions were developed later on and did not only reveal that filamentous fungi possess far more BGCs than anticipated, but also opened opportunities for a more targeted activation of single BGCs.

We are now at a point where the combination of technological possibilities, abundance of available methods, and the already substantial amount of collected data makes it possible to expand the research to novel yet not well described fungal species. There is no “one for all”-approach that is superior to other strategies, but available methods should rather be used in a complementary and context-dependent manner.

3.1. Mimicking Natural Habitats and Stress Conditions

Fungal SMs serve different purposes during the life cycle of a fungal colony and accordingly, their production profiles somehow mirror these environmental or developmental conditions. Therefore, one of the approaches to trigger the production of new SMs is to impose challenging, sometimes stressful growth conditions on the fungal cells. Indeed, testing different cultivation conditions and imposing environmental stress has proven to be a very effective way of triggering the production of otherwise absent secondary metabolites. This approach was termed “One Strain-Many Compounds” (OSMAC) [115,116] and is very useful for assessing which BGCs can be induced within a laboratory environment and which need more laborious methods such as genetic manipulation for their activation. Especially in the case of less-studied fungi that are in the process of being established for laboratory work, different cultivation conditions also give insights into the fungal physiology and suitable media and parameters for their cultivation.

In some instances, it was shown that the fungus reacted as expected to the applied conditions. For example, UV light exposure can trigger the production of UV protectants [117], while oxidative stress can lead to the production of antioxidants [118]. It was also shown that *A. terreus* produces the pathogenesis-related SM terrain when fungal culture conditions mimic the environment of the plant or rhizosphere, which is associated with nitrogen starvation, iron shortage, and the presence of methionine [119].

Environmental stimuli are generally processed via global regulators. The purpose of global regulators is to coordinate the expression of an array of genes that ensure a resource-efficient response that is suited to the environmental circumstances [120,121]. Therefore, instead of mimicking such stimuli via media and cultivation conditions, the genetic engineering of global regulators (i.e., deletion, overexpression, knockdown, mutation) is also a successful way of triggering the activation of BGCs. This, however, can also lead to phenotypical abnormalities such as aberrant sexual and asexual cycle and growth defects [122,123] which could be linked to the intertwined character of many global regulatory networks [29].

The most thoroughly researched environmental signals that are connected to the production of fungal metabolites are nutrient availability and light regulation.

The type and concentration of the available nitrogen source also greatly impacts secondary metabolism, as shown for some well-established model organisms from the genus *Fusarium* [124–127] and *Aspergillus* [128]. The major GATA transcription factor AreA, AreB, and Nmr are global regulators of nitrogen-dependent genes and pathways in filamentous fungi. In *F. fujikuroi*, deletion of *AREA* and *AREB* led to differential regulation of many known but also yet cryptic BGCs [127]. In *F. graminearum*, AreA is required for the production of deoxynivalenol (DON), zearalenone, and fusarielin H [129]. Similar results were obtained in *Acremonium chrysogenum* where the deletion of *areA* led to the reduction of cephalosporin [130] and in *Fusarium oxysporum* where AreA is necessary for the synthesis of beauvericin and ferricrocin [131].

Light is also an important natural regulator of growth, development/conidiation and biosynthesis of natural products in fungi [132–136]. Genetic manipulation of components of the fungal-specific light regulator velvet complex showed its involvement in many developmental and also biosynthetic processes [137–141]. It consists of velvet-like proteins like, VelA, VelB and most importantly, the methyltransferase LaeA. Deletion of *laeA* in *A. nidulans*, resulted in the abolishment of the production of sterigmatocystin, penicillin, and lovastatin while overexpression of *laeA* led to increased lovastatin and penicillin production [142]. Similarly, LaeA was also found to be a positive regulator of secondary metabolism in *Valsa mali* [143], *Aspergillus ochraceus* [136], *Penicillium expansum* [144], *Chaetomium globosum* [145], *Fusarium verticillioides* [146] and *F. fujikuroi* [147]. Therefore, LaeA seems to have a conserved role of a positive regulator of BGCs in many filamentous fungi which makes it a promising target for overexpression studies.

Other variables influencing SM levels are the pH value of the growth medium [148–153], an effect mainly mediated by the transcription factor (TF) PacC [154–156], temperature stress [118,157,158], osmotic stress, and salinity [159–162], or metals and trace elements [163–166]. The concentration and quality of the available carbon source can also be a critical parameter [135,167,168] for SM production which is mediated by the carbon catabolite repressor CreA [122]. For oxidative stress [118,123,169–171] Skn7 [172] and ApyapA/AoyapA (Aflatoxin production) are known response regulators [173,174]. There are general repressors such as McrA, but the conditions for its activity remain unknown [175] or Nsd1(CsM1/Ltf1) which is involved in sexual development and conidiation in *A. nidulans* and other fungi [176].

Apart from media composition, the type of cultivation condition also can play a pivotal role in the physiology of the fungus and thus potentially influence the production of secondary metabolites. Differences in the metabolomic profiles could be observed when comparing submerge and solid cultivation [177,178], as well as between agitated or static fermentation [179]. The addition of a polymeric growth support to a submersed culture also had profound influences on growth and metabolite biosynthesis [180].

Table 2 provides an overview on methods and examples where they have been used to successfully induce BGCs by mimicking natural triggers or by genetic manipulation of global regulators.

Table 2. Successful application of BGC induction by mimicking environmental conditions or by genetic manipulation of global regulators.

BGC Activation by Natural Triggers and Manipulation of Their Global Regulators			
Section 1: <i>Aspergillus</i> and <i>Penicillium</i>			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
<i>ApyapAΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus parasiticus</i>	<i>ApyapAΔ</i> : increased aflatoxin production	[173]
<i>csnEΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	<i>csnEΔ</i> : production of orsellinic acid-related metabolites: orcinol, diorcinol, cordyol C, violaceol I and violaceol II; activation of DHMBA cluster	[181,182]
<i>mcRAΔ</i> (TF)	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> <i>Aspergillus terreus</i> <i>Penicillium canescens</i>	<i>mcRAΔ</i> : Upregulation of secondary metabolites in all three organisms <i>A. nidulans</i> dereplication strain: two new metabolites from the cichorine pathway, production of felinone A new compounds of other organisms not identified	[175]
<i>sumOΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	<i>sumOΔ</i> : production of Asperthecin, decrease of austinol/dehydroaustinol and sterigmatocystin	[183]
Additives (supernatant extract)	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> <i>Streptomyces rapamycinicus</i>	a novel a guanidine containing macrolide named polaramycin B, produced by <i>S. rapamycinicus</i> , is responsible for the derepression of the ors- cluster and its derivatives in <i>A. nidulans</i>	[184]
Additives	<i>Penicillium citrinum</i>	Cultivation in presence of rare earth metals (i.e., scandium chloride) and isolation of three new peptide derivatives	[185]
C-source Δ /OE of <i>creA</i>	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	<i>creAΔ</i> (Carbon catabolite repressor) Growth defects, impaired conidia production, increased amount of sclerotia, near abolishment of aflatoxin production, impaired virulence OE of <i>creA</i> : similar to wild type	[122]
C-source	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	Carbon source dependent BGC expression	[186]
C-source <i>laeAΔ</i>	<i>Penicillium expansum</i>	sucrose decreases both patulin and <i>laeA</i> levels and increases <i>creA</i> expression LaeA regulates patulin BGC, <i>laeAΔ</i> results in less virulence	[144]
Cultivation (chemostat) N starvation	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	Production of antiproliferative compounds sanghaspirodins A and B Convergence of two BGCs pathways (anthraquinone and orsellinic acid-derived)	[128]
Light Temperature <i>veAΔ</i> <i>laeAΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Connection between temperature and light regulation of 11 BGCs Involvement of VeA at 37 °C and LaeA at 30 °C and 37 °C in BGC regulation	[157]
Light <i>velBΔ</i> <i>veAΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	velvet complex VelB/VeA/LaeA regulates developmental regulation and secondary metabolism in a light-dependent manner. <i>velBΔ</i> or <i>veAΔ</i> : defects in sexual fruiting-body formation and secondary metabolite production	[138]

Table 2. Cont.

BGC Activation by Natural Triggers and Manipulation of Their Global Regulators			
Section 1: <i>Aspergillus</i> and <i>Penicillium</i>			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
Light <i>laeAΔ, veAΔ, velBΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus ochraceus</i>	<i>laeAΔ/veAΔ/velBΔ</i> : differential regulation of 66% of all BGC backbone genes (majority downregulated) drastic reduction of Ochratoxin A production	[136]
Light Velvet: $\Delta Apc.LaeA\Delta$ <i>Apc.VeAΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus pachycristatus</i>	<i>Apc.LaeAΔ</i> or <i>Apc.VeAΔ</i> reduce production of echinocandin B and sterigmatocystin Impact of deletions on aerial hyphae, pigmentation, development of conidiophores, conidial germination rate, and ascospore maturation	[134]
Media Mimicking of plant and rhizosphere environment Nitrogen, Metals, Amino acids	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	(independent) signals for terrain production: methionine, nitrogen limitation, iron starvation (=host rhizosphere) Global regulators AreA and AtfA essential for terrain production	[119]
Media composition Carbon source Amino acids CreA	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	discovery of isoflavipucine and dihydroisoflavipucine production only in the presence of certain amino acids, alkaline pH, and strictly repressed in the presence of glucose (CreA).	[167]
Media C-source	<i>Penicillium citrinum</i>	Increased production of citrinin on glucose compared to sucrose	[187]
Media HDACi DNMTi	<i>Aspergillus awamori</i>	Media: MEA, rice, nutrient, triptone soya agar HDACi: valproic acid, nicotinamide, trichostatin A DNMTi: 5-azacytidine Different metabolic profiles between media and epigenetic modifiers Nicotinamide was found to be the best epigenetic inducer Rice grains were the best medium for SM induction	[188]
Metals and Trace elements	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Xanthocillin BGC-derived isocyanides help accumulate copper and exhibit antimicrobial activity	[166]
Metals and Trace elements	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	HapX and SreA, which oppositely regulate iron homeostasis also control an iron-dependent secondary metabolite network comprising the virulence factor hexahydroastachrome (tryptophan-derived iron (III)-complex) which causes an iron starvation phenotype upon overexpression	[165]

Table 2. Cont.

BGC Activation by Natural Triggers and Manipulation of Their Global Regulators			
Section 1: <i>Aspergillus</i> and <i>Penicillium</i>			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
Metals and Trace elements Oxidative stress <i>sidCΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	NRPS SidC involved in iron regulation (excess and starvation) Upregulated by oxidative stress <i>sidCΔ</i> : bad iron utilization (reduced growth under iron-starvation and higher iron demand), delayed germination under iron-depleted conditions, higher sensitivity of conidia to oxidative stress, no cleistothecia formation	[169]
Metals and Trace elements	<i>Penicillium brasilianum</i>	CuSO ₄ and MnSO ₄ alter the SM-profile production of a series of cyclodepsipeptides repression of verruculogen biosynthesis	[163]
Metals and Trace elements	<i>Penicillium urticae</i>	eight metal ions tested manganese dependent conversion of 6-methylsylicyic acid to patulin	[164]
OE <i>laeA</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	overexpression of <i>laeA</i> : activation of the Terrequinone (tdi) cluster and production of terrequinone A	[189]
Osmotic & Saline stress	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i> Three ex-type strains from three different collections	Osmotic (glycerol) and saline stress had different impacts on SM profile of fungal strains. Also strain-source specific chemotypes. Same morphology across all treatments	[159]
Oxidative stress Carbon source	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	Strains that produce less aflatoxin are more prone to oxidative stress and have more differentially regulated genes (also SM genes) under oxidative stress conditions carbon source affects BGC expression and production	[190]
Oxidative stress <i>ApyapAΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus ochraceus</i>	<i>ApyapAΔ</i> shows missing redox balance which triggers aflatoxin synthesis and an involvement of oxidative stress in ochratoxin A regulation	[174]
Oxidative stress <i>veAΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus parasiticus</i>	transcription factor AtfB regulates conidial tolerance towards oxidative stress AtfB binds to promoters with CRE sites in the aflatoxin cluster under inducing conditions. <i>veAΔ</i> abolishes these interactions	[171]
pH	<i>A. nidulans</i> <i>A. parasiticus</i>	Sterigmatocystin/aflatoxin expressed at higher levels at acidic pH than on neutral or alkalic pH Constitutive active PacC in <i>A. nidulans</i> reduced sterigmatocystin production	[150]

Table 2. Cont.

BGC Activation by Natural Triggers and Manipulation of Their Global Regulators			
Section 1: <i>Aspergillus</i> and <i>Penicillium</i>			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
pH Acidic stress	Acid-Tolerant Fungi <i>Penicillium</i> <i>Aspergillus</i> <i>Talaromyces</i> <i>Cladosporium</i> <i>Allophoma</i> <i>Alternaria</i> <i>Trichoderma</i>	Supernatant extracts: $\frac{3}{4}$ shows cytotoxic activity, < $\frac{1}{4}$ show antimicrobial or anti-H1N1 activity pH-related chemical diversity of <i>P. oxalicum</i>	[149]
pH <i>AcpacCΔ</i>	<i>Aspergillus carbonarius</i>	<i>AcpacCΔ</i> : impaired fungal growth at neutral/alkaline pH, diminished gluconic and citric acid production, reduced virulence toward grapes and nectarine fruits PacC involved in pathogenicity and Ochratoxin A production	[148]
pH Light Temperature	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	Aflatoxin production: 5x increase of in darkness pH 4 media produces 30 times more than pH 7.4 strongly reduced production at 18 or 40 °C	[191]
pH <i>pacC</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	Penicillin highest at alkaline pH and in mutated <i>pacC</i> (mimics alkaline conditions) Production was lowest at acid pH and in strains that mimic acid pH	[151]
Solid-state vs. submerged fermentation Media	<i>Aspergillus oryzae</i>	Solid-state: Increase of coumarins and oxylipins, higher antimicrobial activities submerged: Terpenoids abundant	[178]
Solid-state vs. submerged fermentation	<i>Penicillium expansum</i>	Submerged fermentation: strongly increased production of polyketide metabolites (agonodepside B, rotiorin, verrucosidin, and ochrephilone) Solid-state fermentation: exclusive production of meroterpenoid compounds (andrastin A and C)	[177]
Temperature	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Temperature affects stress tolerance, pigmentation, and tryptacidin accumulation in conidia	[192]
Temperature	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Endocrocin biosynthesis in spores is temperature-dependent and endocrine is connected to pathogenicity	[193]
Temperature	<i>Penicillium oxalicum</i> <i>P. citrinum</i>	Unique metabolite profile under temperature stress	[194]

Table 2. Cont.

BGC Activation by Natural Triggers and Manipulation of Their Global Regulators			
Section 1: <i>Aspergillus</i> and <i>Penicillium</i>			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
Temperature Oxidative stress Culture conditions	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	Float culture method Stress conditions: afatoxin is downregulated under stress secondary metabolites with antioxidant properties (e.g., kojic acid and imizoquins) were upregulated under stress	[118]
Velvet: $\Delta laeA$ $laeA$ -OE	<i>Aspergillus</i> spp.	$laeA\Delta$: abolishment of sterigmatocystin, penicillin, and lovastatin $laeA$ -OE: increased penicillin and lovastatin production $laeA$ expression is negatively regulated by AflR	[142]
$mpkA\Delta$ (kinase knockout library)	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	$mpkA\Delta$: activation of the pkf-cluster and production of aspernidine A	[195]
Section 2: <i>Fusarium</i>			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
Δ /OE $lae1$	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	$\Delta lae1$: downregulation of unknown NRPS4 cluster OE- $lae1$ induced beauvericin cluster and STC7-cluster (product not identified) generally LaeA has a substantial impact on many SMs	[147]
$\Delta areA$, $\Delta areB$	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	deletions have an impact on >50% of BGCs $\Delta areB$: upregulation of cryptic clusters PKS09, NRPS04, NRPS21	[127]
$\Delta areA$, $areB$	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	AreA and AreB are required for gibberellic acid production	[196]
$\Delta pacC$	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	$pacC$ deletion de-represses bikaverin cluster-complementation with active $pacC$ variant represses bikaverin cluster	[153]
Global regulator of development $\Delta csm1$ (<i>NsdD</i>)	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	$\Delta csm1$: elevated conidiation in wt and also in non-sporulating ΔveA strain. Induction of BGC for bikaverin and fusarubins Impact on 19 of 47 BGCs	[176]
Light N-source ΔveA , $\Delta laeA$	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	velvet complex and nitrate metabolism intertwined ΔveA or $\Delta laeA$: growth impaired on nitrate/nitrite AREA involved in chromatin accessibility of two velvet-regulated BGCs (beauvericin and siderophore ferricrocin)	[131]

Table 2. Cont.

BGC Activation by Natural Triggers and Manipulation of Their Global Regulators			
Section 2: <i>Fusarium</i>			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
Light N- source pH $\Delta areA$, $\Delta areB$ $\Delta vel1$, $\Delta lae1$ $\Delta pacC$	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	$\Delta areA$: reduces fusaric acid production $\Delta areB$: abolished fusaric acid production $\Delta vel1$ and $\Delta lae1$: significant reduction of fusaric acid $\Delta pacC$: abolishment of fusaric acid cluster expression	[197]
Light $\Delta fgwc-1$ $\Delta fgwc-2$	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	$\Delta fgwc-1/\Delta fgwc-2$: impaired carotenogenesis, photoreactivation and maturity of perithecia mutants produced more aurofusarin and trichothecenes independent from light and have derepressed conidiation during constant light	[198]
Light $\Delta vel1$, $\Delta vel2$, $\Delta lae1$	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	$\Delta ffvel1$ and $\Delta fflae1$: velvet positively regulates gibberellic acid, fumonisins and fusarin C, velvet negatively regulates bikaverin	[141]
N-source pH Host infection	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i> <i>F. circinatum</i> <i>F. mangiferae</i> <i>F. oxysporum</i>	PKS19 cluster is induced on rice but not maize Gibberelic acid cluster only expressed in <i>F. fujikuroi</i> Different conditions for different metabolites necessary: fusarins: high nitrogen, bikaverin and fusarubins: acidic low nitrogen or alkaline low nitrogen, Fumonisin B1: acidic low nitrogen	[125]
N-source $\Delta areA$	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	asparagine was found to be a preferential nitrogen source. $\Delta areA$ led to poor growth on $NaNO_3$ Utilization of aspartic acid, histidine, isoleucine, leucine, threonine, tyrosine, and valine as nitrogen sources was shown to depend of a functional AREA. AREA is required for the production of deoxynivalenol (DON), zearalenone, and fusarielin H regardless of the medium	[129]
N-source $\Delta areA$	<i>Gibberella fujikuroi</i>	$\Delta areA$: significantly reduced gibberellin production	[199], [200]
N-source/starvation Δ of N-pathway regulators	<i>Fusarium Fujikuroi</i>	Effect of N-source (glutamine, nitrate) and starvation in different mutants $\Delta niaD$, $\Delta nrtA$, $\Delta nirA$ and $\Delta areA$ expression of backbone genes of gibberellic acid and bikaverin BGC after 72 h in starvation in wt and all mutants except for gibberellic acid in $\Delta areA$	[124]

Table 2. Cont.

BGC Activation by Natural Triggers and Manipulation of Their Global Regulators			
Section 2: <i>Fusarium</i>			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
pH <i>PAC1</i>	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	Pac1 negatively regulates trichothecene BGC; induction under acidic pH Δ fgpac1: reduced development under neutral and alkaline pH, increased sensitivity to H ₂ O ₂ and early onset of Tri expression and product synthesis	[155]
Temperature	<i>Fusarium langsethiae</i> <i>F. sporotrichioides</i>	Impact of temperature and time on spore amount and T-2, HT-2 toxin production	[201]
Section 3: Other Species			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
Additives	<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	Triggering silent BGCs by natural dietary components: Grape skin and turmeric extracts resulted in 20 and 14 additional compounds	[202]
C-source	<i>Spicaria elegans</i>	starch vs. glucose novel spicochalin A and five new aspochalasins (M–Q)	[203]
Co-cultivation Additives	<i>Isaria felina</i>	potassium bromide and cocultivation with <i>Aspergillus sulphureus</i> : discovery of Isariketide B and Oxirapentyn L	[204]
Cultivation optimization for SM production	<i>Phomopsis</i> sp. <i>Hant25</i>	Optimization of different media and cultivation parameters for overproduction of mycoepoxydiene Parameters: combination of stationary and agitated, solid support (cellulose paper disc), different medias, cultivation time	[179]
Light Δ <i>lreA</i> (= <i>WC-1</i>)	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	Opposite light regulation of mycotoxin and spore production spores decreased under light and production of alternariol increased two to three times altertoxin production was strictly dependent on light. Δ white-collar 1 (<i>WC-1</i>) gene (<i>lreA</i>): derepression of spore formation in dark and in light. altertoxin formation strongly induced in the dark alternariol formation partially dependent on <i>LreA</i> still able to partially respond to blue light	[205]

Table 2. Cont.

BGC Activation by Natural Triggers and Manipulation of Their Global Regulators			
Section 3: Other Species			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
Light Velvet $\Delta velB$ ΔveA $\Delta laeA$	<i>Cuetootiopsis microspora</i>	Velvet Complex involved in the development, stress tolerance, and secondary metabolism $\Delta velB$: hypersensitive to osmotic stress and congo red pestalotiollide B production requires <i>velB</i> and <i>laeA</i> . <i>veA</i> inhibits pestalotiollide B biosynthesis	[132]
Light Velvet Iron starvation	<i>Neurospora crassa</i>	Velvet controls development, secondary metabolism, and light-dependent carotenoid production Heterotrimeric velvet complex (VE-1/VE-2/LAE-1) suppresses the production of the siderophore coprogen under iron starvation	[133]
Light C-source $\Delta CRE1$	<i>Trichoderma reesei</i>	Intertwined regulation of light and carbon pathways CRE1- regulated cluster is responsible for light-dependent production of dihydrotrichotetronin Biosynthesis of the antibiotic paracelsin was influenced	[135]
Light $\Delta SUB1$	<i>Trichoderma reesei</i>	<i>SUB1</i> is light-regulated <i>SUB1</i> affects growth and is required for female fertility SM is regulated by <i>SUB1</i> in a light- and nutrient-dependent manner	[206]
Media Salts Cultivation type	<i>Nigrospora</i> sp. MA75	Discovery of 2,3-didehydro-19a-hydroxy-14-epicochlioquinone B, 6-O-desmethyldechlorigriseofulvin 6'-hydroxygriseofulvin Media: NaCl vs. NaI, static/solid vs. agitated/liquid, rice-based vs. yeast extract	[207]
Media HDACi	<i>Drechslera</i> sp.,	HDACi: SAHA, valproate, octanoylhydroxamic acid 2 new metabolites: chromanone and prenylhydroxybenzoic acid different metabolome between MEA and minimal media biotransformation of the inhibitors occurred	[208]
Media HDACi DNMTi	<i>Cladosporium resinae</i>	Media. Czapek-DOX, YES, PDA, starch, liquid vs. solid HDACi: SAHA DNMTi: 5-AZA Czapek yeast extract broth: more total secondary metabolites DNMTi and HDACi: expressions of silent genes	[209]

Table 2. Cont.

BGC Activation by Natural Triggers and Manipulation of Their Global Regulators			
Section 3: Other Species			
Trigger	Organism	Observation	Ref.
N-source Δ AcareA	<i>Acremonium chrysogenum</i>	AcareA is required for nitrogen metabolism and cephalosporin production	[130]
OE-laeA	<i>Chaetomium globosum</i>	overexpression of laeA: activation of the chaetoglobosin gene cluster and production of chaetoglobosin Z	[145]
pH Δ pacC pacC ^c	<i>Trichoderma virens</i>	Δ pacC: decreased competitiveness against <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> and <i>Sclerotium rolfsii</i> Constitutive PacC: wt like overgrowth of <i>R. solani</i>	[152]
Plant Hormones	<i>Arthrinium sacchari</i>	discovery of the polyketides kinetin, 6-benzylaminopurine, and forchlorfenuron	[210]
Salinity	47 marine fungi isolates	NaCl and KCl had growth-promoting effect on most marine fungi and 15% of isolates showed increased antifungal activity against <i>Candida albicans</i> , NaCl had impact on the metabolite profile	[160]
Salinity	<i>Spicaria elegans</i>	Different secondary metabolites on different saline conditions (3% and 10%) Four metabolites, only at 10% salinity: (2E,2'Z)-3,3'-(6,6'-dihydroxybiphenyl-3,3'-diyl) (new compound), diacrylic acid, aspulvinone E, aspochalasin E and trichodermamide B	[162]
Solid vs. liquid fermentation Solid growth support	<i>Cylindrocarpon</i> sp. <i>Acremonium</i> sp. <i>Penicillium</i> sp.	Addition of inert absorbent polymeric attachment supports in solid state and submerged fermentation leading to distinct metabolite profiles Impact on culture morphology and relative metabolite yields Solid agar with moist polyester-cellulose paper: <i>Cylindrocarpon</i> sp. (pyrrocidines A and B), <i>Acremonium</i> sp. (acremonidins A–E) Agitated submerged cultures: Complex HPLC metabolome, decrease in target compounds Liquid fermentation with various inert growth supports (polypropylene, polypropylene cellulose, polyester-cellulose, or polyurethane): production of rugulosin, skyrin, flavomannin, and the new compound WF159-A (bisanthracene)	[180]
Temperature	40 polar fungal isolates	45% of fungal strains showed antimicrobial activity Different fungal metabolite profiles dependent on temperature (4, 10, 15, 28 °C)	[158]
Δ vmlaeA	<i>Valsa mali</i>	Δ vmlaeA : reduced virulence and differential regulated secondary metabolism profile (31/60).	[143]

The table is separated into three sections: Section 1 contains studies that were conducted on fungi of the genus *Aspergillus* or *Penicillium*, Section 2 comprises fungi from the genera *Fusarium* and Section 3 presents studies with filamentous fungi of other genera. The sections themselves are ordered alphabetically by the trigger that was applied. Signs and Abbreviations: Δ : deletion of a gene; OE: overexpression of a gene; TF: transcription factor.

3.2. Co-Cultivation

During co-cultivation [116,211,212], microorganisms are brought into an interactive environment with the aim to mimic natural competition that can also trigger the production of SMs. There are several possible setups for co-cultivation. One approach uses (random) pairwise co-cultivation of strains [213] (Table 3; Setup 1). A second approach tests a strain collection against certain microorganisms of interest, such as (antibiotic-resistant) pathogens [214,215] (Table 3; Setup 2). A third approach cultivates strains together with the (sterile-filtrated or extracted) culture supernatants of other microorganisms. The latter approach can be necessary if cultivation or media requirements of the individual species are not compatible for simultaneous cultivation or if the mechanisms of the induction of SMs (e.g., physical interaction or presence of a compound) is being investigated [216] (Table 3; Setup 3). This latter strategy was just recently chosen in our laboratory resulting in the identification of the signaling molecule, that triggers the fungal response in the interaction between the bacterium *Streptomyces rapamycinicus* and the filamentous ascomycete *A. nidulans* [184]. Another fruitful concept is the co-cultivation of a fungus with a bacteriophage (i.e., infection) which led to the production of a novel SM [217]. Co-cultivation can be very challenging due to the sheer endless combinatorial numbers of specimens and cultivation parameters that have to fit both organisms. However, if the co-cultivation approach is already well established, it can be a very powerful and rewarding tool. Table 3 lists publications that successfully applied co-cultivation approaches for the activation of BGCs.

Table 3. Discovery of new secondary metabolites by co-cultivation. Ordered by Set-up type.

BGC Activation by Co-Cultivation				
Setup	Method	Organism	Observation	Ref.
1	Co-cultivation of two developmental stages (morphs) of a marine alga-derived fungus Pre-grow both morphs on agar plates (2–3 weeks) → small liquid pre-cultures → combine mono-cultures after 14 days → cultivate for 15–20 days	<i>Aspergillus alliaceus</i> and its teleomorph <i>Petromyces alliaceus</i>	Production of the cytotoxic chlorinated bianthrone allianthrone A (only liquid) Morphs develop new phenotype in co-culture under liquid but not solid fermentation Restreaks after co-culture keep phenotype and can produce bianthrone on liquid and solid media	[218]
1	Submerge co-culture and membrane-separated culture 5 mL of pre-culture (<i>A. flavipes</i> and <i>Streptomyces</i> sp. in a ratio of 1:4 (v/v)) were added to 200 mL medium 8 days of cultivation	<i>Aspergillus flavipes</i> marine actinomycete <i>Streptomyces</i> sp.	Production of five aspochalasins and rosellichalasin by fungus with cytotoxic effects against <i>Streptomyces</i> . Physical interaction necessary	[219]
1	3 media (ISP2, GYE, F) inoculated with 3d old pre-cultures. 4L culture, fungal preculture was incubated 2 d earlier, 6 h before harvest 50 g/L Diaion HP-20 resin was added	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> MR2012 (marine) <i>Streptomyces leeuwenhoekii</i> (C34 and C58) (desert)	Fungus: production of luteoride D (luteoride derivative), pseurotin G (pseurotin derivative), terezine D, 11-O-methylpseurotin A Bacteria C34: Chaxapeptin C58: Chaxapeptin doubled, pentalenic acid	[220]
1	16 h old mycelia of <i>A. fumigatus</i> were washed and placed in fresh AMM with 1/20 vol of the <i>streptomyces</i> culture or with 1/20 filtered supernatant. Harvest after 12 h	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> <i>Streptomyces rapamycinicus</i>	induction of fungal PKS FgnA, the discovery of bacteria-specific germination inhibitor fumigermin	[221]
1	2 day 30 °C liquid agitated co-culture (93 mL London + 32 mL GYM medium). simultaneous inoculation of both MOs (equal amounts of spores)	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> <i>Streptomyces mobaraensis</i>	bacterial glycopeptide (antibiotic) triggers antibacterial and iron-chelating tropolonesanhydrosepedonin and antibiotic C (<i>A. nidulans</i>), polyketide tripyrnidone (novel structure)	[222]
1	Solid rice medium	<i>Aspergillus versicolor</i> <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	two new tetralones; aspvanicin A and aspvanicin B several other cryptic SMs; cytotoxic activity against mouse lymphoma cells	[223]
1	Confrontation assay on ISP2 agar MALDI-TOF straight from agar Inoculation for 48 h at 30 °C	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> <i>Aspergillus niger</i> <i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> (GA40)	The coral-derived bacteria GA40 produced an antifungal iturin	[224]

Table 3. Cont.

BGC Activation by Co-Cultivation				
Setup	Method	Organism	Observation	Ref.
1	Precultures on rice media 1 week then co-culture for 2 weeks. Axenic cultivation with potassium bromide	<i>Aspergillus sulphureus</i> KMM 4640 <i>Isaria feline</i>	discovery of Isariketide B (rice media with KBr) and Oxirapentyn L (Co-cultivation)	[204]
1	Fungal bacterial stepwise liquid co-culture. Addition of bacterial broth (1/1000) to fungal culture on day 3. Further cultivation for 2 days	<i>Emericella</i> sp. (CNL-878; marine fungus) <i>Salinispora arenicola</i> (CNH-665; ascomycete)	Emericellamides A and B synthesis by <i>Emericella</i> sp.	[225]
1	Solid agar confrontation assay (5 days) Submerged fermentation (2 mL of each pre-culture and cultivation for 5 days in broth) Co-cultivation of MF028 with five other strains time-course	<i>Chaunopycnis</i> sp. (CMB-MF028) <i>Trichoderma hamatum</i> (CMB-MF030) Co-isolated from mollusc <i>Siphonaria</i> sp.	Chaunopyran A production Cultivation on sterilized mycelia showed no induction	[226]
1	Extraction of confrontation zone (Agar) Incubation of several weeks Dereplication via monocultures Method development: ~600 cultures by confrontation assay on agar UHPLC–TOF-MS fingerprints of mono and cocultures have been prepared to filter out new peaks	<i>Fusarium</i> isolates (clinical, soil or plant-derived) <i>Aspergillus clavatus</i> , <i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> , <i>Acremonium</i> , <i>Cladosporium</i> sp. <i>Hohenbuehelia reniformis</i> <i>Bionectria ochroleuca</i> <i>Eutypa lata</i>	Chemical novel MS spectra have been recorded Results indicate that a large portion of fungi produce new metabolites in co-culture	[213]
1	Solid state confrontation cultivation 17 basidiomycetes, 136 co-cultures Molecular network analysis Liquid co-cultivation for 5–30 days	<i>Ganoderma applanatum</i> <i>Trametes versicolor</i>	discovery of novel xylosides 3-phenyllactic acid and orsellinic acid in <i>G. applanatum</i>	[227]
1	Addition of bacterial broth (1/1000) to fungal culture on day 3. Harvest after 24 h. Screen of 50 fungal strains	<i>Libertella</i> sp. (CNL-523) <i>α-proteobacterium</i> (CNJ-328)	Discovery of Libertellenones A–D, produced by the addition of marine α -proteobacterium to a 3-day <i>Libertella</i> sp. culture.	[228]
1	Submerged fermentation Different pre-grow times before co-cultivation. Optimal: addition of fungal culture to 2-day bacterial culture and further incubation for 7 days. Other setups showed metabolome of either bacterial or fungal axenic culture	<i>Penicillium</i> sp. (WC-29-5) <i>Streptomyces fradiae</i> (007)	Production of five phenolic polyketides	[229]

Table 3. Cont.

BGC Activation by Co-Cultivation				
Setup	Method	Organism	Observation	Ref.
1	Solid rice media, Cultivation parameters Optimal: inoculation of <i>Penicillium</i> sp mycelium plug, and seed medium of <i>Bacillus</i> sp. simultaneously at the center of petri dish 15d culture	<i>Penicillium</i> sp. (DT-F29) <i>Bacillus</i> sp. (B31)	Ten bioactive 2,5-diketopiperazines by <i>Penicillium</i> sp.	[230]
1	Co-cultivation on solid rice medium	<i>Penicillium</i> strains (IO1 and IO2) isolated from sponge	Accumulation of norlichexanthone and monocerin, biotransformation of the antifungal pyridoxatin to methyl-pyridoxatin	[231]
1	Liquid co-culture with seawater-based marine nutrient medium. After 24 h, bacterial culture is added to fungal cultivation following further 6d cultivation	<i>Pestalotia</i> (marine fungus) CNJ-328 (marine bacterium)	Discovery of pestalolne (antibiotic)	[216]
1	Submerged fermentation and sea water agar, inoculation of flasks with spores of both fungi, cultivation for 9 days	<i>Talaromyces aculeatus</i> <i>Penicillium variable</i>	Four new polyketides (penitalarins A/ B/C and nafuredin B) cytotoxicity against some human cancer cell lines	[232]
2	Mycelia from <i>A nidulans</i> o/n preculture was combined with 1/20 (<i>v/v</i>) <i>Streptomyces</i> preculture in fresh AMM medium. Further cultivation at 37 °C for 24 h	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> with a collection of 58 soil-dwelling actinomycetes	Physical interaction between the fungus and <i>Streptomyces hygrosopicus</i> . Induction of orsellinic acid and derivatives (lecanoric acid, yellow polyketides)	[215]
2	Co-culture in Warkingsman's agar (Confrontation assay) and liquid medium (5 days)	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i> vs. 12.000 bacteria	reduced virulence of <i>F. graminearum</i> due to <i>Pseudomonas piscium</i> (FgGcn5 inhibitor phenazine-1-carboxamide)	[214]
3	treatment of <i>Aspergillus</i> with extracts of <i>Streptomyces</i> cultures	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> <i>Streptomyces rapamycinicus</i>	a guanidine containing macrolide, polaramycin B that is constitutively produced by the bacteria triggers the production of the ORS BGC	[184]
3	analytical scale microbial cultivations in a 24-well plate cultivation in presence of metabolites from other cultivation	<i>Aspergillus</i> sp. <i>Streptomyces</i> sp.	bacteriostatic cyclo-(L-Phe-trans-4-hydroxy-L-Pro) from <i>Aspergillus</i> stimulates nitric oxide production by <i>Streptomyces</i> which triggers silent BGC of <i>Aspergillus</i> : fungistatic heronapyrrole B	[233]

3.3. Conclusions of Initial Assessment

OSMAC approaches, paired with metabolome analysis, transcriptome analysis, and bioinformatic methods can already create an extensive map of the secondary metabolome that is produced in a laboratory environment. To discriminate already known compounds from putatively new compounds, exact masses of the new compounds are compared to masses from already described compounds. This can be performed in the lab by screening against a library of SM standards [234] or by applying bioinformatic tools such as PRISM 4 [235] or DEREPLICATOR+ [76].

After this initial assessment, the remaining cryptic BGCs can then be targeted by molecular biology methods for releasing the full bioactive potential of the target organism.

4. BGC Activation Using Molecular Biology Tools: The Way to Fully Exploit the Genome for Novel Bioactive Substances

Applying molecular biology tools for genetic engineering enables the alteration of regulatory mechanisms at the genomic or epigenetic layer. This way, cryptic BGCs not transcribed under any tested laboratory condition can be activated in the native host by the manipulation of global regulators, pathway-specific regulators, chromatin modifiers, or by disruption of a repressive signaling pathway. Furthermore, if the fungus is not amenable to any approach that requires genetic transformation, the whole BGC may be transferred to and expressed in another organism (i.e., heterologous expression). There are untargeted methods that result in a global metabolomic and transcriptional response (e.g., deletion of global repressor or overexpression of global activator) and there are targeted methods, that aim to activate only a specific BGC by manipulating regulatory elements of the BGC (e.g., overexpression of pathway-specific transcription factor (TF)). The advantage of targeted methods is that changes in the metabolome can be much more easily linked to the BGC under study. Figure 2 illustrates the molecular genetic methods for the activation of silent BGCs.

Figure 2. Molecular biology methods for BGC activation. Silent genes are depicted as grey or black arrows while active genes are green. Yellow thunder bolts represent genetic manipulation.

Genetic manipulation that results in overexpression or deletion of a gene is abbreviated as “OE” or “KO” respectively. (a) The exchange of one (i.e., pathway-specific TF) or several promoter regions of the BGC of interest leads to gene activation. (b) Overexpression of a global regulator can lead to the activation of several BGCs all over the genome. (c) Heterologous expression of a BGC of interest in an expression host followed by cultivation, extraction and structure elucidation of the compound encoded within the BGC. (d) Genetic manipulation of a chromatin remodeler can lead to the de-repression or silencing of a BGC that is regulated by the respective remodeler. Silencing and expression-promoting histone modifications are depicted as grey and green pins respectively.

4.1. Overexpression of a Pathway Specific Transcription Factor or Whole BGC

By overexpression of a pathway-specific TF, the whole cluster may be upregulated. This strategy was shown to be successful in increasing the production of aflatoxin in *A. flavus* [236] and also led to the discovery of aspyridone [237], and asperfuranone in *A. nidulans* [238] or trichosetin in *F. fujikuroi* [239]. Further examples can be retrieved from Table 4.

Bioinformatic analyses revealed that in the case of the genus *Aspergillus* 50% to up to 70% of the BGCs contain a pathway-specific TF [240,241]. Co-expression studies under different conditions in *Aspergillus niger*, however, provided evidence that eight of 45 BGCs that contain a TF, show no co-expression between the BGC-synthetic genes and the TF, which indicates that they are not affiliated with the BGC and hence, overexpression would not lead to its activation [242]. This hypothesis is supported by a publication where overexpression of the pathway-specific TF failed in 15 of 18 cases in *A. nidulans* [243]. This approach also fails if the TF needs to get post-translationally activated, as it is the case with AflR, the pathway-specific TF of the sterigmatocystin cluster of *A. nidulans*, which is inactivated by the presence of glucose [244] and activated by the RimO kinase in response to glucose starvation, as recently discovered in our laboratory [245]. Another possibility could be a necessary interaction between the BGC-specific TF and another factor or natural inducer to unfold the full activation potential. In this scenario, the overexpression of just the TF might not have any effect on the clustered genes [246]. A possible way to circumvent this was shown in the (+)-asperlin cluster in *A. nidulans*. The modular composition of many TFs (activator domain, DNA-binding domain) made it possible to fuse the DNA-binding domain of the asperlin BGC-specific TF (AlnR) with the trans-activator domain of another TF (afoA). This way, the overexpression of this hybrid TF led to the discovery of the antibiotic (+)-asperlin [246].

In the case of clusters that do not have a TF, serial promoter replacements of all BGC-specific genes can be conducted. This approach has been successful in the activation of several uncharacterized BGCs in *A. nidulans*, finally shown to be responsible for the expression of the Ivo gene cluster producing a new pigment [247], or for the discovery of the new proteasome inhibitor fellutamide B [248], and chicorine [243]. The idea was also tested in other species and Table 4 summarizes some of the successful attempts in the published literature. However, it is clear that exchanging many promoters in a multi-gene BGC can be quite cumbersome and may not always lead to successful transformation events, especially when the BGC under investigation is located in heterochromatic regions.

Table 4. Successful application of overexpression methods for induction of BGCs. Entries are ordered alphabetically by organism.

Targeted BGC Activation by Overexpression				
Method	Target/Parameter	Organism	Observation	Ref.
TF	<i>fsqA</i> (TF)	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	OE of <i>fsqA</i> (<i>fsq</i> gene cluster) production of pyrido [1,2-b]isoquinolines fumisoquin A and fumisoquin B	[249]
TF	<i>xanC</i>	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	OE of <i>xanC</i> : Activation of <i>xan</i> cluster and production of xanthocillin derivatives, the sulfated xanthocillin derivative BU-4704 and xanthocillin X monomethyl ether	[250]
CRISPRa	AN8506 AN8507 <i>mdpE</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	Method establishment: upregulation of putative BGC genes (AN8506, AN8507) and the silent <i>mdpE</i> cluster via nucleosome map assisted targeting of inducible VPR-dCas9 into accessible chromatin in promoter	[251]
CRISPRa	<i>breF</i> , <i>fuml</i> , <i>fwnA</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	Method establishment: fusion of different chromatin active enzymes/domains to dCas9, activation of <i>breF</i> and <i>fuml</i> via p300-dCas9 (HAT), repression of <i>breF</i> by HAT GcnE-dCas9 and HDAC HosA-dCas9 and RpdA-dCas9 activation of <i>fwnA</i> by HosA-dCa9	[252]
CRISPRa (multiplex)	mic- BGC	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	method establishment: activation of mic cluster by dCas12a-VPR (multigene CRISPRa): dehydromicroperfurane production	[253]
Hybrid Activator	(+)-Asperlin cluster	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	fusion of the DNA binding domain of AlnR (pathway-specific TF) and the trans-activation domain of AfoA lead to the activation of the (+)-Asperlin cluster	[246]
TF	aspyridone cluster (<i>asp</i>)	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	overexpression of the pathway-specific TF <i>apdR</i> : activation of the silent BGC and production of aspyridone	[237]
TF	<i>ctnR</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	overexpression of the TF <i>ctnR</i> : Cluster activation (7 genes) and asperfuranone biosynthesis	[238]
TFBB gene	several BGCs	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	Chicorine cluster activation pkg cluster activation: alternariol, citreoisocoumarin, analogs of citreoisocoumarin pki cluster: 6-Hydroxy-7-methyl-3-nonylisoquinoline-5,8-dione pkhB /pkhA: 2,4-dihydroxy-6-[(3E,5E,7E)-2-oxonona-3,5,7-trienyl]benzaldehyde Pkd: 2-ethyl-4,6-dihydroxy-3,5-dimethylbenzaldehyde	[243]

Table 4. Cont.

Targeted BGC Activation by Overexpression				
Method	Target/Parameter	Organism	Observation	Ref.
TF	<i>pbcR</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	overexpression of <i>pbcR</i> resulted in upregulation of a 7-gene cluster and the production of ent-pimara-8(14),15-diene	[254]
BB gene Het. Expr.	micro-perfuranone (<i>micA</i> , BGC)	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	promoter exchange or heterologous expression (<i>A. niger</i>) of backbone gene <i>micA</i> was sufficient to produce microperfuranone	[255]
BB gene Het. Expr.	<i>asqK</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	OE of BB gene and heterologous expression for stepwise pathway elucidation: Products: 4'-methoxylated 6,7-benzodiazepinediones and 4'-methoxyviridicatin	[256]
Multiple genes	<i>inpE</i> cluster	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	promoter replacement of seven genes (<i>inpC</i> - <i>inpB</i>): production of protease inhibitor fellutamide B	[248]
Multiple genes	<i>ivo</i> cluster	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	OE of <i>ivoA</i> , <i>B</i> and <i>C</i> (and combinations): production of a dark pigment with the precursors N-acetyltryptophan and N-acetyl-6-hydroxytryptophan	[247]
Multiple genes	<i>sgdA</i> , <i>D</i> , <i>C</i> , <i>F</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	promoter replacements (4 genes): production of aspernidgulene A1 and A2	[257]
TF	<i>azaR</i> (TF)	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	overexpression of <i>azaR</i> : Activation of <i>aza</i> cluster and production of azanigerones A–F	[258]
TF	<i>aflR</i>	<i>Aspergillus parasiticus</i>	overexpression of <i>aflR</i> lead to the production of aflatoxin under repressing conditions	[259]
TF	TF of <i>pgm</i> BGC	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	OE of <i>pgm</i> cluster TF (ATEG_06205) led to the production of naphthoquinones	[260]
Resistance gene	neomycin resistance	<i>Aspergillus versicolor</i>	The introduction of neomycin resistance leads to production of the new anti-tumor bioactive compounds	[261]
TF	NRPS31 BGC (APS-like) PKS19- BGC	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	overexpression of pathway-specific TF (<i>APS2</i>) and complementation of enzyme (<i>F. semitectum APS8</i>) resulted in production of ApicidinF OE of TF and PKS19 resulted in production of four novel compounds (Fujikurin A–D)	[125,262,263]
TF	<i>APF2</i>	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	overexpression of <i>APF2</i> increases apicidin F synthesis	[262]
Whole BGC	<i>BIK2</i> or <i>BIK3</i>	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	Separate OE of <i>BIK2</i> and <i>BIK3</i> : revelation of precursor oxo-pre-bikaverin	[264]
BB gene	<i>DMATS1</i> , FFUJ_09179	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	OE of <i>DMATS1</i> yielded a reversely N-prenylated tryptophan	[265]

Table 4. Cont.

Targeted BGC Activation by Overexpression				
Method	Target/Parameter	Organism	Observation	Ref.
TF	<i>TF22</i> (PKS-NRPS1)	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	Tet-on activation of <i>TF22</i> (FFUJ_02222): cluster activation and trichosetin production	[239]
TF	<i>FSL7</i> (TF)	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	overexpression of the TF <i>FSL7</i> : activation of the FSL cluster (<i>PKS9</i>) and production of fusarielins, F, G, and H	[266]
BB gene	<i>PKS8</i>	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	activation of Gibepyrone and Prolipyrone B production	[33]
TF	<i>FGM4</i> (fg3_54 BGC; NRPS)	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	OE triggers the production of fusaoctaxin A. Deletion compromises plant infection	[267]
BB gene	<i>FSDS</i>	<i>Fusarium heterosporum</i>	OE of backbone gene resulted in novel Tyrosine-Derived 2,4-Pyrrolidinedione	[268]
TF	<i>PEXANC</i> (TF)	<i>Penicillium expansum</i>	OE of <i>PEXANC</i> resulted in the activation of the Citrinin cluster via the TF CtnA and production of Citrinin (evolutionary TF repurposing) The theoretical cluster responsible for xanthocillin remained silent	[269]
Resistance gene	neomycin resistance	<i>Penicillium purpurogenum</i>	Introduction of neomycin resistance results in the production of the new cyclic dipeptide penicimutide	[270]
CRISPRa (TF)	<i>macR</i> (TF)	<i>Penicillium rubens</i>	induction of macrophorin pathway-specific TF <i>macR</i> : production of macrophorin A, D and 4'-oxomacrophorin D	[271]

Abbreviations: Heterologous expression (Het. Expr.), backbone gene (BB gene), pathway-specific Transcription factor (TF).

4.2. Heterologous Expression

In the case that none of the aforementioned methods worked out or the studied species is not amenable to transformation or does not yield stable transformants, heterologous expression in a model host can be a powerful tool for the activation of unknown BGCs. For this method, single protein domains or genes or a whole BGC are introduced into a well-known production host. For the expression of single domains or genes, bacterial hosts such as *Escherichia coli* are often sufficient [272,273]. For larger genes or small clusters, many (engineered) yeast overexpression hosts such as *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Hansenula polymorpha* or *Pichia pastoris* exist [274,275].

If the expression scaffold of the donor organism (promoters, terminators, codon usage, splicing, etc.) is however not suited for the host there are two other possibilities. The regulatory elements of a BGC can be exchanged by host-specific ones, or the BGC can be heterologously expressed in a host that is closely related to the donor organism [274]. There are already engineered fungal hosts (low metabolite background, removal of proteases) that are readily deployed such as *A. oryzae* [276], *A. nidulans* [277] *A. niger* [278], but also *F. graminearum* [279,280] and *Penicillium* strains [281,282] are emerging as expression platforms. Heterologous expression is often used when high yields of a certain SM are important (i.e., industrial application) but specifically for the activation of silent fungal BGCs, systems such as FAC-MS [283,284], HeX [285] or CoIN [286] have been developed. Table 5 lists publications that used heterologous expression for the activation of silent BGCs.

Table 5. Successful examples of heterologous expression of single genes and BGCs. Ordered by organism.

BGC Activation by Heterologous Expression			
Target/Parameter	Organisms	Observation	Ref.
high throughput BGC activation	22 Species (Donors) <i>S. cerevisiae</i> (Host)	method establishment: Hex Expression of 22/41 fungal BGCs resulted in detectable compounds	[285]
156 FACs with random genome fragments	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus terreus</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus wentii</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Host)	method establishment: FAC-MS, Identification of 15 new substances Clusters/metabolites: <i>A. terreus</i> : ATEG_07067, ATEG_07500, sesterterpenoid, valactamide A, benzomalvin A/D <i>A. aculeatus</i> : AACU_51108, AACU_59515, <i>A. wentii</i> : ASPWE_027400, ASPWE_034272, ASPWE_042595, ASPWE_044725, ASPWE_085322, ASPWE_151732, ASPWE_163793	[284]
diketomorpholine BGC	<i>Aspergillus aculeatus</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Host)	Elucidation of the biosynthetic pathway of acu-dioxomorpholine, featuring a new type of condensation domain, by FAC-MS	[287]
<i>ftmA</i> (NRPS)	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> (Donor/Host) <i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Host)	OE of the NRPS <i>ftmA</i> : Production of Brevianamide F (Product of NRPS, product of cluster is putatively fumitremorgin)	[288]
pyr Cluster	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus. oryzae</i> (Host)	successive expression of the pyr cluster: Characterization of pyr cluster and isolation of the meroterpenoid pyripyropene	[289]
micro-perfuranone (<i>micA</i> , BGC)	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus niger</i> (Host)	promoter exchange or heterologous expression of backbone gene <i>micA</i> was sufficient to produce microperfuranone	[255]
<i>asqJ</i> <i>asqE-L</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Donor) <i>Escherichia coli</i> (Host)	OE of <i>asqE-L</i> in host and elucidation of AsqJ function by expression in <i>E. coli</i> Final products: 4'-methoxylated 6,7-benzodiazepinediones and 4'-methoxyviridicatin	[256]
<i>wA</i> (NWA)	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus oryzae</i> (Host)	expression of the WA-PKS: identification of the YWA1 compound	[290]
terreazepine BGC	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Host)	production of terreazepine	[291]
39 BGCs from various species	Donors: <i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i> <i>Alternaria alternata</i> <i>Fusarium graminearum</i> <i>Trichoderma viride</i> <i>Aspergillus flavipes</i> Host: <i>Aspergillus oryzae</i>	method establishment: genome mining assisted automated and high-throughput (auto-HTP) biofoundry workflow refactoring of 39 BGCs and production of 185 distinct terpenoids	[292]

Table 5. Cont.

BGC Activation by Heterologous Expression			
Target/Parameter	Organisms	Observation	Ref.
STC5, STC3	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i> (Donor) <i>E. coli</i> (Host)	Use of homologues STC3: (+)-eremophilene STC5:(<i>ε</i>)-guaia-6,10(14)-diene	[55]
carotenoid BGC of <i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Host)	method establishment: <i>aflR</i> scaffold as heterologous expression matrix; successful production of β -carotene	[286]
STC1	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i> (Donor) <i>E. coli</i> (Host)	Heterologous Expression of STC1 identification of (-)-germacrene D	[176]
FgJ03939 BGC	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i> (Donor) <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> (Host)	stepwise synthesis of several new sesquiterpene synthase-derived metabolites such as fusariumdiene, fusagramineol	[293]
part of the fusarubin gene cluster	<i>Fusarium solani</i> (Donor) <i>S. cerevisiae</i> (Host)	Expression of <i>FVPPT</i> , <i>fsr1</i> , <i>fsr2</i> , and <i>fsr3</i> in <i>S. cerevisiae</i> (galactose inducible promoter) and biosynthesis of bostrycoidin	[294]
<i>pvhA-E</i> (BGC)	<i>Penicillium variable</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Host)	Heterologous expression of genes <i>pvhA-e</i> : production of varicidin A and B	[295]
psilocybin BGC	<i>Psilocybe carpophores</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Host)	method establishment: Successful Expression of whole BGC as polycistronic RNA piconavirus assisted expression of the whole basidiomycete derived psilocybin BGC	[296]
TESG_6702 to 6705	<i>Trichophyton tonsurans</i> (Donor) <i>Aspergillus nidulans</i> (Host)	Expression of the whole cluster resulted in the production of neosartoricins	[297]

4.2.1. Fungal Artificial Chromosomes (FAC-MS) [283,284]

During the FAC-MS approach, the donors' DNA is sheared and random chromosomal parts (up to 300 kb) which eventually contain a whole BGC are cloned into fungal artificial chromosomes (FACs). These FACs are then transformed into the host organism (e.g., *A. nidulans*). This already led to the identification of 15 new metabolites from a library of 56 FACs each containing one unknown BGC from *A. aculeatus*, *A. terreus* or *A. wentii* in the heterologous expression host *A. nidulans*. It also resulted in the elucidation of the biosynthetic pathway of acu-dioxomorpholine from *A. aculeatus* [283,284,287]. As long as the expression host can utilize the AMA1-region and the donors' genomic information, the FAC-MS approach is a viable option for BGC mining.

4.2.2. CoIN [286]

This approach uses the *A. nidulans* regulatory matrix (TFs and their downstream promoters) of the sterigmatocystin cluster in combination with the *niiA/niAD* promoter. In this system, the TF-encoding genes *aflR* and its cofactor *aflS* are put under the control of the bi-directional promoter of the *niiA/niAD* genes coding for nitrate- and nitrite reductase, respectively, in *A. nidulans*. The genes of the BGC of interest are put under the control of the eight sterigmatocystin promoters that are regulated by AflR/AflS. This way, the orchestrated expression of up to eight genes of an unknown BGC without reusing a single promoter sequence can be accomplished by the growth of nitrate as the sole N-source leading to a high induction of the TFs.

4.2.3. Single Promoter BGC Expression [296]

Hoefgen and coworkers utilized the 2A peptide of the picornavirus to enable the transcription and translation of a whole BGC with only one promoter and one terminator. The 2A peptide auto-cleaves itself after translation without leading to the disassembly of ribosomes. This way, several genes can be co-expressed with the use of only a single promoter. The cloning of the construct however can be difficult and laborious and the transcript levels of the genes will stay equal and cannot be individually regulated.

4.2.4. Hex [285]

With the Hex approach, it is possible to express whole fungal BGCs in an engineered strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. New promoter sequences that are coregulated with p_{ADH2} (called Hex-promoters) have been utilized to enable cloning via a high throughput DNA assembly strategy by homologous recombination into 2 μ vectors. Genome mining assisted the selection of novel BGCs and subsequent cloning into yeast plasmids with an upper limit of seven genes per plasmid (maximum of two plasmids per clone). Expression is followed by untargeted metabolomics and LC-MS and NMR for structural elucidation of putatively novel compounds. For proof of concept, 41 investigated BGCs (from ascomycete and basidiomycete species) resulted in the detection of 22 new compounds.

5. Chromatin: An Important Layer of (BGC) Gene Regulation

While previously mentioned methods have already led to the discovery of many bioactive substances of fungal origin, many BGCs may still resist discovery with these approaches. Therefore, another strategy would be the manipulation of epigenetic and chromatin-based regulation of BGCs. Until recently, this could only be accomplished by the manipulation of global chromatin remodelers, however, as the general knowledge of this level of regulation increases, engineering of programmable chromatin regulators becomes feasible. The emergence of CRISPR/Cas-based methods, moreover, opens up new opportunities for activating BGCs by locus-specific modification of histones. These new approaches would not only make it possible to activate BGCs where other methods failed but have the potential of giving many new insights into the histone code of gene regulation. The next sections concentrate on the regulation of BGC expression via chromatin and histone modifications and describe also the current state of locus-specific

chromatin modifications for the activation of secondary metabolites. After that, we will review the role of a CRISPR/Cas as a carrier for targeted BGC activation via locus-specific chromatin modification.

In eukaryotes, genomic DNA wraps around histone protein octamers (~146 bp DNA/nucleosome) to form nucleosome chains (i.e., chromatin) [298,299]. Each nucleosome consists of an octamer constituted of two of the four core histone proteins H2A, H2B, H3 and H4 with sometimes iso-forms (e.g., H2AZ, CENH3, H4.2, H4v) of the histones being incorporated into the nucleosome for the specific cellular processes (e.g., DNA repair, etc.) [300]. Histones, especially H3 and H4, can carry post-translational modifications (or histone marks) on specific amino acid residues, that are read and translated by so-called reader proteins. Depending on the histone marks, chromatin structure is either loosely packed and open for transcription or very compact which hinders access to the DNA and therefore transcription. Furthermore, chromatin reader proteins can also recruit other proteins such as TFs or components of the transcriptional machinery. This way, genes can be either packaged into a very tight polymer of nucleosomes that is transcriptionally silent, called heterochromatin, or into a more relaxed form of packaging, called euchromatin, that allows proteins to interact with the underlying DNA (i.e., TFs, transcriptional machinery, etc.) [301].

5.1. Heterochromatin

The DNA within heterochromatic regions is not freely accessible for transcriptional activation. Pioneering factors however are capable of binding to condensed chromatin and subsequently recruit TFs or chromatin remodelers. This way, heterochromatin can be reversed to a more open and accessible state which promotes the binding and interaction of TFs or other reader/writer/eraser proteins and subsequently can result in gene activation [302,303]. In general, there are two pathways to form heterochromatic regions within the genome which are conserved in most eukaryotes i.e., constitutive and facultative heterochromatin. Both chromatin states are associated with distinct histone methylation marks.

5.1.1. Constitutive Heterochromatin via H3K9 Methylation and Clr4/HP1

Methylation of H3K9 is a hallmark of constitutive heterochromatin. H3K9me3 is established by the histone methyl-transferase KMT1 (ClrD in *A. nidulans*, *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* Clr4 homolog) [304] and the heterochromatin protein 1 (HP1, *A. nidulans* homolog HepA) which is a reader protein for this mark [305]. In some fungi, it was shown that the DNA methyltransferase (e.g., Dim-2 in *Neurospora crassa*) is subsequently recruited for further silencing of the region [306]. In the case of fungi, the term “constitutive” may be misleading as it was shown that *A. nidulans* can activate its sterigmatocystin cluster that contains hallmarks of constitutive heterochromatin (i.e., H3K9me3, HepA occupancy). Our lab showed that under inducing conditions in the wild type (nutrient starvation), H3K9me3 peaks are depleted from the ST BGC, and dissociation of HepA and increase of acetylation levels in the BGC occur, and these events are correlated with transcriptional activation of the cluster [305]. A similar observation was made in *Epichloe festucae* where BGCs that are silent in axenic culture, had H3K9me3 marks, but during plant infection, the H3K9me3 marks were reduced and the BGCs were activated [307]. In contrast, however, the phytopathogenic fungus *F. fujikuroi* does not have any detectable H3K9me3-enriched areas inside BGCs. In *F. fujikuroi*, these marks are generally in pericentric and centromeric regions and sometimes in transposon-rich regions with few or no annotated genes [125]. In *Fusarium mangiferae*, deletion of the *clrD* homolog *FmKMT1* led to increased production of beauvericin biosynthesis while fusapyrone biosynthesis was nearly abolished [308]. These examples suggest that heterochromatin via H3K9 methylation is differently involved in BGC silencing depending on the fungal species and the BGC in question. This pathway may be especially important in fungal species such as aspergilli, which lacks the molecular machinery for the establishment of H3K27me3 (PRC2 complex) associated with facultative heterochromatin in other fungi [309–311]. Thus, it is currently unknown if

and how facultative heterochromatin is established in these genera that do not possess PRC2 homologs.

5.1.2. Facultative Heterochromatin via H3K27me3 and Polycomb Repressive Complex II (PRC2)

The second pathway for heterochromatin formation is mediated by the polycomb repressive complex II and marked by the histone modification H3K27me3 [307,312,313]. This form of heterochromatin is generally regarded as facultative as it can be conditionally restructured into euchromatin, hence promoting the transcription of underlying genes (e.g., regulation of developmental genes in drosophila) [314]. Some genera such as *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* [309], *Ustilago* [310], and some yeasts [311] however are devoid of these chromatin marks. In fungi such as *F. graminearum* [312] and *F. fujikuroi* [315] many BGCs are located in H3K27me3 regions and knockdown or knockout of the methyltransferase-encoding gene *KMT6* of the PRC2 led to de-repression of several BGCs. More interestingly, formerly H3K27me3 regions are acetylated in *KMT6* knock-down strains as shown for the beauvericin BGC in *F. fujikuroi* [315]. Similar effects were observed for *Verticillium dahliae* where lack of *Set7*, the PRC2 methyl transferase, led to the induction of 839 genes of which 75% are within H3K27me3 domains in the wild type. Furthermore, many genes that are upregulated *in planta* are also located within these domains [316]. In the case of *N. crassa*, H3K27me3 marks are distributed throughout the genome but especially in the sub-telomeric regions where it was shown that a short DNA telomere repeat (i.e., (TTAGGG)₁₇) can trigger the establishment of large domains of H3K27me2/3 [317]. In *N. crassa* facultative heterochromatin covers around 7% of the genome containing 1000 silent genes [313]. In *Magnaporthe oryzae*, 50% of TEs and many plant infection-related genes, which are suppressed in axenic culture, are covered by H3K27me3 [318].

These examples show the versatile nature of gene regulation by H3K27me3 and H3K9me3 in different fungal genera which still needs more research that elucidates the mechanism and chronological order of the (de)-repression process.

Accumulating evidence in mammals [319] and also in fungi (e.g., *N. crassa* [317]) suggest that there exist DNA motifs that trigger specific histone modifications. In humans and mouse, over 350 of such motifs have been found and linked to different histone modifications such as H3K4me1, H3K4me2, H3K4me3, H3K27ac, H3K27me3, H3K9me3, H3K9ac, and H3K36me3. Genetic manipulations of these motifs were successful in reducing H3K27 acetylation at a chosen locus [319]. If this is also applicable to filamentous fungi, especially H3K27me3 and H3K9me3 it would be a promising approach for relieving heterochromatic structures around silent BGCs.

Table 6 lists various approaches that lead to the production of SMs by interfering with chromatin active enzymes (via chemicals or via molecular biology methods such as overexpression, deletion, or knockdown).

Table 6. Untargeted BGC activation by interference with global chromatin regulatory mechanisms. Ordered alphabetically by organism.

BGC Activation by Interference of Chromatin-Regulation			
Method	Organism	Observation	Ref.
HDACi DNMTi	162 mangrove endophytic Fungi	HDACi: sodium butyrate, DNMTi: 5-azacytidine Activity against ESKAPE MOs and <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> and <i>Leishmania donovani</i> : 254/ 1608 extracts showed bioactivity, HDACi or DNMTi: 72 fungi produced active extracts, 40 fungi were active only in the control	[320]
Media HDACi DNMTi	<i>Aspergillus awamori</i>	Media: MEA, rice, nutrient, triptone soya agar HDACi: valproic acid, nicotinamide, trichostatin A, DNMTi: 5-azacytidine Different metabolic profiles between media and epigenetic modifiers Nicotinamide was found to be the best epigenetic inducer Rice grains was the best medium for SM induction	[188]
HDACi DNMTi	<i>Aspergillus calidoustus</i> , <i>Aspergillus westerdijkae</i> <i>Aspergillus bombycis</i> <i>Aspergillus carbonarius</i> <i>Aspergillus fischeri</i>	HDACi: SAHA, DNMTi: 5-azacytidine significant changes in secondary metabolite profile with examples of both induction and repression.	[321]
HDACi DNMTi	<i>Aspergillus clavatus</i>	HDACi: valproic acid, trichostatin A, butyrate DNMTi: 5-azacytidine. N-acetyl-d-glucosamine Source of peptone strongly influences the SM profile, epigenetic modifier effects SM profile which is metabolite-specific and dependent on growth media and incubation time	[322]
Deletion	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	<i>cclAΔ</i> (Bre2; H3K4me): activation of mdp cluster: production of monodictyphenone, emodin, and emodin derivatives activation of anti-osteoporosis polyketides cluster: F9775A and F9775B	[323]
Deletion	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	HepA occupancy decreases during sterigmatocystin activation <i>hepAΔ/clrDΔ</i> (H3K9me): upregulation of sterigmatocystin, isopenicillin A, terraquinone A LaeA involved in reversing heterochromatic marks at ST BGC,	[305]
Deletion	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	<i>hosAΔ</i> (HDAC): impact on H4ac, SM, carbohydrate metabolism, virulence, defense	[324]
Knockdown	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	knockdown of <i>rpdA</i> (HDAC): production of aspercryptin A1 and A2 and fellutamides	[325,326]
HDACi	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	HDACi: SAHA, discovery of nygerone A	[327]

Table 6. Cont.

BGC Activation by Interference of Chromatin-Regulation			
Method	Organism	Observation	Ref.
Deletion	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>gcnEΔ</i> (SAGA/Ada; acetylation): activation of 12 silent clusters (1 novel compound): nigerpyrone, carbonarone A, pestalamide A, funalenone, aurasperone E, aurasperone A	[328]
HDACi DNMTi	<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	HDACi: suberohydroxamic acid, DNMTi: 5-azacytidine discovery of diphenylether-O-glycoside (diorcinol 3-O- α -D-ribofuranoside)	[329]
HDACi	<i>Botryosphaeria mamane</i>	HDACi: SAHA, Valporate, production of five unknown compounds	[330]
Deletion	<i>Calcarisporium arbuscula</i>	$\Delta hdaA$ (HDAC): upregulation of 75% of BGC genes: isolation of 10 new compounds	[331]
HDACi DNMTi	<i>Chalara</i> sp. 6661	HDACi: sodium butyrate, suberobishydroxamic acid, vorinostat; DNMTi: 5-azacytidine vorinostat: four new modified xanthenes, only one out of four inhibitors showed effect Biotransformation of vorinostat	[332]
Media HDACi DNMTi	<i>Cladosporium resinae</i>	Media: Czapek-DOX, YES, PDA, starch, liquid vs. solid; HDACi: SAHA; DNMTi: 5-AZA Czapek, yeast extract broth: more total secondary metabolites DNMTi and HDACi: expressions of silent genes	[209]
HDACi DNMTi	<i>Cyathus stercoreus</i>	nine previously undescribed sesquiterpenes	[333]
Deletion	<i>Dothistroma septosporum</i>	$\Delta DsKmt1$ (H3K9me) or $\Delta DsKmt6$ (H3K27me): Substantial decrease of H3K9me3 or H3K27me3. Increase of production of dothistromin in both cases	[334]
Media HDACi	<i>Drechslera</i> sp.,	HDACi: SAHA, valproate, octanoylhydroxamic acid; 2 new metabolites: chromanone and prenylhydroxybenzoic acid; different metabolome between MEA and minimal media biotransformation of the inhibitors	[208]
Deletion	<i>Epichloe festucae</i>	$\Delta clrD$ (H3K9me) and/or $\Delta ezhB$ (H3K27me): reduction of H3K9me3 and/or H3K27me3 activation of bioprotective lolitrems (ltm) and ergot alkaloids (eas)	[307]
Deletion	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	$\Delta hda1$ (<i>hdaA</i> ; HDAC): production of beauvericin (BEA-cluster; NRPS22)	[335]
Deletion	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	$\Delta set2$ and $\Delta ash1$ (H3K36me): upregulation of PKS-NRPS9 and NRPS4	[336]
Deletion	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	$\Delta set1$ (H3K4me): activation of PKSNRPS9, PKS type III, NRPS4, NRPS23, and DMATS3	[337]
Deletion	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	$\Delta kmt6$ (PRC2, H3K27me): Differential regulation of many SM genes, upregulation of: NRPS9, NRPS14, NRPS16, NRPS19, PKS2, PKS3, PKS13, PKS22, PKS28, PKS29, STC5	[312]

Table 6. Cont.

BGC Activation by Interference of Chromatin-Regulation			
Method	Organism	Observation	Ref.
Deletion	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i> (dereplication strain)	$\Delta kmt6$ (H3K27me): discovery of Protofusarin and N-ethyl anthranilic acid, N-phenethylacetamide, N-acetyltryptamine $\Delta kmt6$ and $\Delta fus1$: tricinolone, tricinolonic acid	[338]
Deletion	<i>Fusarium mangiferae</i>	$\Delta fmkmt1$ (H3K9me): increased beauvericin biosynthesis, nearly abolished fusapyrone production; revelation of fusapyrone BGC (FmPKS40)	[308]
Deletion	<i>Fusarium verticillioides</i>	$\Delta fvdim5$ (H3K9me): increase of fumonisin B1 and melanin biosynthesis, reduced virulence	[339]
Deletion	<i>Metarhizium robertsii</i>	$\Delta hat1$: activation of 11 orphan BGCs Meromuside A–I, Meromutides A and B	[340]
HDACi DNMTi	<i>Muscodor yucatanensis</i>	HDACi: SAHA, DNMTi: 5-azacytidine different morphology, cultural characteristics, metabolites	[341]
HDACi DNMTi	<i>Nigrospora sphaerica</i>	HDACi: SAHA, sodium butyrate, valproic acid, quercetin DNMTi: 5-azacytidine, hydralazine hydrochloride induction of cryptic metabolites by all modifiers used	[342]
HDACi	<i>Penicillium brevicompactum</i>	HDACi: nicotinamide, sodium butyrate total phenolic compounds increased drastically upon HDACi treatment Nicotinamide: p-anisic acid, p-anisic acid methyl ester, benzyl anisate, syringic acid, sinapic acid, acetosyringone, phenyl acetic acid, gentisaldehyde and p-hydroxy benzaldehyde Sodium butyrate enhanced the productivity of anthranilic acid and ergosterol peroxide	[343]
Deletion	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	$\Delta hdaA$ (HDAC): new compound. Maybe crosstalk with sorbicillinoids cluster	[344]
HDACi	<i>Phoma</i> sp.	SAHA triggers the production of (10'S)-verruculide B, vermistatin and dihydrovermistatin Absence of SAHA: discovery of (S,Z)-5-(3',A'-dihydroxybutyldiene)-3-propylfuran-2(5H)-one	[345]
HDACi	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	HDACi: sodium butyrate; diterpenoids changed into cyclonerane sesquiterpenoids. 3 new compounds: cleistanthane diterpenoid, harzianolic acid A, harziane diterpenoid, harzianone E, cyclonerane sesquiterpenoid, 3,7,11-trihydroxy-cycloneran	[346]
Knockdown	<i>Fusarium fujikuroi</i>	Knockdown of <i>KMT6</i> (H3K27me; PRC2): differential regulation of SM-clusters, upregulated SM genes: <i>NRPS22</i> , <i>STC4</i> , tetraterpene cyclase-encoding gene <i>TETC1</i> , <i>PKS-NRPS1</i> , <i>STC5</i> , <i>STC8</i> , <i>DMATS3</i> , <i>NRPS4</i> , <i>PKS2</i>) detection of six yet unidentified cluster-products: STC5: guaia-6,10(14)-diene, STC3: (+)-eremophilene	[55,315]

Abbreviations: HDACi (inhibition of histone deacetylases by chemical inhibitors), DNMTi (inhibition of DNA methyltransferases by chemical inhibitors), SAHA (vorinostat), 5-AZA (azacitidine).

5.2. Euchromatin

While heterochromatic regions suppress the transcription of underlying genes, euchromatin promotes gene expression. It is characterized by highly accessible DNA (i.e., low nucleosome density) and is often marked by histone acetylation and H3K4 trimethylation. Histone acetylation is regarded as an active mark and is established by histone acetyl transferases (HATs) [347]. Usually, they are part of protein complexes such as the Saga/Ada (HAT: GcnE) or the NuA4 complex (HAT: EsaA) [348]. Removal of acetylation marks is performed by histone deacetylases (HDACs) which often mediate transcriptional repression [324]. Some of these HDACs were shown to act on the genome-wide level and are involved in developmental and metabolic processes (e.g., HosA in *A. flavus* [349], HosB and HstA in *A. nidulans* [350]) while others are active in specific regions (i.e., Sir2 in *Candida albicans* in subtelomeric regions [351], HdaA regulates two telomere proximal but not distal clusters in *A. nidulans* [350]). These findings suggest that some HDACs have a location or even cluster-specific activity. Demethylation by HDACs can be inhibited by HDAC inhibitors. Because these chemicals often inactivate multiple HDACs simultaneously, their application results in a genome-wide increase in acetylation and de-regulation of thousands of genes [352]. For references concerning the inhibition or deletion of HDACs for activation of silent BGCs please consult Table 6.

5.2.1. Methylation of Histone 3 Lysin 4

H3K4me1/2/3 is probably one of the most discussed and controversial histone modifications in terms of gene transcription and activation. It is established by the COMPASS complex with Set1 as the catalytic subunit [353]. H3K4me3 is reversed by lysine demethylases such as KdmB in *A. nidulans* [354,355] or Kdm5 in *F. graminearum* [355]. This modification was initially thought to have a transcriptionally promoting character. Recent studies in mice, however, suggest that H3K4me3 is not necessary for transcription but instead prevents silencing of the region by PRC2 or DNA methylation [356]. This would explain several contradictory observations such as the underrepresentation of H3K4me3 in active clusters in several fungal species such as *A. nidulans* [354], *F. fujikuroi* [125] and *F. graminearum* [312] or the partial upregulation of BGCs after abolished H3K4me3 due to deletion of subunits of the COMPASS complex (e.g., *cclA*, *sppA*, *setA*). This was observed in many species such as *A. nidulans* (monodictyphenone, desacetylaustin, dehydroaustinol, citreorosein, emodic acid, 2-OH, 2-aminoemodin, emodin, and the polyketides F9775A and F9775B) [357,358], *A. fumigatus* (gliotoxin) [359], *F. fujikuroi* (BIK, FUS) [360], *F. graminearum* (ZON, fusarins) [360]. But also downregulation of BGCs in *A. nidulans* (Penicillin G, Sterigmatocystin) [355], *F. fujikuroi* (gibberellic acid) [360] and *F. graminearum* (deoxynivalenol) [360] was observed in these mutants. Further puzzling results came from knockout experiments of the H3K4 demethylase (i.e., *kdmB*) in *A. nidulans* by our laboratory. It led to a 20% increase of global H3K4me3 but 90% of all annotated genes that are connected to secondary metabolism were downregulated. Sterigmatocystin and orsellinic acid biosynthesis were reduced while products of the monodictyphenone pathway were increased (i.e., 2, ω -dihydroxyemodin, ω -hydroxyemodin, 2-hydroxyemodin, emodin) [354]. Following this observation, the role of KdmB as inducer of SM clusters goes beyond its function as H3K4me3 demethylase and several indirect effects on general SM regulators may account for the observed phenotype of *kdmB* deletion or overexpression. For example, one could assume that, due to the downregulation of the majority of secondary metabolism genes, the precursor pool may have been increased which may have led to a better turnover by the same amounts of enzymes from the mdp pathway, resulting in higher quantities of mdp-related metabolites [354]. Similar results were found in *F. fujikuroi* [337] and *F. graminearum* [355] but most interestingly, in the case of Kdm5 in *F. graminearum*, we found that many SMs are regulated by Kdm5 in a demethylase-independent role (regulation by a catalytically inactive variant of Kdm5) [355].

Taken together, results that try to link H3K4me3 and active transcription often result in complex and sometimes contradictory results. The role of H3K4me3 as protection

against silencing would explain why this mark often but not always is correlated with transcriptional activation. Further insight into the local role of H3K4 trimethylation would be important to evaluate its role in the induction and transcription of silent BGCs.

5.2.2. H4K12 Acetylation

In *A. nidulans*, the H4K12 acetyltransferase EsaA is essential for viability and also involved in the up-regulation of three of four examined BGCs. EsaA overexpression led to depletion of the H4 nucleosome at investigated loci and increased expression levels of BGCs. In the case of the cryptic *ORS* cluster, increased acetylation and nucleosome depletion occurred, but the BGC was not activated. It was suggested by the authors that EsaA and H4K12 acetylation could be responsible for histone depletion at promoter regions so that other effectors such as TFs can access the locus and recruit the transcriptional machinery [361].

Similar findings were published by Roze et al. in *A. parasiticus* where they detected an increase of overall H4 acetylation in the aflatoxin BGC promoters followed by *aflR* binding and transcription [362].

5.2.3. H3K9 Acetylation/H3K14 Acetylation

H3K9 acetylation, which is the mark counteracting silencing by H3K9me₃, is enriched in transcriptionally active promoters, sometimes enriched especially in BGCs. In *F. fujikuroi* it was seen that the overall correlation between genome-wide H3K9ac and transcription is weak but that in the case of BGCs the correlation is very strong, suggesting that H3K9ac has important roles in the production of SMs [125]. In the case of the fusarin C BGC, H3K9 acetylation was significantly enriched across the whole BGC when grown under inducing conditions [363]. Another study showed that deletion of the histone deacetylase FfHda1 in *F. fujikuroi* also results in increased levels of H3K9ac in gene promoters and increased transcriptional activity. This even resulted in the activation of the bikaverin cluster under repressive conditions [364].

The most intensively studied HAT GcnE, which is part of the SAGA/Ada complex, was shown to be responsible for the acetylation of H3K9 and H3K14 in *A. nidulans*, and additionally H3K18 and H3K27 in *F. graminearum* [365] and H3K4, H3K9, H3K18 and H3K27 in *F. fujikuroi* [366]. In the case of several BGCs in *A. nidulans* (orsellinic acid, sterigmatocystin, penicillin, terrequinone) GcnE is necessary for activation. While H3K14 acetylation was not enriched within clusters, H3K9 acetylation was only applied in BGCs (only sterigmatocystin and *ORS* clusters were examined for H3K9ac). While genes outside the cluster showed no signs of differential expression, all BGCs that were expressed in the wild type showed abolished transcription in the *gcnE* deletion mutant [367,368]. The acetylation pattern around active genes showed a strong correlation between the increase of H3K9ac around the TSS and transcription while in the case of H3K14ac, the correlation was rather weak. Upon acetylation, the H3 density around the TSS was reduced which suggests that at least one of these marks could be involved in nucleosome depletion around the TSS [367].

Recently the fungal-specific HAT Rtt109, which is responsible for H3K9 and/ or H3K56 acetylation (DNA damage repair), was described in *A. flavus*, *Beauveria bassiana* and *F. graminearum* [369]. Deletion in *A. flavus* led to the removal of both H3K9 and H3K56 acetylation which resulted in impaired growth and virulence, vulnerability to DNA damage stress and also to the abolished expression of genes of the aflatoxin cluster, further promoting H3K9 acetylation as an important mark for gene transcription [370].

5.2.4. H3K27 Acetylation

H3K27 acetylation is the counteracting mark of the silencing H3K27me₃ modification. During chromatin accessibility studies in *Neurospora crassa*, it was found that H3K27 acetylation is one of the most predictive histone marks of open chromatin [371]. As already mentioned it was shown in *F. fujikuroi* [335] and *M. oryzae* [318] that H3K27ac spreads to

regions previously marked by H3K27me3 if components of the PRC2 complex are deleted. This often resulted in transcriptional activation. Loss of H3K27ac on the other hand did not result in transcriptional inactivation. This suggests that H3K27ac is not necessary for active transcription but plays a role in gene activation/accessibility of previously silenced genes. It seems that H3K27 acetylation by the SAGA complex (i.e., GcnE) is one of the mechanisms that can revert silencing by the PRC2 machinery. The exchange mechanism itself and the involvement of other histone acetylations (by GcnE) in the transcriptional activation is however not fully understood yet.

5.3. The Histone Code of Actively Transcribed Genes

Actively transcribed genes have a distinct chromatin signature around the promoter region, gene body, and terminator. We assessed the histone mark occupation around the start codon in all active genes of Chromosome IV of *A. nidulans*. H3K9/K14 acetylation is enriched in the promoter with the highest level at the first nucleosome after the translation start site. H3K4me3 is enriched at the first three nucleosomes downstream of the ATG and H3K36me3 spreads across the active gene body. While H3K4me3 and H3K9/K14Ac decreased towards the 3' of the gene, H3K36me3 increased [354]. Similar findings were published in *V. dahliae* [316] and *Candida albicans* [351]. Furthermore, it was found that transcriptional active genes correlate positively with increased acetylation within the promoter region in *Aspergillus parasiticus* [362]. Noteworthy, in human cells, artificial application of H3K27 acetylation in the promoter region led to subsequent H3K4me3 and transcription while the deployment of H3K4me3 did not result in increased acetylation or transcription [372].

5.4. Finding New Bioactive Compounds by Breaking the Chromatin Silencing Machinery

The production of SMs is a metabolically costly process requiring high energy input to produce the necessary reduction equivalents (NADPH) and ATP. Therefore, their biosynthesis is strictly economized. To ensure that energy is not wasted, fungi by default silence their BGCs at the level of heterochromatin formation, making these genomic regions inaccessible to the transcriptional machinery [305,315,348]. As soon as environmental or developmental conditions demand the production of a certain beneficial SM, the chromatin-based silencing is lifted and specific activation factors start the expression of BGC genes. Experimental setups that aim for induction of fungal BGCs via chromatin modifications either delete, inhibit or overexpress chromatin active enzymes. Most common approaches in this regard are the genetic or chemical inhibition of HDACs [324,331,335,344] or inactivation of components of the silencing machinery via PRC2 [307,312,334,338] or components related to heterochromatin formation via H3K9me (e.g., Dim5/Kmt1/ClrD/HP1, . . .) [305,307,308,334,339].

One particular successful and easy-to-apply strategy for artificial lifting heterochromatin based silencing was the application of chemical inhibitors for HDACs that are known to be essential for most heterochromatin formation complexes. HDAC inhibitors (HDACi) lead to higher acetylation of histones, a driver for gene expression. The most rewarding results following this strategy used SAHA, butyric acid, valproic acid, nicotinamide, and trichostatin as additives to the growth medium [188,342]. A similar approach that often is applied together with HDACi aims for the inhibition of DNA-methyltransferases (DNMTs). DNA methylation in fungi is mostly connected to the silencing of transposable and repetitive elements [373]. Inhibition or deletion of HDACs or DNMTs resulted in the discovery of nygerone A in *A. niger* [119], or the production of diorcinol 3-O- α -D-ribofuranoside in a marine-derived isolate from *Aspergillus* sp. [130] or in the induction of many silent BGCs during a screen of 162 mangrove endophytic fungi of which 72 produced bioactive substances [137]. Table 6 lists publications that used the genetic or chemical interference of chromatin remodelers for the induction of silent BGCs.

There are however downsides to strategies that interfere with globally active regulators. While approaches that mimic environmental conditions result in a native regulatory response of BGCs, the disruption of global regulatory mechanisms can lead to the syn-

thesis of cryptic compounds that emerge due to uncoordinated regulation of genes or by bio-transformation of the inhibitors [332,344,374]. Additionally, chemical or genetic manipulation of globally active chromatin remodelers can be lethal [315] or lead to phenotypically aberrant transformants (i.e., growth, morphology, conidiation, . . .) [308,339,375–377]. All these factors can result in a substantial change of the whole metabolome [321,346] and transcriptome [326,351] which makes interpretation challenging, even with software solutions that assist with the detection of degradation products or bio-transformed moieties such as BioTransformer [378].

In recent years, however, CRISPR/Cas technology advanced to a point where new options for targeted local chromatin modifications are available and some have already been established in fungal species.

6. CRISPR/Cas: New Opportunities in Molecular Biology: Targeted Gene Deletion, Activation and Epigenetic Editing in Filamentous Fungi

CRISPR/Cas is a fast-advancing technology in molecular biology that is nowadays deployed in many prokaryotes and eukaryotes, illustrated by around 25,000 publications connected to “CRISPR” over the last 5 years. Its fast development in terms of genome editing but also in epigenome editing and as a tool for transcriptional activation makes it a very promising option for future application. Although CRISPR/Cas technology is widely used for gene manipulation, approaches for gene and BGC activation are just recently gaining attention in filamentous fungi. In the next section, we shortly introduce the principle of CRISPR/CAS technology and different classes and types that are available before moving to approaches that are applied in filamentous fungi and future perspectives of gene activation (i.e., CRISPRa) applications.

6.1. Principle of CRISPR-Cas Technology

The best-known variant of CRISPR/Cas systems is the RNA-guided nuclease Cas9 from *Streptococcus pyogenes*, SpCas9. CRISPR/Cas is the major component of the acquired bacterial or archaeal immune system [379]. It is a nuclease that inactivates foreign DNA by causing double-strand breaks at specific DNA-loci via previously acquired guide sequences.

The native lifecycle of the CRISPR/Cas adaptive immunity consists of three stages. Adaption, expression, and interference [380]. Upon initial infection, invading (e.g., phage) DNA is digested by Cas proteins that recognize foreign DNA by a nucleotide sequence that does not occur in the host genome. The so-called protospacer adjacent motif or PAM. Each CRISPR/Cas system has a distinct PAM sequence. A short stretch of the DNA (i.e., protospacer) is then cleaved out and inserted into a DNA locus called CRISPR-array. In the expression phase, the whole CRISPR array with all protospacers is transcribed (i.e., pre-CRISPR RNA or pre-crRNA) and processed into mature CRISPR RNAs (i.e., crRNA). Different CRISPR/Cas variants have different procedures during this phase, either demanding a complex interplay of many Cas proteins or requiring only one multi-domain protein [380]. During the interference stage, the mature crRNA or guide RNA is used as a reference pattern for the Cas nucleases to inactivate invading non-host DNAs by inducing double-strand breaks at loci that match the crRNA sequence and possess a PAM motif [380].

After the discovery of CRISPR/Cas, its potential instantly attracted the interest of the scientific community. Many research groups refined this strategy over the past years to one of the most versatile tools used in modern molecular biology that has now been established in many eukaryotic organisms, including filamentous fungi [381,382]. New variants of the CRISPR/Cas from different bacterial sources or engineered forms evolve(d). Some are only capable of nicking the DNA or even are incapable of modifying the DNA at all (nuclease-dead Cas9, dCas9). By fusing these variants with proteins of versatile functionality, researchers created a multitude of effector proteins that can be targeted precisely throughout the genome. This opened many new possibilities for addressing research questions that go beyond genome editing, such as CRISPR/Cas mediated chromatin modification [252], gene

activation (CRISPRa) [251,253,271,383] or transcriptional interference (CRISPRi) [384,385] and locus-specific protein proximity labelling (CasID or BioID) [386].

6.2. Differences between CRISPR/Cas Variants

Following Cas9, different variants of CRISPR-Cas systems have been found in nature as reviewed in detail by [380]. They are divided into two classes which differ in their complexity. While class I CRISPR/Cas systems utilize many proteins for each phase of the natural defense (adaption, expression, interference), class II CRISPR/Cas systems only use 2–3 proteins during adaption and only 1 (Type V (i.e., Cas12a) and VI) or two (Type II (i.e., Cas9)) proteins during expression and interference. The simplicity of Class II systems makes them the prevalent choice for CRISPR/Cas applications in molecular biology. Depending on the type of Cas variant, they can either target RNA molecules (Type VI) or DNA (Type II and V) molecules [381]. Within Class II especially *SpCas9* from *Streptococcus pyrogenes* or *Cas12a* (i.e., Cpf1) from *Francisella novicida*, *Acidaminococcus* sp. or *Lachnospiraceae bacterium* (i.e., FnCas12a, AsCas12a, LbCas12a) are being deployed for molecular biology in fungi. They have important differences that make both of them viable options, depending on the application [381].

Easier handling and cloning with Cas12a due to different gRNA processing. Cas9 needs the matured form of the tracrRNA and the crRNA which, in nature, anneal to produce a functional guide RNA that can then build a complex with the Cas9 protein. Genetic engineering-led, however, to the development of both crRNA and tracrRNA in one single guide RNA (sgRNA) which increased the handling comfort and efficiency [387]. Nevertheless, for the proper maturation of the sgRNA, it has to be ensured that only the sgRNA without any additional nucleotides is released from the transcript which is currently accomplished by either ribozymes [388] or tRNAs [389] that flank the sgRNA. The sgRNA maturation via ribozymes uses an RNA polymerase II promoter and terminator together with the Hammerhead and HDV ribozymes to release the mature sgRNA [388]. Nødvig and co-workers took this idea even further and developed a system capable of multiplexing sgRNAs utilizing the endogenous tRNA processing machinery. It consists of a cassette that uses an RNA polymerase III promoter to express sgRNAs which are flanked by tRNAs. This then results in the release of mature sgRNAs by tRNA-specific RNase P and RNase Z enzymes [389] (Figure 3a). This made it possible to express multiple sgRNAs at the same time thereby increasing editing efficiency by application of several gRNAs at the same locus which in turn allows for multiple gene editing. However, the genetic scaffold that is required for proper processing and release of multiple mature sgRNAs makes the cloning and transformation process of Cas9 multiplexing systems a challenging and labor-intensive endeavour in filamentous fungi. In the case of the ribozyme approach, the repetitive expression scaffold for one gRNA sequence is around 185 nt-long [388] and in the case of the tRNA-assisted approach, it spans even around 222 nts (containing 2x identical glycine tRNA) [389] (Figure 3a).

In stark contrast to Cas9, Cas12a can directly process the U6 promoter-driven CRISPR array into the mature guide RNAs which only consists of a 19 nt-long direct repeat (DR) and a 23–25 nt-long protospacer sequence (PS) (i.e., U6-DR-PS-DR-PS-DR-PS-, etc.) (Figure 3b). This greatly facilitates the cloning and application of single and multiple sgRNAs with Cas12a [390–393].

The DNA cleavage pattern is different between Cas9 and Cas12a. While *SpCas9* produces a blunt end cut 3 bps upstream of the NGG PAM [387], Cas12a variant FnCas12a cleaves after the 23rd base on the targeted strand at the 18th base of the non-targeted strand which results in staggering cleavage sites distant from the PAM [394]. In the case of Cas9, the cleavage is mediated by two nuclease domains (HNH and RuvC) [395], while Cas12a only has one RuvC domain for the cleavage of both strands [394].

The PAM sequence of Cas9 is the short 3 nucleotide long G-rich motif NGG while Cas12a has a T-rich PAM (AsCas12a and LbCas12a: 5'-TTTN-3' [381] or 5'-TTTV-3' [396]; FnCas12a: 5'-TTN-3' [394]). Other PAMs are possible, depending on the origin of Cas12a [397].

There are also engineered variants that accept a broader range of PAMs which will be described in Section 6.5. The PAM greatly limits the loci that can be targeted because, without a present PAM, neither annealing nor cutting occurs properly.

Figure 3. Maturation of guide RNAs and Cas mediated Gene editing. (a) Methods for release of mature sgRNAs with Cas9. **Top:** the ~100 bp long sgRNA is flanked by the 37 bp Hammerhead (HH) and the 68 bp HDV ribozyme. Upon transcription by RNA polymerase II (RNA POL II), the sgRNA is released by the formation of secondary structure and autocleavage of the ribozymes. **Bottom:** Cas9 sgRNAs can be matured and released by flanking it by ~72 bp long tRNAs (i.e., glycine). Upon transcription by RNA polymerase III (RNA POL III), the tRNAs are cleaved by the endogenous RNase P and RNase Z and the mature sgRNA is released which then can form a functional complex with Cas9. Arrays of sgRNA and tRNAs can be cloned and expressed in vivo for multiplexing purposes. (b) Cas12a can process the CRISPR transcript itself. The expression fragment contains an only ~19 bp direct repeat followed by the approximately 25 bp long protospacer sequence. Due to its small size, it is easy to clone several guide RNAs in sequence for multiplexing purposes. After expression by RNA polymerase III (RNA POL III), the transcript is processed by Cas12a and the mature sgRNAs are released which can form a functional complex with Cas12a. (c) two options for gene editing with CRISPR/Cas technology. After the successful introduction of the double-strand break, the DNA can either be repaired via the non-homologous end joining pathway (NHEJ) or, if an oligo or gene with complementary regions (orange) is provided (i.e., HDR Substrate), the homology directed repair mechanism can be activated (HDR) and the provided genetic material is introduced into the target locus.

Genetic engineering led to the development of catalytically inactive (i.e., dead or dCas) and nicking CRISPR/Cas tools. Cas9 proteins that can only nick the DNA (i.e., nCas9) [398] resulted in improved single base editing efficacy [399]. There are also mutant versions of Cas12a proteins although they are not yet capable of perfect nicks as they still retain some of the catalytic activity for the second strand. Merely the ratio of single and double-strand breaks is shifted in favor of the nicks [400,401]. In contrast to Cas9, Cas12a

only has one catalytic domain that cleaves both strands which makes the engineering of nCas12a variants more complicated.

The development of catalytically inactive Cas9 and later Cas12a variants (i.e., dead or dCas9 and dCas12a) made CRISPR/Cas to a very powerful tool in molecular biology [400,402]. dCas proteins can be used as guidance vessels for attached proteins or protein domains. This way, CRISPR/Cas can be deployed for a multitude of applications, involving basically any protein that can be functionally fused to the N and/or C-terminal or even as a mediator of transcriptional interference (CRISPRi) by the sterical hindrance of the transcriptional machinery within a gene body or at the transcriptional start site [403].

Although SpCas9 is currently the prevalent choice for gene editing and other applications, the Cas12a system has many benefits for working with filamentous fungi. The biggest advantage with regard to BGC activation is the easy deployment of multiple gRNAs as compared to SpCas9. While Cas12a can process the raw pre-crRNA transcript directly, Cas9 needs more complex cloning strategies involving features that allow for a proper release of blunt end sgRNAs (e.g., ribozymes or tRNA scaffolds). Cas12a is, therefore, much easier to handle which not only makes experiments more time efficient but also more robust as the system requires fewer components.

The second advantage for work with filamentous fungi specifically is the temperature maximum. Most filamentous fungi grow well around room temperature. SpCas9 has its catalytic maximum at 32 °C which can be challenging for some fungi. Cas12a, on the other hand, can be deployed at lower temperatures (i.e., 28 °C) which increases the efficiency in most fungal strains [404].

One of the drawbacks of the CRISPR/Cas system is the requirement of the PAM motif at the target locus. The difference in PAM sequences in different variants increases the versatility and flexibility in this matter which can be very important for experiments that require specific loci, with limited PAM options, to be targeted.

6.3. Gene Editing via CRISPR/Cas

Various approaches that involve CRISPR/Cas technology have been already applied to different fungal species [395]. Especially in fungal species where site-directed mutagenesis and gene editing rates by conventional methods are very low, CRISPR/Cas is a promising option [405,406].

To increase the editing efficiency by utilizing homologous DNA repair pathways, linear or circular double-stranded DNA with homologous regions or single-stranded DNA oligos with small homologous regions can be transformed together with the Cas construct. These then can get inserted at the Cas9 restriction site after cleavage which not only can increase the mutation rate but makes it also possible not only to mutate, but exchange the DNA sequence via homology-directed repair mechanisms (Figure 3c) [389,407].

The transformation of the CRISPR/Cas machinery and the guide RNA(s) can be performed on a single [388] or multiple plasmids [251], episomal plasmids by utilization of the AMA1 region of *A. nidulans* [388,389], by random integration into the genome [408] or within a specific genomic locus [251]. We recently also developed an inducible CRISPR/Cas variant in filamentous fungi that uses the human estrogen receptor [251,409]. Other variants utilize the Tet-ON system for induction [410].

If the fungus is not amenable to stable or transient genomic transformations, mutation by CRISPR/Cas systems can also be achieved by transformation of the in vitro pre-assembled (i.e., sgRNA and Cas-protein) ribonucleotide complex (RNP) [407,411,412]. For more information about CRISPR/CAS applications in fungi, please consult the recent review by Schuster and Kahmann [413].

6.4. Gene and BGC Activation via CRISPR/dCAS Variants

Catalytically inactive Cas variants (i.e., dCas9, dCas12a) have great potential to be used for the activation of silent BGCs. When fused to a trans-activator domain it can be deployed as a programmable TF for the activation of one or multiple genes (via sgRNA

multiplexing; Figure 3a,b) [251,253]. Another potent approach is the fusion of a chromatin remodeler (domain) which would provide the possibility to change histone modifications in a targeted and locus-specific manner [252]. This way, BGCs that are buried within heterochromatin could be made accessible by replacing the silencing marks (i.e., H3K9me3, H3K27me3) with active marks (i.e., acetylation). Figure 4 illustrates both dCas-mediated approaches for the activation of silent BGCs.

Figure 4. Targeted gene activation approaches via CRISPR/Cas technology. (a) targeted chromatin remodeling via a chromatin active domain (CAD). DNA is depicted in dotted black lines, nucleosomes

are cyan, heterochromatic histone modifications are grey pins while euchromatic histone modifications are green pins. A fusion protein of dCas and a CAD is targeted into a nucleosome-free region (NFR) in a heterochromatic area where it modifies the local histones. This leads to an increase in DNA accessibility and promotes transcription. **(b)** Targeted gene activation by dCas fused to a trans-activating domain (TAD; e.g., VPR). DNA is depicted as a black bar, genes are either grey (inactive) or green (active) arrows. The colored bars in front of the genes are target sites for dCas-TAD (i.e., protospacer sequence). dCas-TAD is sent into accessible promoter regions of target genes. The TAD recruits components of the transcriptional machinery which leads to the transcription of the target gene. By using multiple guide RNAs, several genes/promoters can be targeted simultaneously.

6.4.1. Transcriptional Regulation

The fusion of a trans-activator or trans-activating domain and a dCas protein transforms it into a programmable transcription factor that can be sent to any spot within the genome (as long as an appropriate PAM is present). This CRISPRa method was established simultaneously in the filamentous fungi *Aspergillus nidulans* for dCas9 [251] and dCas12a [253] and shortly after also in *P. rubens* [271]. In every case, the trans-activator VPR [414] was chosen as it was shown to be more effective than other known trans-activator domains. It is a tripartite activator with protein domains that were shown to interact with parts of the transcriptional machinery and also the histone acetylase complex SAGA [415]. The hybrid trans-activator consists of four copies of the VP16 domain of the Herpes simplex virus, the p65 domain of the human activator NF- κ B and the Rta domain of the Epstein-Barr virus TF. These publications tackle multiple challenges when it comes to BGC activation. Roux et al. successfully deployed dCas12a-VPR in an episomal and stable approach. They showed that the activation of a BGC can be achieved by upregulation of the pathway-specific TF but also by using guide RNA multiplexing to upregulate all genes of a BGC [253]. Simultaneously, we published a nucleosome positioning map of the genome of *A. nidulans* which was used to target VPR-dCas9 into nucleosome-free regions within the promoter [251]. This facilitates the binding of VPR-dCas9 as it was shown that steric hindrances such as nucleosomes or other proteins can prevent the annealing of (d)Cas proteins to their target [416]. Furthermore, we deployed an inducible version of VPR-dCas9 to precisely time the activation process because some metabolites could be toxic to the host and therefore interfere with the morphology and (chemical) phenotype of the fungus if the BGC product is synthesized constitutively [251].

6.4.2. Targeted Chromatin Remodelling Using CRISPR/Cas

Targeted locus-specific deposition of histone marks via fusion proteins of dCas and chromatin active domains is an emerging field in molecular biology. In human cancer cells, targeted modification of H3K9me3 and H3K27ac can be accomplished by deploying a fusion protein composed of dCas9 and the H3K9 methyl-transferase KRAB (i.e., Krüppel-associated box repressor) or the histone acetyl transferase p300, respectively. In both cases, the targeting of the fusion proteins to DNA accessible sites (e.g., nucleosome-free regions, NFRs) led to the respective modification at the locus (i.e., H3K9me3 and H3K27ac). In the case of H3K9me3, it was even shown that the DNA is inaccessible after the histone mark H3K9me3 is deployed [417,418].

In fungi, gene activation and repression by targeting chromatin active domains via CRISPR/Cas to target loci were accomplished in *A. niger*, although the actual effect on chromatin status (i.e., histone modifications) has not been assessed [252]. Li et al. hereby targeted the human acetyl transferase p300 to the promoter region of the HR-PKS-encoding gene *FUM1* and managed to activate the fumonisin cluster in *A. niger*. Furthermore, they fused endogenous proteins such as GcnE, the acetyltransferase of the SAGA complex, histone deacetylases HosA and RpdA, and the H3K9 demethylase Lde to dCas9 separately and tested its effect on the SM gene *breF*. While the fusion of the catalytic core of human p300 fused to dCas9 led to an activation of the target gene as expected, fusion proteins of dCas9 and GcnE, RpdA and HosA resulted in repression of the gene while no difference

was seen with the dCas9-Lde fusion protein. While most of the results are as expected, the repression effect by dCas9-GcnE is interesting. Although the authors state that the repression of *breF* by dCas9-GcnE is expected as GcnE was shown to be a negative regulator of 12 PKSs in *A. niger*, the result is surprising to us. Upregulation of BGCs due to the deletion of a broad domain regulator-encoding gene such as *gcnE* could be due to many indirect effects, for instance if GcnE was the activator of a repressor of these BGCs. Targeting the acetyltransferase to a specific genomic location, however, should lead to higher levels of acetylation only at the specific location and, therefore, to upregulation of only the targeted gene.

In the case of the dCas9-HosA, activation of the pigmentation gene *fwnA* was observed. Again, this is theoretically consistent with literature where *fwnA* expression decreased in *hosA* deletion strains. Such as with GcnE however, comparing a local effect (i.e., deacetylation of the promoter region) with a genome-wide effect (i.e., deletion of broad domain regulator such as HosA) does not take indirect regulatory effects into account. Unfortunately, histone modifications of the targeted loci were not analyzed, so it is not clear if really a change in histone modifications is responsible for the observations. Furthermore, there could also be the possibility of host-mediated recruitment of the endogenous fusion protein (i.e., HosA, RpdA, GncE, Lde) which could interfere with the experimental setup. Using only the catalytic domain (of homologs) would be a way of circumventing this.

Histone phosphorylation is another mechanism for gene induction that is prevalent in stress response gene promoters. A fusion of dCas9 and a hyperactive variant of the human histone kinase MSK1 (i.e., dMSK1) could be targeted to promoters for gene activation by phosphorylation of H3S28 and H3S10 [419]. Here, several (also non-stress response) genes were activated by targeting the promoter. When gene activation was successful, an increase in H3S10ph, H3S28ph, and H4K27ac was found. In cases where H3S10ph but not H3S28ph occurred, neither H4K27ac nor gene activation was observed. This was, however, not yet tested in fungal organisms.

In summary, the targeted deployment of histone modifications as a regulator of transcription is an emerging field in fungal research but experimental data is currently scarce. More research is needed to fully assess this strategy for the activation of silent BGCs. If successful, CRISPR/Cas-based targeted deployment of chromatin active domains will not only result in the discovery of many natural products but will also provide a lot of information about transcription and the local chromatin context.

6.5. Application Relevant Information for CRISPR/Cas-Methods

Next, we want to summarize insights regarding the deployment of CRISPR/Cas methods. This is aimed at helping with the experimental planning. It will focus on the two main CAS systems that have been used for fungal research, Cas9, and Cas12a.

Cas and dCas approaches have different prerequisites in regard to the target site, residence time and off-targets. When using CRISPR/Cas for gene-editing purposes, the successful outcome depends on a one-time event (the cleavage of DNA). In the case of CRISPRa or CRISPRi however the effect is determined by a continuous interaction of the fusion complex with the proteome or DNA at the target locus [420,421]. Concluding, a sgRNA that proved to elicit DNA mutations via CRISPR/Cas might not be of use for experiments where a long residence time is essential (e.g., CRISPRa).

Off-target annealing also has different consequences depending on the application. Cas proteins can anneal to off-target sites but as long as the sgRNA does not match appropriately, no cut will occur. In the case of dCas approaches, however, this could theoretically lead to off-target effects mediated by the active domain that is fused to the dCas protein.

There are several tools that design gRNAs for different (d)Cas systems based on one or several of the following features: sequence composition, chromatin accessibility, gene expression, nucleotide position, RNA secondary structure, melting temperature, free energy, off-target possibility, and more [422]. Some of them also feature different applica-

tion types such as DNA cleavage, CRISPRi and CRISPRa. This is important because the sgRNA/crRNA design for mutational Cas approaches is different from those for CRISPRa approaches because they target the gene body and not promoter regions [423]. Most of them are biased towards one or more organisms (mostly mammalian) or applications (e.g., mutational vs. CRISPRa). Some tools such as Cas-Designer (Cas9) [424] feature a broad spectrum of genomes that are continuously updated (also by user request). CASPER (Cas9 and Cas12a) is not biased towards an organism and was specifically designed for genome editing in non-model organisms [425]. Guide RNA design tools for non-model organism often calculate the gRNA efficiency based only on sequence features which can lead to reduced sgRNA performance if other, unconsidered parameters, such as nucleosome occupancy, prevents target site accessibility.

In the case of CRISPRa approaches, the location of deployment within the promoter (in plants) was shown to have a distinctly different effect on the activation of the target gene even if the sgRNAs were only as little as 50 base-pairs apart from each other [426]. For more detailed information, read the following recent reviews which describe available prediction tools and guide RNA optimization [422,427].

Cas efficiency depends on multiple factors including Cas-sgRNA complex formation and concentration, target site accessibility, residence time, and codon optimization. By codon optimization alone, Cas efficiency could be increased from 35 to 70% [428].

Cas stabilizes the sgRNA, but the complex formation can be hindered by other RNAs and some divalent ions. To be functional, the Cas protein and the sgRNA/crRNA have to form a complex. Unbound sgRNAs get degraded very quickly. Upon complex formation, the Cas9 protein stabilizes the sgRNA, undergoes conformational changes, and is released from the inactive apo-state [429,430]. Random RNA molecules that are present in the cell also can bind unspecific to Cas9 and compete with sgRNAs which delays or prevents complex formation [431]. After complex formation however, unspecific RNAs have no significant impact on the ribonucleotide stability anymore [429]. It is therefore important to express the sgRNA/crRNA at high levels so that the Cas protein has a high chance of collision before another RNA molecule can interfere or the sgRNA/crRNA is degraded [429]. The following publications give in-depth information about Cas9 [432] and Cas12a [433] kinetics.

It also is important to note that in the apo-state Cas9 can bind DNA in a non-specific manner while the protein remains catalytically inactive, so no unguided "rogue"-activity is happening under normal conditions [430]. It was, however, shown that the presence of Mn^{2+} or Co^{2+} ions can lead to unspecific DNA cleavage even without bound crRNA (Cas12a) or sgRNA (Cas9), respectively, which makes media composition potentially also an important brick in the wall of CRISPR/Cas applications [434]. Processing of the pre-crRNA by Cas12a variants does not seem to be Mg^{2+} -dependent but it was shown that in the case of LbCas12a and FnCas12a, affinity to the crRNA is dependent on Mg^{2+} ions which were found to be coordinated in the RNP complex [435,436]. It can be concluded that divalent ions can have a significant impact on Cas activity and specificity which should be kept in mind when deciding on culture conditions.

The determinants of the residence time of Cas at its target locus are the proper pairing with the PAM, the subsequent annealing to the seed region, the local proteome and its fluctuations (i.e., accessibility and dislocation), and the concentration of Cas-sgRNA complex [421]. The impact of mutations on the annealing, residence time and cleavage efficiency also follow this order (PAM > seed sequence > PAM-distal sgRNA sequence (=5'-end)) with the proteomic occupancy around the target locus having a varying influence [429,437]. The residence time is significantly shorter the less complementary the annealing sequence is which was shown in human cell lines where residence times of less than two minutes to up to more than three hours have been observed [429].

The proteome of the target site can prevent binding of Cas-sgRNA complex or even dislodge bound Cas. In vitro experiments confirmed that cleavage by Cas9 is nearly abolished when targeted to DNA occupied by nucleosomes. At the edges of nucleosomes or

within linker regions, however, cleavage was largely unaffected. Interestingly, the position of the PAM was the essential determinant of cleavage efficiency when sequences close to the border of a nucleosome were targeted. This was verified *in vitro* by designing two nearly perfectly overlapping sgRNAs (shifted by four nts) but with opposite orientations. The sgRNA that had the PAM located proximal to the nucleosome showed drastically reduced cleavage efficiency compared to the sgRNA that had the PAM located distal [416]. This observation was also confirmed *in vivo* in human cell lines [438–440]. The magnitude of this effect is, however, also dependent on the strength of the interaction between nucleosome and DNA. Upon comparing two different DNA sequences that are known to have different affinities to nucleosomes, it was shown that breathing chromatin structures (fluctuations of DNA occupancy of the nucleosome) show a much higher cleaving permissiveness towards Cas9 than nucleosomes with strong interactions to DNA. Interestingly, the cleaving efficiency around the nucleosome dyad was comparably low in both cases. Furthermore, when repeating the same experiments with the addition of the chromatin remodeler SNF2H or RSC, Cas9 cleavage efficiency was significantly enhanced [441].

The obstruction of CRISPR/Cas by proteins is not limited to nucleosomes. In the case of SpCas9 (*Streptococcus pyogenes*), which is known to remain bound to both DNA ends after cleavage [442], RNA polymerase was able to dislodge the Cas9 protein when targeted to the template strand. This resulted in increased editing efficiency due to the release of both cleaved DNA ends and the onset of the DNA repair machinery [443]. This might however only be true for SpCas9 because in the case of SaCas9 (*Staphylococcus aureus*) [444] and AsCas12a (*Acidaminococcus* sp.) [445] it was shown that these proteins automatically release one DNA strand some hours after the catalytic event.

Apart from the sgRNA annealing site itself, post-PAM interactions were found to be important for stable interactions between the Cas protein and the DNA. SpCas9 was not able to remain in a place of the target site when the DNA sequence 14 base pairs downstream was occupied by another protein. It was observed that this post-PAM interaction is weak in force but very crucial for Cas9 binding and cleavage [446]. Displacement mediated by disturbance of the post-PAM accessibility can also happen after the association of SpCas9 to the DNA. In the case of SaCas9, the post-PAM interaction was only around seven base-pairs and had a much lesser effect than on SpCas9 [446]. SaCas9, in stark contrast to SpCas9, represented a significant barrier for other proteins such as DNA-tracking motors [444]. Zhang and co-workers give a nice comparison of interactions strength between SaCas9 and SpCas9 mediated by different regions across the footprint [444].

Methylated DNA could be cleaved without problems by Cas9 [447] and also CRISPRa approaches had been successful when the target area had DNA-methylated sites [442].

The examples from above show that the proteome of the target site can have a profound impact on the binding and residence time and therefore cleavage efficiency of CRISPR/Cas. Structures that statically occupy and block the DNA such as nucleosomes should be avoided when choosing a target site for CRISPR/Cas applications.

Off-target annealing has different consequences, depending on the application (i.e., Cas vs. dead-Cas). Cleavage at off-target locations depends on PAM sequence and guide-RNA homology. Two major concerns about the deployment of CRISPR/Cas systems are the possibility of off-target effects (i.e., annealing to a not intended stretch of DNA) and the restriction that CRISPR/Cas systems need a specific PAM sequence for annealing. An interesting finding in case of off-target activity of Cas9 was, that the RNP complex could bind to many off-targets, even with a seed sequence complementarity of only five nts (seed: 6–12 nts or 5 nts proximal to the PAM sequence for SpCas9 [448] or FnCas12a [394,435] respectively). However, for proper catalytic function, a complementary gRNA of at least 17 nts was found to be necessary. In the case of Cas9, proper initial binding of the Cas9-sgRNA complex to the DNA is mainly mediated by PAM interaction and complementary forces between the DNA and the seed region of the sgRNA. In a second step, Cas9 cleaves after sufficient pairing of the 5'-end of the guide RNA [449]. This model would explain why binding of Cas9 to the target site can even occur in case of little homology between

sgRNA and target site but cleavage is nevertheless impaired due to low overall homology between sgRNA and target sequence.

The PAMs and, therefore, the possible annealing/cutting sites are different for Cas9 and Cas12a and are one of the biggest limitations of these tools. As already mentioned, Cas9 has a G-rich while Cas12a variants have T-rich PAMs. To circumvent these limitations, protein engineering performed on Cas9 and Cas12a led to the development of near-PAM-less [450] or PAM-flexible [451–454] variants with increased off-target activity. But also high fidelity (HF) [455] variants have been engineered. Even combinations of both variants exist which compensate for the increased off-target activity of near-PAM-less or PAM-flexible variants [453,454]. It is of importance that the sgRNA/crRNA design has to account for the flexible PAM. It must not enable the Cas protein to anneal to the gRNA expression cassette itself which could lead to cleavage or transcriptional blockage. To assess the (off-target) cleavage pattern of a specific Cas-sgRNA complex *in vivo*, the GUIDE-SEQ approach can be applied which performs an unbiased detection of CRISPR/Cas-mediated double-strand breaks (DSBs) by *in vivo* integration of an oligo at sites that have DSBs (i.e., on- and off-target loci) and subsequent amplification and next-generation sequencing [456].

The information above should illustrate the many application forms and variants of CRISPR/Cas systems. There is not a one for all experimental strategy because the prerequisites of the experimental question determine not only the variant of CRISPR/Cas to be deployed but also the target genetic features (i.e., gene body in case of gene knockouts but promoters in case of activation via CRISPRa approaches) and their connected properties (i.e., PAM, proteomic occupancy, sequence bias) that have to be considered during gRNA design. In fungal organisms, mutational CRISPR approaches are already widely implemented. In the case of CRISPRa or targeted chromatin remodeling, however, this technology is still in its infancy but harbors great potential of the activation of BGCs and the discovery of new bioactive metabolites in the future.

7. Perspectives

Genome mining is a core component in the revelation of unknown BGCs in fungal genomes. The data sources that are used for predictions are very diverse across the platforms and include not only DNA or protein sequences but also transcript data, phylogenetic data, and more. Deploying more and more predictive parameters that are connected to BGCs and their regulation will surely promote the discovery of new BGCs in the future. Increasing insights into novel BGC types (i.e., gene types, protein domains, genomic arrangement, backbone genes, etc.) will also lead to a transition from “high novelty/low reliability” to “low novelty/high reliability” BGC prediction algorithms which, in turn, again increases their discovery rate. Approaches for the detection of novel BGC types are very diverse and will surely enable us to discover new and currently unknown BGC types in heavily researched model organisms.

The development of these tools, however, is similar to a feedback loop between prediction and experimental verification. Predictions of known BGCs largely depend on the detection of patterns from already verified BGC types and so, the provision of high-quality experimental verification data of BGCs is a crucial component of reliable predictions. Curated databases fulfill these requirements but need the regular attention of professionals in the field. The guided deposition of such data by the research group itself into curated databases will hopefully become a standard procedure within the publication process in the future. This would increase the reliability of predictions and also accelerate the discovery process of BGCs in fungal genomes and, hence, the development of novel pharmaceuticals.

CRISPR/Cas technology is emerging as a new tool and already has proven to deliver new molecules by the activation of silent BGCs in a number of organisms. Its functionality as a transcriptional activator was already experimentally shown in fungi by fusing the trans-activator VPR to dCas9 and dCas12a. Heterochromatic regions, however, could get problematic because of target site accessibility and the sole deployment of trans-activator domains.

The targeted local histone modifications could represent the next step in the toolbox for the activation of silent BGCs. If it is possible to relieve heterochromatic regions of silent marks (i.e., H3K27me3, H3K9me3), the targeted and locus-specific transition to transcriptionally active euchromatin could be within reach. The choice of the right histone-modification domain, however, is still a topic that needs thorough research. Many observations that connect transcriptional activation and histone modification indicate that H3K9 acetylation (gene activation especially in the case of BGCs), deployed by Rtt109 and GcnE, and H3K27 acetylation (hallmark for open chromatin and de-repression in *N. crassa*), also deployed by GcnE, within the promoter region correlate best with gene activation across several fungal species. As there are often nucleosome-free regions in promoters, even within heterochromatin, nucleosome positioning maps assist with the choice of a proper entry point of dCas-fusion proteins. Depending on the target locus and the prevalent histone marks, additional activators (e.g., VPR) could be necessary to induce target genes. H3S28ph also seems a promising way of activating single genes but more research, especially in the fungal context is needed in this regard. Furthermore, if DNA motifs are also proven to be responsible for occurring histone marks in fungi, this would be an additional opportunity to relieve whole BGCs from heterochromatin. This way, the programmable histone modifier can be used in combination with these mutants to activate silent BGCs and reveal their biosynthetic product.

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